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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the conception and execution of the survey on training needs in digital preservation and curation carried out in the context of the DigCurV project. It summarises the main findings of the survey together with those from a series of focus group meetings held in the partner countries and also an analysis of job advertisements which have appeared since January 2011 when the project began.

A report on the detailed analysis of the survey results is available in English from the [DigCurV website](#) and is also attached as an appendix to this deliverable.

Section 2 gives an overview of the three components of the research carried out.

Section 3, after an introduction, presents the results of the survey on training needs that was carried out in July and August 2011. The survey aimed at identifying the skills and competences needed for digital preservation and curation as well as the needs for vocational education and training in this field. It was structured into four parts that concentrated on basic information about the respondent's organisation, training plans and preferences, the skills and competences required and the training needs.

The survey received 454 valid responses from 44 countries, with the majority of them coming from Europe. The participants represent a broad spectrum of organisations from the cultural heritage as well as the scientific and education sectors and are engaged in a variety of activities with regard to digital preservation and curation.

The data collected shows that the overwhelming majority of organisations face the challenge of digital preservation and curation. About three quarters of the institutions in our survey already store digital materials for long-term preservation and almost a fifth are planning to do so in the future. Despite this fact, more than half of the organisations do not intend to hire new staff for digital preservation activities. In many cases it seems likely that the tasks associated with the long-term storage of digital assets will be assigned to existing staff who will need to acquire the necessary skills and competences if they do not have these already. Thus the survey results suggest there is likely to be a substantial need for appropriate training amongst these organisations.

A significant number of the survey respondents stated that their organisation is planning training for digital preservation staff. One particular training method and time frame clearly stood out in the responses: Small group workshops were by far the most popular method, regarded as most suitable by about 75% of the survey population, followed by blended learning, i.e. a mixture of face-to-face instruction and online components (favoured by about 38% of the respondents). Short-term events were the most popular option with one-time events of 1-2 workdays, chosen by about 55% of the participants, followed by one-time events of 3-5 work days (mentioned by about 30% of the respondents).

When asked to assess the importance of a range of general, as well as a number of digital preservation-specific and technical skills for the work of digital preservation staff, respondents indicated that almost all of the given general skills were highly relevant. Collaborating with others, communicating with others and affinity for technology were indicated to be of particular importance. Of the digital preservation-specific and technical skills, virtually all were indicated to be of high importance by respondents.

Accordingly, a high degree of training need is signified for both digital preservation-specific and technical skills and for the general skills. With respect to digital preservation-specific and technical areas, general/ basic knowledge of digital preservation issues, preservation and data management planning and preservation tools were the areas where the survey results suggest the highest training need. In terms of general skills, the survey suggests the highest degree of training need lies in the areas of liaising between customers and information technology experts, and communicating with others.

Although there is also a considerable training need in terms of general skills, the survey participants clearly prioritised digital preservation-specific and technical skills as being the most pressing areas where training is required. General/basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning, and preservation tools were ranked most highly in this regard.

The findings with respect to involvement in digital preservation activities, the training plans of the organisations and the assessment of training needs all suggest that there is a great demand for training with regard to digital preservation and curation.

Section 4 gives a summary of the analysis of the focus groups that were conducted to gather additional information from stakeholders. The findings support the results of the survey analysis. The participants reported a severe lack of professionals with the appropriate skills for digital preservation and curation both among existing staff of their institutions and

potential staff on the labour market. They expressed an urgent need for training, particularly with regard to IT skills and technical digital preservation skills. Generic skills, management skills and the ability to train others have also been indicated as areas with a considerable training need.

Section 5 presents the analysis of 48 job advertisements for positions in the field of digital preservation and curation. The information obtained with regard to the tasks, skills and competences relevant in the field of digital preservation and curation underpins the findings of the survey and the focus groups. The task responsibilities and the corresponding skills, competences and knowledge are wide-ranging and cover many digital preservation-specific and technical as well as general areas.

Section 6 synthesises the findings and draws conclusions. The results of the research suggest a great demand for training in digital preservation and curation that arises from a serious lack of qualified staff in the field. The findings revealed a broad spectrum of skills and competences relevant for staff involved in digital preservation. When designing training, this diversity as well as the integration of practical application and the suitability of the format for working staff should be taken into account.

This report together with the report on the baseline survey on training opportunities and the evaluation framework will be used as a background for developing a curriculum framework for vocational education and training in the field.

2. Introduction

This report presents the results of a survey on training needs in the field of digital preservation and curation run by the Digital Curator Vocational Education Europe (DigCurV) project. DigCurV aims to address the availability of vocational training and education in digital preservation and curation to staff working in cultural heritage organisations by developing a curriculum framework and building a network of stakeholders. The results of this review of sector training needs together with the results of a review of existing training initiatives will inform the development of the DigCurV curriculum.

The project set out to identify the need for vocational education and training in the field of digital preservation and curation. It carried out research by using three methods:

1. **Online survey**

An online stakeholder survey on the training needs in digital preservation and curation was carried out in July and August 2011; the results are presented in Chapter 3 and Appendix A.

2. **Focus groups**

A series of focus groups were held in the partner countries between September and November 2011. These structured group discussions aimed to gather additional information on training needs from stakeholders. The findings from the focus groups are summarised in Chapter 4.

3. **Analysis of job advertisements**

From February 2011 to January 2012, DigCurV collected 48 job advertisements from the UK, Germany, the USA, New Zealand and Australia. These were analysed with regard to the tasks associated with the advertised jobs as well as the according skills, competences and qualifications required of the prospective job holders. The results of this analysis of job descriptions are presented in Chapter 5 of this deliverable.

3. Survey of Training Needs

3.1 Conception and Execution of the survey

The survey was conducted from 4th July to 26th August 2011¹. The target audience of the survey comprised of staff members of libraries, archives, museums and other cultural heritage institutions as well as of organisations of the scientific and education sector, such as universities. Invitations to participate in the survey were disseminated by DigCurV partners in their country or region as well as to the international community via email lists relevant for the target audience. In total, 491 respondents completed the survey. After 37 largely incomplete responses were taken out there were 454 responses for analysis.

The survey was structured into four parts:

1. Basic information about the respondent's organisation
2. Training plans and preferences
3. Skills and competences needed for digital preservation and curation
4. Training needs in digital preservation and curation

The first part collected general information about the participants' organisations, such as the country, the type and the size of the organisations. It asked the participants to indicate the tasks they perform in their day to day work and questions about their organisation's involvement in digital preservation activities, i.e. if there is storage of digital materials, if yes, what kind of staff and how many are responsible for the associated tasks.

The second part focused on training. This part contained questions about the institutions' plans for training in digital preservation matters as well as the existence of a training budget and training facilities. Respondents were asked which training method and time frame for training they considered the most suitable for their organisation and if it was important that training was certified.

Part 3 concentrated on the skills and competences that are required for digital preservation and curation. Two lists of tasks and skills (with each item representing a task and the required skill or competence to fulfil this task alike) were presented to the respondents. One comprised general tasks and skills, which are relevant for digital preservation but also in other contexts, such as communication or management tasks and skills. A second list

¹ Five late responses were received in the two weeks after the deadline (26th August 2011). These were included in the survey analysis.

contained digital preservation-specific and technical tasks and skills. The participants were asked to assess the importance of each skill in terms of the work of staff involved in digital preservation and curation.

After identifying the necessary skills for digital preservation and curation, the questions in the last part of the survey aimed at assessing the need for training with regard to the several skills and competences. Again, there were two lists of items – one containing general skills, the other digital preservation-specific and technical areas. A copy of the questionnaire is provided in the appendix.

The compilation of the lists of tasks, skills and competences for part 3 and 4 of the survey was based on previous research and literature on the topic, such as the OAIS reference model², the DCC curation lifecycle model³, the DPOE's training needs assessment survey⁴, the work of Scheffel, Osswald and Neuroth (2010) on qualification in the field of digital preservation⁵ as well as the paper on education for eScience professionals⁶ of Kim, Addom and Stanton (2011).

² <http://public.ccsds.org/publications/archive/650x0b1.pdf>

and http://nestor.sub.uni-goettingen.de/handbuch/artikel/nestor_handbuch_artikel_474.pdf

³ <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-lifecycle-model>

⁴ <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/education/documents/DPOENeedsAssessmentSurveyExecutiveSummary.pdf>

⁵ http://nestor.sub.uni-goettingen.de/handbuch/artikel/nestor_handbuch_artikel_468.pdf

⁶ <http://www.ijdc.net/index.php/ijdc/article/view/168/236>

3.2 Summary of the training needs survey results

In total, the survey received 454 responses. The majority of participants (81.3%) were from Europe. Among these, the largest proportion came from the countries of the DigCurV partners (Germany, the UK, Ireland, Italy and Lithuania) who together made up 53.9% of the total survey population. 14.0% of the responses received were from North America. Other countries were underrepresented, forming merely 4.7% of the total population.

The survey participants were affiliated to a broad spectrum of organisations from the cultural heritage as well as the scientific and education sectors. Cultural heritage institutions were represented by large proportions of respondents (archives by 24.4%, research and university libraries by 23.8%, national, federal or legal deposit libraries by 14.5% and museums by 10.8%). Organisation related to science and education were also well represented (universities 18.1%, research centres 11.5%, scientific associations 2.0% and research and university libraries 23.8%). Many (18.7%) respondents indicated that they were affiliated to institutions which we had not included in the list of options, such as broadcasters and national, state or local authorities.

The size of the organisations the survey respondents were affiliated to reflected the distribution that we had anticipated. The largest proportion of respondents (45.3%) came from small institutions with up to 100 FTEs (full time equivalents). About a third (30.3%) were employed at middle-sized organisations of 101-500 FTEs. Roughly a quarter (24.4%) came from large institutions with more than 500 FTEs.

The survey participants were involved in a variety of activities related to digital preservation and curation, ranging from management tasks to functional tasks as well as training, education and research.

About three quarters (75.7%) of the participant's organisations are already storing digital materials for long-term preservation. Another 18.1% plan to store materials for long term preservation in the future. Merely 6.2% of the institutions neither store nor intend to store digital assets.

Of the organisations that store digital materials, 62.8% reported employing core-funded staff partly assigned to digital preservation tasks, 30.8% reported core-funded staff exclusively assigned to digital preservation tasks. Respondents stated that in some institutions digital preservation duties are fulfilled by externally funded staff either exclusively (12.3%) or partly

(10.8%) assigned to digital preservation. 12.0% of the respondents from organisations holding digital materials stated that there was no staff that was assigned to the related tasks.

The vast majority (93.8%) of the institutions in our survey face the challenge of digital preservation. However, 57.3% do not intend to hire new staff for digital preservation duties. 31.0% of the respondents indicated plans to hire staff who is partly assigned to this field of activity, 16.7% indicate that their organisations intend to hire exclusively assigned staff for digital preservation. With regard to the large proportion of institutions that do not intend to hire new digital preservation staff, it seems likely that the tasks associated with the long-term storage of digital materials will be assigned to existing staff who will need training to acquire or develop the necessary skills and competences. This suggests that there will be a considerable need for appropriate training offers arising from these circumstances.

A considerable proportion of respondents stated that their organisation is planning training for digital preservation staff. 35.4% signify that there will be training for staff with no previous experience in the subject matter, 31.4% say that there are plans to train staff that has already got some experience in digital preservation and curation. However, there is also a percentage of 35.1% that indicate that there are no training plans for digital preservation staff.

With regard to the training methods that are regarded as most suitable for their organisation by the respondents, one method clearly stood out – small group work shops were favoured by 75.3%. Blended learning (a mixture of face-to-face instruction and online training) was favoured by 38.6% and ranked as the second most popular form of training. The other methods suggested (written manuals, one-to-one training by a senior staff member, online training and large group workshops) were by far less popular.

In terms of the time frame considered most suitable, the trend is similar. By far the most popular time frame (mentioned by 55.3% of the respondents) were one time training events of 1-2 work days. Next in line, with a percentage of 29.8% were one time events of 3-5 work days. Training forms that require more time, such as course of 1-4 hours a week for one or more semesters or recurring 1-2 week block courses for several semesters were regarded less suitable. The comments for this question suggest this pattern of preferences is related to time constraints caused by heavy workloads.

The survey participants were asked to assess the importance of certain tasks and skills for the work of digital preservation staff. They were presented with two sets, one referring to

general tasks and skills, such as management or communication skills, the other referring to digital preservation-specific and technical skills.

In terms of general tasks and skills, three items were clearly indicated as the most important – collaborating with others, communicating with others and affinity for technology. These areas are regarded either essential or important by more than 95% of the respondents.

As for digital preservation-specific and technical tasks and skills, all of the given options were ranked as being of a high importance, with 90% of participants considering all these tasks and skills to be either essential or important.

The need for training was stated to be substantial for the digital-preservation specific and technical skills as well as for the general skills.

With regard to the general skills, between 60.6% and 85.4% of the respondents indicated either a great or moderate need for training. The greatest need for training is stated in terms of liaising between customers and information technology experts.

When looking at the digital preservation-specific and technical skills, the high degree of need for training expressed by the participants is striking. For each of the given areas (general/basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning, preservation tools, information modelling and metadata, trusted repositories, strategic planning and policies, technical systems and legal aspects) between 86.2% and 96.2% of respondents signified a great or moderate need for training. General/basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning and preservation tools were the areas rated with the highest need.

Although the survey recorded a considerable training need in terms of general skills, the most pressing need prioritised by respondents is for digital preservation-specific and technical skills. The areas where the survey results suggest the most pressing need are general/basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning, and preservation tools with 48.9%, 48,7% and 38.2% of respondents identifying these as the priority areas for training.

4. Summary of the Focus Groups Analysis

To gather additional information on the training needs in the field, DigCurV conducted a series of nine focus groups with stakeholders. These were carried out in the DigCurV partner countries (Germany, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania and the UK) in autumn 2011.

Focus groups can be described as structured group discussions on a specific topic. The participants have in common certain characteristics that relate to this topic. The groups are held in a permissive environment to make the participants feel comfortable and free to share their thoughts and opinions about the matter in question⁷.

The DigCurV focus groups aimed at identifying the skills and competences needed for digital preservation and curation as well as the corresponding training needs. The discussions started with a brief introduction and then moved on to the challenges that the participants perceived with respect to digital preservation and curation. Thereafter, the participants were asked to indicate the skills and competences that they regarded necessary for staff involved in the field and to develop a number of ideal job profiles including the relevant task and skills. Subsequently, the training needs with respect to the skills and competences elaborated before were assessed. The session closed with a discussion about suitable formats for training and the relevance of accreditation or certification.

In terms of challenges related to digital preservation and curation, the participants reported a lack of properly skilled staff in the field as well as a lack of training offers. With respect to the skill-sets of both existing and potential staff, especially the combination of technical expertise, information science and subject knowledge as well as communication skills is hard to find. In addition, a general lack of awareness was stated for the importance of digital preservation among many organisations.

According to the participants, the skills and competences required for digital preservation and curation cover a broad spectrum that ranges from technical expertise, IT knowledge and digital preservation-specific skills to social skills, management skills, and knowledge of the organisation, the subject domain as well as library, archival or information science. These manifold requirements are also reflected in the different job profiles that were elaborated by the participants.

⁷ See: Krueger, Richard A.; Casey, Mary Ann: Focus Groups. A Practical Guide for Applied Research. 4th edition. Los Angeles: Sage 2009, pp. 2 et sqq.

In terms of training in digital preservation and curation, the participants stated an urgent need, particularly with regard to IT skills and technical digital preservation skills. However, generic skills, management skills and the ability to train others have also been indicated as areas with a considerable training need. Furthermore, for Ireland and Lithuania, participants also reported a great need for introductory training.

With regard to suitable training methods, blended learning, courses of one to two weeks length and short-term courses of a few days were the most frequently mentioned forms. Several participants also expressed a need for long-term courses, such as a 1-2 year master's degree. In addition, some participants stated the necessity to rearrange the curricula of basic professional education and training of cultural heritage professionals to integrate digital preservation and curation issues.

In the majority of the groups, the participants stressed the importance of accreditation or certification – for staff as a proof of their qualification, and for employers as a benchmark which could be referred to during the recruitment process. However, other participants, particularly from the management level, held the opinion that the need for skilled staff is so great, that certification is rather irrelevant when recruiting staff.

The results of the focus groups reflect the difficult situation that many cultural heritage organisations are struggling with at present. They have to rise to the challenges that result from the growing importance of digital materials – including long-term preservation and curation. To be able to do this, they need qualified staff. The focus group participants indicated a severe lack of staff in this area as well as great difficulties in finding professionals with the appropriate skills and competences on the labour market. On top of this, they also state a lack of training offers that could help existing staff to up-skill. They express an urgent need for training, particularly in terms of technical and IT skills, but also with regard to other areas such as communication and management.

The findings of the focus groups are in accordance with the results of the survey. Both indicate that there is a great demand for training in the field of digital preservation and curation. The results suggest that, in the longer term, there is an interest in the accreditation of courses. However, in view of the urgent demand for staff, certification is not the immediate concern.

5. Summary of the Job Description Analysis

To gather information on the skills and competences being requested by employers, DigCurV has collected job descriptions for analysis.

From February 2011 to January 2012, forty-eight⁸ job advertisements were collected of posts related to the area of digital preservation and curation⁹. The job descriptions¹⁰ included in these advertisements were analysed with regard to the tasks the prospective job holders would be responsible for, the required skills, competences, experiences and knowledge as well as the degrees and qualifications. The findings of the analysis provide supplementary information to the results of the survey and the focus groups and are summarised below (see Appendix C for the full analysis).

The analysis of job descriptions shows that the task responsibilities of professionals working in the field of digital preservation and curation are varied and cover a broad spectrum. Tasks include generic activities as well as activities that are of technical nature and/or specific to the field. The general fields of activity include communications, outreach and liaison, project management, teaching and training, supervisory and grants and funding. The most frequently mentioned digital preservation-specific or technical task areas are digital collection and data management, digital curation and preservation, trusted repository and archive, technical tasks as well as best practice and documentation.

Corresponding to the extensive scope of task responsibilities, the skills, competences and knowledge sought in ideal candidates are broad. Communication, collaboration and team work skills as well as project management skills stand out with regard to general skills, being required or indicated as desirable in the majority of job descriptions. In terms of the digital preservation and technical skills, the requirements specify a variety of areas including: digital archives, digital library collections, trusted repositories, lifecycle data management, information technology, programming, metadata, current long term preservation tools as well as policies, standards and best practices. In many cases, not only theoretical knowledge was required, but also practical experience.

⁸ Two job descriptions were for three open positions; one job description was for two open positions. The forty-eight job descriptions collected represent a total of fifty-three open posts.

⁹ Please note that the collection is neither exhaustive nor representative.

¹⁰ In the analysis we focused on the job description part of the advertisements. Therefore, we use the terms “job advertisement” and “job description” almost synonymically.

The job descriptions expressed a strong preference for an advanced degree; most of them stated that a master's degree or equivalent would be required. The preferred fields of study were Library and Information Science and Archival Studies or Science, with many job descriptions stating that a relevant academic field, such as Information Science, Computer Science or Humanities, would also be acceptable.

The information obtained from the job descriptions with regard to the tasks, skills and competences relevant in the field of digital preservation and curation underpins the findings of the survey. The task responsibilities and the corresponding skills, competences and knowledge are wide-ranging and cover many digital preservation-specific and technical as well as general areas. This diversity should be taken into account when designing training.

6. Summary and Conclusion

The findings of our research illustrate the difficult situation many organisations of the cultural heritage sector as well as scientific institutions find themselves in at the moment. More than 90% of the survey respondents stated that their organisation already stores or plans to store digital materials for long-term preservation. However, around 12% of them also indicated that there are no staff assigned to the corresponding tasks. This particularly applies to smaller institutions, which constitute the majority of cultural heritage organisations. In addition, more than half of the respondents reported that their organisation does not plan to hire staff for digital preservation tasks in the future. In their comments, many respondents pointed out that budget constraints are the main reason for this. Some also noted that there are not enough skilled candidates on the labour market.

The lack of properly skilled staff is also brought up as a major issue by the focus group participants. Again, the reasons given for this are a lack of funding that prevents the hiring of new staff and a lack of qualified applicants. In terms of the latter, it is particularly difficult to find professionals with both subject or domain knowledge and technical expertise. Another challenge is the ongoing and constant rate of change in the field. This requires staff to permanently keep up to date with new developments. Across the groups participants stated a lack of appropriate training offers.

In summary, the findings described above suggest a great demand for training in digital preservation and curation to help the staff of cultural heritage institutions to acquire the skills and competences needed to take care of digital holdings.

The information gathered in the survey, the focus groups and the job description analysis consistently indicates that the necessary skills and competences are wide-ranging and cover various areas. Among them, digital preservation-specific skills and technical expertise are regarded crucial. But a number of generic skills are considered equally important, particularly social skills, such as communication and collaborating with others.

In the survey, all of the given options for digital preservation-specific and technical skills were considered to be either important or essential by more than 90% of the respondents. They included: preservation planning, ensuring access, managing data, evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation, storing data, ingesting data, research, development and implementation of digital preservation environments and administering the archive. As for the general skills, collaborating with others, communicating with others and affinity for technology

stood out with more than 95% of the respondents considering them to be either essential or important. Managing projects and training others were considered to be of high importance as well.

Other areas mentioned in this respect in the focus groups and the job descriptions include: knowledge of the organisation and the subject domain as well as archival, library or information science. In addition, people working in the field should ideally have an open minded attitude, the willingness to learn, the ability to think in structures and processes as well as a solution-focused way of thinking.

Both the respondents of the survey and the focus group participants indicate a substantial need for training with respect to digital preservation-specific and technical skills as well as general skills.

In terms of the digital preservation-specific and technical skills, the percentage of survey respondents signifying a great or moderate training need was between 86% and 96% for each of the given areas (including general/ basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning, preservation tools, information modelling and metadata, trusted repositories, strategic planning and policies, technical systems and legal aspects).

With regard to the general skills, between 60% and 85% of the respondents indicated either a great or moderate need for training. The greatest need for training is stated in terms of liaising between customers and information technology experts, followed by communication, project management and networking with people.

The areas where the survey results suggest the most pressing need are general and basic knowledge of digital preservation issues, preservation and data management planning, and preservation tools.

With respect to the training methods that were regarded as most suitable for their organisation by the survey respondents, one method clearly stood out – small group work shops were favoured by 75.3%. Blended learning (a mixture of face-to-face instruction and online training) was favoured by 38.6% and ranked as the second most popular form of training.

In terms of the time frame considered most suitable, the trend in the survey is similar. By far the most popular time frame was one time training events of 1-2 work days. Next in line were

one time events of 3-5 work days. Training forms that require more time, such as courses of 1-4 hours a week for one or more semesters or recurring 1-2 week block courses for several semesters were regarded less suitable. The comments for this question suggest this pattern of preferences is related to time constraints caused by heavy workloads.

The best method and time frame indicated by the focus group participants are similar, but not exactly the same. Three forms of training were frequently mentioned across the groups: blended learning, courses of one to two weeks' length and short-term courses of a few days. Blended learning emerged as the most popular method, because it allows working staff to reconcile job and training more easily. Several participants also advocated long-term courses, such as a 1-2 year master's degree, as well as the restructuring of the basic professional education and training for library, archive and museum professionals to integrate at least basic knowledge of digital preservation and curation issues. In addition, participants stressed the importance of building a bridge between theory and practical application.

In conclusion, the results of the research suggest a great demand for training in digital preservation and curation that arises from a severe lack of qualified staff in the field. The findings revealed a broad spectrum of skills and competences relevant for staff involved in digital preservation. When designing training, this diversity as well as the integration of practical application and the suitability of the format for working staff should be taken into account.

Appendix: Report and analysis of the survey of Training Needs

1. Executive Summary

This report describes the conception and execution of the survey on training needs in digital preservation and curation carried out in the context of the DigCurV project. It summarises the main findings of the survey together with those from a series of focus group meetings held in the partner countries and also an analysis of job advertisements which have appeared since January 2011 when the project began.

Section 2 gives an overview of the three components of the research carried out.

Section 3, after an introduction, presents the results of the survey on training needs that was carried out in July and August 2011. The survey aimed at identifying the skills and competences needed for digital preservation and curation as well as the needs for vocational education and training in this field. It was structured into four parts that concentrated on basic information about the respondent's organisation, training plans and preferences, the skills and competences required and the training needs.

The survey received 454 valid responses from 44 countries, with the majority of them coming from Europe. The participants represent a broad spectrum of organisations from the cultural heritage as well as the scientific and education sectors and are engaged in a variety of activities with regard to digital preservation and curation.

The data collected shows that the overwhelming majority of organisations face the challenge of digital preservation and curation. About three quarters of the institutions in our survey already store digital materials for long-term preservation and almost a fifth are planning to do so in the future. Despite this fact, more than half of the organisations do not intend to hire new staff for digital preservation activities. In many cases it seems likely that the tasks associated with the long-term storage of digital assets will be assigned to existing staff who will need to acquire the necessary skills and competences if they do not have these already. Thus the survey results suggest there is likely to be a substantial need for appropriate training amongst these organisations.

A significant number of the survey respondents stated that their organisation is planning training for digital preservation staff. One particular training method and time frame clearly stood out in the responses: Small group workshops were by far the most popular method, regarded as most suitable by about 75% of the survey population, followed by blended learning, i.e. a mixture of face-to-face instruction and online components (favoured by about 38% of the respondents). Short-term events were the most popular option with one-time events of 1-2 workdays, chosen by about 55% of the participants, followed by one-time events of 3-5 work days (mentioned by about 30% of the respondents).

When asked to assess the importance of a range of general, as well as a number of digital preservation-specific and technical skills for the work of digital preservation staff, respondents indicated that almost all of the given general skills were highly relevant. Collaborating with others, communicating with others and affinity for technology were indicated to be of particular importance. Of the digital preservation-specific and technical skills, virtually all were indicated to be of high importance by respondents.

Accordingly, a high degree of training need is signified for both digital preservation-specific and technical skills and for the general skills. With respect to digital preservation-specific and technical areas, general/ basic knowledge of digital preservation issues, preservation and data management planning and preservation tools were the areas where the survey results suggest the highest training need. In terms of general skills, the survey suggests the highest degree of training need lies in the areas of liaising between customers and information technology experts, and communicating with others.

Although there is also a considerable training need in terms of general skills, the survey participants clearly prioritised digital preservation-specific and technical skills as being the most pressing areas where training is required. General/basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning, and preservation tools were ranked most highly in this regard.

The findings with respect to involvement in digital preservation activities, the training plans of the organisations and the assessment of training needs all suggest that there is a great demand for training with regard to digital preservation and curation.

Section 4 gives a summary of the analysis of the focus groups that were conducted to gather additional information from stakeholders. The findings support the results of the survey analysis. The participants reported a severe lack of professionals with the appropriate skills for digital preservation and curation both among existing staff of their institutions and

potential staff on the labour market. They expressed an urgent need for training, particularly with regard to IT skills and technical digital preservation skills. Generic skills, management skills and the ability to train others have also been indicated as areas with a considerable training need.

Section 5 presents the analysis of 48 job advertisements for positions in the field of digital preservation and curation. The information obtained with regard to the tasks, skills and competences relevant in the field of digital preservation and curation underpins the findings of the survey and the focus groups. The task responsibilities and the corresponding skills, competences and knowledge are wide-ranging and cover many digital preservation-specific and technical as well as general areas.

Section 6 synthesises the findings and draws conclusions. The results of the research suggest a great demand for training in digital preservation and curation that arises from a serious lack of qualified staff in the field. The findings revealed a broad spectrum of skills and competences relevant for staff involved in digital preservation. When designing training, this diversity as well as the integration of practical application and the suitability of the format for working staff should be taken into account.

This report together with the report on the baseline survey on training opportunities and the evaluation framework will be used as a background for developing a curriculum framework for vocational education and training in the field.

2. Introduction

This report presents the results of a survey on training needs in the field of digital preservation and curation run by the Digital Curator Vocational Education Europe (DigCurV) project. DigCurV aims to address the availability of vocational training and education in digital preservation and curation to staff working in cultural heritage organisations by developing a curriculum framework and building a network of stakeholders. The results of this review of sector training needs together with the results of a review of existing training initiatives will inform the development of the DigCurV curriculum.

The project set out to identify the need for vocational education and training in the field of digital preservation and curation. It carried out research by using three methods:

1. Online survey

An online stakeholder survey on the training needs in digital preservation and curation was carried out in July and August 2011; the results are presented in Chapter 3 and the appendix.

2. Focus groups

A series of focus groups were held in the partner countries between September and November 2011. These structured group discussions aimed to gather additional information on training needs from stakeholders. The findings from the focus groups are summarised in Chapter 4.

3. Analysis of job advertisements

From February 2011 to January 2012, DigCurV collected 48 job advertisements from the UK, Germany, the USA, New Zealand and Australia. These were analysed with regard to the tasks associated with the advertised jobs as well as the according skills, competences and qualifications required of the prospective job holders. The results of this analysis of job advertisements are presented in Chapter 5 of this deliverable.

3. Survey of Training Needs

3.1 Conception and Execution of the survey

The survey was conducted from 4th July to 26th August 2011¹¹. The target audience of the survey comprised of staff members of libraries, archives, museums and other cultural heritage institutions as well as of organisations of the scientific and education sector, such as universities. Invitations to participate in the survey were disseminated by DigCurV partners in their country or region as well as to the international community via email lists relevant for the target audience. In total, 491 respondents completed the survey. After 37 largely incomplete responses were taken out there were 454 responses for analysis.

The survey was structured into four parts:

1. Basic information about the respondent's organisation
2. Training plans and preferences
3. Skills and competences needed for digital preservation and curation
4. Training needs in digital preservation and curation

The first part collected general information about the participants' organisations, such as the country, the type and the size of the organisations. It asked the participants to indicate the tasks they perform in their day to day work and questions about their organisation's involvement in digital preservation activities, i.e. if there is storage of digital materials, if yes, what kind of staff and how many are responsible for the associated tasks.

The second part focused on training. This part contained questions about the institutions' plans for training in digital preservation matters as well as the existence of a training budget and training facilities. Respondents were asked which training method and time frame for training they considered the most suitable for their organisation and if it was important that training was certified.

Part 3 concentrated on the skills and competences that are required for digital preservation and curation. Two lists of tasks and skills (with each item representing a task and the required skill or competence to fulfil this task alike) were presented to the respondents. One comprised general tasks and skills, which are relevant for digital preservation but also in other contexts, such as communication or management tasks and skills. A second list

¹¹ Five late responses were received in the two weeks after the deadline (26th August 2011). These were included in the survey analysis.

contained digital preservation-specific and technical tasks and skills. The participants were asked to assess the importance of each skill in terms of the work of staff involved in digital preservation and curation.

After identifying the necessary skills for digital preservation and curation, the questions in the last part of the survey aimed at assessing the need for training with regard to the several skills and competences. Again, there were two lists of items – one containing general skills, the other digital preservation-specific and technical areas. A copy of the questionnaire is provided in the appendix.

The compilation of the lists of tasks, skills and competences for part 3 and 4 of the survey was based on previous research and literature on the topic, such as the OAIS reference model¹², the DCC curation lifecycle model¹³, the DPOE's training needs assessment survey¹⁴, the work of Scheffel, Osswald and Neuroth (2010) on qualification in the field of digital preservation¹⁵ as well as the paper on education for eScience professionals¹⁶ of Kim, Addom and Stanton (2011).

¹² <http://public.ccsds.org/publications/archive/650x0b1.pdf>

and http://nestor.sub.uni-goettingen.de/handbuch/artikel/nestor_handbuch_artikel_474.pdf

¹³ <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-lifecycle-model>

¹⁴ <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/education/documents/DPOENeedsAssessmentSurveyExecutiveSummary.pdf>

¹⁵ http://nestor.sub.uni-goettingen.de/handbuch/artikel/nestor_handbuch_artikel_468.pdf

¹⁶ <http://www.ijdc.net/index.php/ijdc/article/view/168/236>

3.2 Results of the Survey Analysis

3.2.1 General information on the survey population

The survey aimed to characterise the population of respondents in general terms asking for information about the countries, the types and sizes of the organisations as well as task responsibilities.

Q: In which country is your organisation located?

Overall, the survey received feedback from 44 countries, with a majority of 365 responses (81.3%) coming from Europe (see figure 1 and table 1). Within this large group, the countries of the DigCurV partners hold a considerable proportion with 242 participants (53.9% of the total population). Among these, the country with the highest number of all answers is Germany (122, 27.2% of the total population), followed by the UK (43, 9.4%), Ireland (32, 8.2%), Italy (22, 4.9%) and Lithuania (19, 4.2%). The 123 responses from other European countries form 27.1% of the survey population with participants from Switzerland, Belgium and the Netherlands holding the highest proportions (5.1%, 4.0% and 3.6%, respectively). 14.0% of the respondents come from North America (56 or 12.3% from the USA, 7 or 1.5% from Canada). There are also a few participants from other countries of the world. However, with 21 responses they form just a small part of the survey population (4.7%) (see [table 16](#) for a detailed frequency table of all countries).

Fig. 1: Countries the respondents come from

* excluding Germany, the UK, Ireland, Italy and Lithuania

** excluding Europe, the USA and Canada

Table 1: Countries the survey respondents came from

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Germany	122	26.9	27.2	27.2
	United Kingdom	42	9.3	9.4	36.5
	Ireland	37	8.1	8.2	44.8
	Italy	22	4.8	4.9	49.7
	Lithuania	19	4.2	4.2	53.9
	Europe	123	27.1	27.4	81.3
	USA	56	12.3	12.5	93.8
	Canada	7	1.5	1.6	95.3
	Other	21	4.6	4.7	100.0
	Total	449	98.9	100.0	
Missing	Total***	5	1.1		
Total		454	100.0		

* excluding Germany, the UK, Ireland, Italy and Lithuania

** excluding Europe, the USA and Canada

*** no answer: 5

The strong predominance of the European countries, and the countries of the DigCurV partners in particular, reflects the distribution strategy of the partners that concentrated on addressing mainly the respective local communities. This should be kept in mind when looking at the results.

Q: Which of the following best describes your type of organisation?

Figure 2 and table 2 show the organisational affiliation of the respondents. A broad range of organisations of the cultural heritage and education sectors are represented by the survey population. A large proportion of the participants are employed at typical cultural heritage institutions, such as archives, libraries and museums. 111 respondents (24.4%) indicated that they were working at an archive, 106 participants (23.8%) indicated working at a research or university library, 66 persons (18.1%) at a national, federal or legal deposit library. There were a number of participants from other library types, e.g. public or special collections libraries. The proportion of museum representatives was lower with 49 persons or 10.8% of responses, but nonetheless they make up a considerable part of the participants affiliated to cultural heritage organisations.

The survey also received strong input from scientific and educational organisations, such as universities (82 participants, 18.1%), research centres (52 participants, 11.5%), scientific associations (9, 2.0%) and, again, the already above mentioned research and university libraries (108, 23.8%).

Fig. 2: Types of organisations

The percentage of respondents employed at companies is relatively small: 4% (18 respondents). But, as companies did not belong to our main target group for dissemination of the survey, this low percentage was perhaps to be expected.

A considerable number of respondents (85, 18.7%) stated that they belonged to an organisation other than the ones listed in the online forms. Of the 85 persons who picked the answering option “other”, 26 did this as an additional option alongside one of the standard organisation types. In 59 cases, “other” was the only option chosen. The additional information supplied reveals a variety of organisations including public and special libraries, broadcasters and local, state or national authorities and/or facilities. Four respondents said that they replied to the survey as individuals not belonging to any organisation.

Table 2: Types of Organisations

	Responses ¹⁷		Percent of Cases*
	N	Percent	
Archive	111	19.1%	24.4%
Research or University Library	108	18.6%	23.8%
University	82	14.1%	18.1%
National, Federal or Legal Deposit Library	66	11.4%	14.5%
Research Centre	52	9.0%	11.5%
Museum	49	8.4%	10.8%
Company	18	3.1%	4.0%
(Scientific) Association	9	1.6%	2.0%
Other	85	14.7%	18.7%
Total	580	100.0%	127.8%

* 449 valid cases, 5 missing

Q: Approximately how many Full Time Equivalent does your organisation employ?

426 of the 454 respondents specified the size of their organisation by indicating the approximate number of full time equivalents. The survey covered organisations of all sizes. However, if we compare the three groups in figure 3 and table 3 – smaller organisations with a staff size of 1-100 FTEs, middle-sized organisations with 101-500 FTEs and large organisations with more than 500 FTEs – we can recognize that the largest proportion of responses were received from members of smaller institutions (193, 45.3%), followed by the middle-sized organisations (129, 30.3%). Only about a quarter of the responses (104, 24.4%) come from larger organisations. However, these findings correspond with the distribution that is to be expected within our target audience, where the number of smaller organisations by far exceeds that of large institutions.

¹⁷ For a number of questions, multiple answers were allowed. In the corresponding tables this is displayed by three columns. The first column (title: Responses, subtitle N) refers to the number of total responses. The second column (title: Responses, subtitle: Percent) indicates the corresponding percentage within the total of responses. The third column (titled Percent of Cases), refers to the percentage of participants who answered this question.

In case of table 2, for example, there were 111 responses for “Archive”. This makes up 19.1% of the total number of responses. The percentage of respondents (percentage of cases) who ticked this answer is 24.4%.

Fig. 3: Size of the organisations

Table 3: Size of the Organisations by FTEs

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 - 100	193	42.5	45.3	45.3
	101 - 300	129	28.4	30.3	75.6
	> 500	104	22.9	24.4	100.0
	Total	426	93.8	100.0	
Missing	Total*	28	6.2		
Total		454	100.0		

* „I don't know“: 24, not applicable: 4

Q: Which of the following tasks are you responsible for in your organisation?

To estimate the respondents' relation to the topic of digital preservation and curation, we asked them to indicate the tasks that they are responsible for in their organisation. The results, which are displayed in figure 4 and table 4, illustrate that the members of the survey population are engaged in a variety of activities with regard to different stages of the lifecycle of digital materials as well as on various institutional levels. A great number of respondents are in charge of management tasks: 242 (53.4%) of them are responsible for the management of digital preservation issues and 129 (28.5%) perform general management tasks. The recruitment of staff is another responsibility that belongs to the areas of activity of a number of participants (73, 16.1%).

A considerable proportion of the survey population was engaged in hands-on activities, such as functional tasks in digital preservation (189 or 41.7% of our respondents) or technical development and programming (91 or 20.1% of the respondents).

Another area a considerable proportion of the respondents operate in is the scientific and education sector. About a third of the survey population (143, 31.6%) is engaged in research, roughly a quarter (106, 23.4%) in training for practitioners and 17% (77) are responsible for the education of students.

In addition, other duties are mentioned by 16.8% of the respondents, for about half of which this was the only option chosen. The duties specified are wide ranging including general archivist’s or librarian’s tasks, project management, consulting and policy development.

The figures show that the professional activities of the survey population cover a wide range of tasks associated with digital preservation and curation. Hence, it can be assumed that there is a strong input of knowledge and expertise from many relevant areas into the survey.

Fig. 4: Tasks the respondents are responsible for

Table 4: Tasks the respondents are responsible for

	Responses		Percent of Cases*
	N	Percent	
Management for digital preservation/curation issues	242	18.0%	53.4%
Workflow planning for digital preservation/curation	216	16.1%	47.7%
Functional tasks in digital preservation/curation	189	14.1%	41.7%
Research	143	10.7%	31.6%
General management	129	9.6%	28.5%
Training of practitioners in digital preservation/curation	106	7.9%	23.4%
Technical development/programming	91	6.8%	20.1%
Education of students (i.e. future professionals) in digital preservation/curation	77	5.7%	17.0%
Recruitment of staff	73	5.4%	16.1%
Other	76	5.7%	16.8%
Total	1342	100.0%	296.2%

* 453 valid cases, 1 missing

3.2.2 Involvement in digital preservation and curation activities

The next block of questions referred to the respondent's organisations and their involvement in digital preservation and curation activities, i.e. the long-term storage of digital materials, the existence of staff assigned to digital preservation/curation tasks and plans of hiring staff for this field of work.

Q: Does your institution store digital materials for long-term preservation?

About three quarters (75.7%) of the respondents stated that their organisation is storing digital materials: 55.4% report that their organisation does this completely in-house, 16.5% partly in-house, partly outsourced. Only a small percentage of respondents, 3.9%, indicate that their institutions completely outsource the long term storage of digital materials. Another 18.1% signify that there are plans to store digital assets for long-term in the future. The overwhelming majority of 93.8% of the organisations (the organisations of 93.8% of the survey population) face the challenge of digital preservation and curation now or in the near future. The proportion of institutions neither storing digital materials nor planning to do so was 6.2%.

In their comments to this question, several respondents noted that their organisation is only at the beginnings of dealing with the subject, for example: *"The National Archives of [country]"*

is responsible by law for the preservation of archival records of central government departments in [country]. While it holds some material in digital format, it is only at the early stages of formulating a digital preservation strategy.” Another participant comments: “Little effort has been made to date to actually store it; the material has not been appraised nor have decisions [been] made to delete any items. The reason for this is that we lack expertise to deal with it”.

The survey results and the comments both suggest that there is a substantial need for training with regard to digital preservation and curation in a large number of the organisations that are storing or planning to store digital materials.

Fig. 5: Long-term storage of digital materials

Table 5: Long-term storage of digital materials

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes, in-house	242	53.3	55.4	55.4
	Yes, but we outsource this task	17	3.7	3.9	59.3
	Yes, partly in-house, partly outsourced	72	15.9	16.5	75.7
	No, but we plan to do so	79	17.4	18.1	93.8
	No	27	5.9	6.2	100.0
	Total	437	96.3	100.0	
Missing	Total*	17	3.7		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 12, not applicable: 4, no answer: 1

The next two questions in the survey aimed at shedding light on the staff situation with regard to digital preservation and curation. The questions only appeared to the 331 respondents who had previously indicated that their organisations were involved in long term preservation and were answered by 325 respondents.

Q: Which of the following statements about staff apply best to your organisation?

Multiple answers were allowed for this question as not all of the given statements were mutually exclusive.

Fig. 6: Statements applying to staff involved in digital preservation/curation

The results (see figure 6 and table 6) from the survey show that only about two thirds of the organisations who responded (204, 62.8%) have core-funded staff in charge of digital preservation. If we refer to core-funded staff exclusively assigned to digital preservation tasks, the percentage of institutions reduces to 30.8% (100). 12.3% (40) of the organisations employ externally funded staff exclusively assigned to digital preservation tasks, 10.8% (35) have externally funded staff who are responsible for digital preservation tasks as well as for other duties. The percentage of institutions employing staff for the management of the out-sourced preservation of digital materials is 9.5% (31).

12% of the respondents indicate, that – although their organisation is engaged in long-term preservation – there are no staff assigned to the related tasks. This is especially the case with small institutions – with 16.9% (24) of institutions with 1-100 FTEs (full-time equivalent staff) having no staff allocated to long-term preservation; in organisations with more than 500 FTE's this is the case for only 5.8% (4) (see [table 17](#)).

Few additional comments were recorded with regard to this question, so there is little additional information about how these institutions handle the tasks associated with the storage of digital material. One participant noted, that these were fulfilled by “*part time student employees*”, another that “*staff have some limited responsibility for digital preservation issues*”. This may suggest that, in many of these cases, the responsibilities associated with digital preservation are taken on to a very limited extent by staff (who are not actually assigned to the role) or that, because off a lack of appropriate staff or resources, digital preservation issues are not fulfilled at all.

These results provide evidence for a considerable need for training in this field.

Table 6: Statements applying to staff involved in digital preservation/curation

	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Percent	
We have core-funded staff who work on digital preservation/curation and also for other sections/departments	204	43.9%	62.8%
We have core-funded staff assigned exclusively to digital preservation/curation tasks	100	21.5%	30.8%
We have externally funded staff on contract assigned exclusively to digital preservation/curation tasks	40	8.6%	12.3%
We have externally funded staff on contract who work on digital preservation/curation and also for other sections/departments	35	7.5%	10.8%
We have staff assigned to managing out-sourced preservation of digital materials	31	6.7%	9.5%
We have no staff who are currently assigned to digital preservation/curation tasks	39	8.4%	12.0%
Other (staff)	16	3.4%	4.9%
Total	465	100.0%	143.1%

* 325 valid cases, 129 missing, 123 of which the question was not applicable to

Q: How many members of your staff are involved in digital preservation/curation (both either full-time or part-time)?

There were 271 respondents who specified the number of staff involved in digital preservation and curation activities. To 122 participants this question was not applicable (because their organisations do not store digital materials at present) and a further 52 respondents stated that they did not know the answer.

In the number of staff involved in digital preservation and curation, there is a great variation between the organisations. The staff numbers given range from 0, which was mentioned 9 times, to 150 (see table 7 and figure 7). The latter belongs to a number of extreme values at the upper end of the distribution. There are 6 respondents who indicated a staff number between 33 and 150¹⁸, another 18 participants said there were between 16 and 30 people of their organisation engaged in digital preservation tasks. The vast majority (247 participants, 91.9%) stated a number between 0 and 15, with the bulk of values clustering between 1 and

¹⁸ These outliers can presumably be mainly attributed to a broad interpretation of the tasks and duties that are accounted to digital preservation and curation. So, one of the respondents commented: „Curators, researchers, preparators, librarians and informational experts are involved in various extend in digitalisation, so depending on your ideas, the number can be between 50-150”.

5 (179, 66.1%). The most frequently mentioned digital preservation staff number is 2 (52 times), followed by 1 (42 times) and 3 (38 times).

These figures illustrate that, to date, in large parts of the organisations that store digital material, there are only very few staff members who take care of the corresponding tasks.

Fig. 7: Number of digital preservation staff

Table 7: Number of digital preservation staff

					Cumulative
	No. of dp staff	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	0	9	2.0	3.3	3.3
	1	42	9.3	15.5	18.8
	2	53	11.7	19.6	38.4
	3	38	8.4	14.0	52.4
	4	23	5.1	8.5	60.9
	5	23	5.1	8.5	69.4
	6	13	2.9	4.8	74.2
	7	5	1.1	1.8	76.0
	8	5	1.1	1.8	77.9
	9	2	.4	.7	78.6
	10	16	3.5	5.9	84.5
	11	2	.4	.7	85.2
	12	4	.9	1.5	86.7
	14	2	.4	.7	87.5
	15	10	2.2	3.7	91.1
	16	1	.2	.4	91.5
	17	1	.2	.4	91.9
	18	1	.2	.4	92.3
	19	1	.2	.4	92.6
	20	8	1.8	3.0	95.6
	25	1	.2	.4	95.9
	30	5	1.1	1.8	97.8
	33	1	.2	.4	98.2
	35	1	.2	.4	98.5
	50	1	.2	.4	98.9
	77	1	.2	.4	99.3
	100	1	.2	.4	99.6
	150	1	.2	.4	100.0
	Total	271	59.7	100.0	
Missing	Total*	183	40.3		
Total		454	100.0		

* not applicable: 122, I don't know: 52, no answer: 9

Q: Is your organisation planning to hire staff for digital preservation/curation in future?

There were 335 valid responses for this item. Quite a few respondents (118, 25.1% of the total survey population) said that they could not give a statement with regard to this question.

According to the figures displayed in table 8 and figure 8, the percentage of organisations planning to hire new staff is rather low. Only 56 (16.7%) plan to hire staff exclusively assigned to digital preservation and curation tasks, 104 (31.0%) intend to hire staff partly assigned to the respective responsibilities. In 192 (57.3%) of the valid cases, the respondents signify that their organisation does not plan to hire new staff.

These findings stand in sharp contrast with the large proportion of responding organisations that already store or plan to store digital materials. As mentioned above, institutions are storing digital assets without staff responsible for the associated tasks. This again poses the question of how these organisations are going to cope with the challenges that arise from the long-term storage of digital materials without hiring staff for this purpose. A few institutions might already have staff in place, but many don't. A lot of participants commented on this question. Many pointed out that budget constraints are a major factor that prevent new hirings: *"We would like to [hire staff], but cannot due to budget cuts"*, *"No budget available"* or *"There is a moratorium on hiring new staff"*. Also, several respondents noted that therefore *"we are trying to incorporate digital preservation/curation tasks into existing jobs"* and that *"existing staff will be trained to take on these duties"*.

Another issue that is addressed by some of the respondents' comments is a lack of properly skilled candidates: *"The chance to employ specialized staff is small"*.

Again, the figures and comments from the survey support the need for training to help existing staff of cultural heritage institutions to acquire the skills and competences needed to cope with digital preservation.

Fig. 8: Plans regarding hiring staff

Table 8: Plans regarding hiring staff

	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Percent	
No	192	54.5%	57.3%
Yes, we are planning to hire staff partly assigned to digital preservation/curation amongst other duties	104	29.5%	31.0%
Yes, we are planning to hire staff exclusively assigned to digital preservation/curation tasks	56	15.9%	16.7%
Total	352	100.0%	105.1%

* 335 valid cases, 119 missing

3.2.3 Training plans and preferences

The next part of the survey contained questions regarding the organisations’ training plans for existing staff, their respective budget and facilities as well as their preferences with regard to training methods and time.

Q: Is your organisation planning any training for existing staff?

Of the 370 responses received for this question, 31.4% (116 respondents) said that their organisation is planning training for staff with previous experience in digital preservation. Another 35.4% (131 respondents) indicated that there were plans to train staff who have no previous experience in this field. 35.1% of responses stated that the institutions did not envisage any training for their staff in terms of digital preservation (see figure 9 and table 9).

Nevertheless, the number of organisations that are intending to have their staff trained is considerable. The findings of part 2 also suggest a significant demand for appropriate training offers in the near future.

Fig. 9: Training plans for digital preservation staff

Table 9: Training plans for digital preservation staff

	Responses		Percent of Cases*
	N	Percent	
No	130	27.5%	35.1%
Yes, we are planning training for staff without previous experience in digital preservation/curation	131	27.7%	35.4%
Yes, we are planning training for staff with previous experience in digital preservation/curation	116	24.5%	31.4%
We already provide training for our staff	96	20.3%	25.9%
Total	473	100.0%	127.8%

* 370 valid cases, 84 missing (83 of them choosing the “I don’t know” option)

When having a closer look at the types of organisations and the countries, we find slight differences in the answers to this question. For example, the proportion of organisations planning training for staff with previous dp/dc experience is higher for research centres (40.0%), national, federal or legal deposit libraries (37.7%) and archives (37.5%) than for universities (29.2%), museums (26.3%) and research and university libraries (24.4%). With respect to planned training for inexperienced staff, research centres hold the lowest

percentage (28.9%), followed by museums (31.6%), whilst the other types of organisations rank between 35.2% and 38.4%. The proportion of institutions that, according to the respondents, do not have plans for training is higher for research and university libraries (40.7%), universities (40.0%), museums (39.5%) and research centres (37.8%) than it is for archives (30.2%) and national, federal or legal deposit libraries (29.5%) (see also [table 18](#) in the appendix).

In terms of the country-specific distribution¹⁹, we see that the portion of organisations planning training for experienced staff ranges from 22.4% (Germany) to 43.5% (Other), with the USA (28.3%), the UK (35.3%) and Europe (35.8%) in the middle. With regard to plans to train inexperienced staff, Europe and again Germany hold quite a low percentage (30.9% and 32.7%) compared to the UK, the USA and the mixed country group that lie between 43.5% and 47.1%. There are divergences as well in the proportions of institutions not planning any training. In this regard, we find by far the lowest percentage in the UK (20.6%), the highest in Europe (37.6%) and the USA (39.1%). Germany (33.7%) and the other countries (30.4%) lie in between. (see [table 19](#)). However, the differences suggested by the above described numbers constitute only gradual deviations from the average trend and are not statistically significant.

¹⁹ In terms of country-specific distributions, five groups have been looked at in detail: Europe (without Germany and the UK), Germany, the UK, the USA and other countries. Initially, all DigCurV partner countries (Germany, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, the UK as well as the USA and Canada) should have been regarded here. In view of the rather low numbers of respondents from Ireland, Italy, Lithuania and Canada, however, this idea had to be dismissed, unfortunately, as there was no basis to make substantive statements about these countries.

Q: Does your organisation have a budget for training?

Overall, about two thirds of the organisations do have a budget for training (see figure 10 and table 10).

With the exception of museums (51.1%) and research centres (60.4%), there are no weighty differences between different types of organisations. With regard to the country-specific distribution, the UK, with a proportion of 90%, is significantly above the average, whereas the percentage of European organisations (excluding organisations from Germany and the UK) with a training budget (60.1%) lies below average (see [tables 20 and 21](#)).

Fig. 10: Budget for training

Table 10: Budget for training

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	277	61.0	69.1	69.1
	No	124	27.3	30.9	100.0
	Total	401	88.3	100.0	
Missing	Total*	53	11.7		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 49, not applicable: 4

Q: Does your organisation have in-house training facilities?

According to the figures displayed in table 11 and figure 11, about half of the respondent’s organisations have got in-house training facilities.

Among the types of organisations, museums lie considerably below average (31.9%), universities (59.9%), national, federal and legal deposit libraries (57.1%) as well as research and university libraries (55.7%) slightly above. With respect to countries, the UK stands out with 76.3% (see also [tables 22 and 23](#)).

Fig. 11: In-house training facilities

Table 11: In-house training facilities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	215	47.4	50.7	50.7
	No	209	46.0	49.3	100.0
	Total	424	93.4	100.0	
Missing	Total*	30	6.6		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 25, not applicable: 4, no answer: 1

Q: Is it important to your organisation that training is certified?

The opinions about the importance of certification for trainings are divided. Nearly half of the 347 respondents (165, 47.6%) who answered this question think it is important to their organisations that training for staff is certified. In contrast, 182 (52.4%) believe that such a certification is not absolutely necessary (see figure 12 and table 12). In the comments section, several people noted that certification was of course welcome, but not a prerequisite and that from the institution’s perspective, the most crucial point was that the training offered is of good quality and the outcomes are relevant. However, a number of respondents also pointed out that certification is very important to the participants of training events.

Fig. 12: Importance of certification

Table 12: Importance of certification

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	182	40.1	52.4	52.4
	Yes	165	36.3	47.6	100.0
	Total	347	76.4	100.0	
Missing	Total*	107	23.6		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 101, not applicable: 4, no answer: 2

With regard to the different types of organisations, we find a slight variation in the answers. The rate of respondents affirming the importance of certification ranges from 40.0% (research and university libraries) to 60.0% (museums) (see also table 24). When having a look at the country-specific distribution, there seem to be two countries, in which certification is considered less important: the USA (24.4% approval) and Germany (37.8%), as opposed to the UK (50%), Europe (58.6%) and the other countries (56.5%) (see also table 25).

Q: Which training methods do you consider the most suitable for your organisation?

To assess the preferences in terms of different types of training, we asked the survey participants to indicate up to two training methods that they considered the most suitable for their organisation. The given answers comprised six commonly used forms of training delivery as well as the option to specify alternatives beyond these (see figure 13 and table 13). Small group workshops turned out to be by far the most popular method. They were chosen by 336 (75.3%) of the respondents. 172 (38.6%) of respondents selected blended learning, that mixes conventional face-to-face methods and online components.

The other four options received far less affirmation. Two options were chosen by about a fifth of the survey population: written manuals (96, 21.5%) and supervised one-to-one-training by a senior staff member (90, 20.2%) and reach approximately the same degree of preference, followed by online training (17.5%) and large group workshops (12.8%). Six respondents mentioned methods besides the given ones, such as “group discussions”, “consultant training” or “learning by doing”.

Fig. 13: Most suitable training method

Table 13: Most suitable training method

	Responses		Percent of Cases*
	N	Percent	
Small group workshop (hands-on training)	336	40.2%	75.3%
Blended learning (i.e. a mixture of face to face instruction and online components)	172	20.6%	38.6%
Written manuals	96	11.5%	21.5%
Supervised one-to-one training by a senior staff member	90	10.8%	20.2%
Online training (webinar, self-paced courses or asynchronous learning)	78	9.3%	17.5%
Large group workshop (lectures and practical exercises)	57	6.8%	12.8%
Other	6	.7%	1.3%
Total	835	100.0%	187.2%

* 446 valid cases, 8 missing

When looking at the distribution among different types of organisations, as well as the country-specific distribution, small group workshops remain the most popular with an approval rate of about three quarters of the respondents, with the exception of museums (59.2%), archives (81.8%) and, among the countries, the UK (87.8%). Likewise, blended learning was considered as the second most suitable training form regardless of which type of organisation the respondent belonged to, with rates ranging from 33.3% (research and university libraries) to 50.8% (national, federal or legal deposit libraries). In terms of countries, only one placed another method in second position: Germany regarded written manuals (35.2%) as more suitable than blended learning (26.2%). With regard to written manuals, online training, one-to-one training and large group workshops, there are slight variations from the average approval rate and positioning with regard to different countries and types of organisations ([see tables 26 and 27](#)).

The distribution of answers was also analysed to see if there were different views and opinions about the best methods and time frame for training, and relevant skills dependent on the task responsibilities of the respondents (see above). No major deviations from the general trend were observed in terms of training methods regarded as the most suitable ([see table 28](#)).

Q: Which time frame for training in digital preservation/curation do you consider the most suitable for your organisation?

Similar to the previous question, to find the most preferred time frame for training, we asked the respondents to indicate up to two options on a list of given answers (see figure 14 and table 14). Again, there is one option that was clearly indicated as the by far most popular time frame for training: a one-time event of 1-2 work days was selected by 245 (55.3%) of the respondents. A one-time event of 3-5 work days was the second most popular time frame - selected by 29.8% (132 participants) of the survey population. This is, with a distance of about 10% followed by a course of one to two hours a week for one semester (86, 19.4%). A recurring block course of one to two weeks for several semesters (64, 14.4%) and a course of one to two hours a week for two or more semesters (40, 9.0%) are considered the least suitable time frames.

33 respondents (7.4%) indicated that they found alternative time frames best fitting, for example: *“periodic training on new procedures and technologies”*, *“weekly case discussions”* or *“recurring blocks of 1-2 days, continuously”* ([please see the appendix for the full list](#)).

In the comments, a number of respondents pointed out the reason for the preference for short-term trainings are constraints that arise from heavy workloads that many staff members have to cope with. These make it difficult for organisations to release staff for training for more than a few days: *“Finding time for staff to do training is more difficult than finding money.”*

Fig. 14: Most suitable time frame for training

Table 14: Most suitable time frame for training

	Responses		Percent of Cases*
	N	Percent	
One-time event of 1-2 work days	245	40.8%	55.3%
One-time event of 3-5 work days	132	22.0%	29.8%
Course of 1-4 hours a week for one semester	86	14.3%	19.4%
Recurring block course of one to two weeks for several semesters	64	10.7%	14.4%
Course of 1-4 hours a week for two or more semesters	40	6.7%	9.0%
Other	33	5.5%	7.4%
Total	600	100.0%	135.4%

* 443 valid cases, 11 missing

As to the organisation-, task- and country-specific distributions, there are hardly any significant variations from the average results ([see tables 29-31](#)). The one-time event of 1-2 work days and the one-time event of 3-5 work days were affirmed as the time frames regarded most suitable and second most suitable respectively. In the group of other countries, the one-time event of 3-5 work days (48.1%) is preferred over the one-time event of 1-2 work days (33.3%). The positions of the other options are in the main in accordance with the overall trend.

3.2.4 Skills and competences needed for digital preservation and curation

When designing training measures, it is vital to first identify the tasks and skills that are relevant to the subject matter. For this purpose, we referred to previous research and literature on the topic (see 3.1) and compiled two lists of tasks and the corresponding skills that have been described as significant for digital preservation and curation. One contained general tasks and skills and the other digital preservation-specific and technical skills. Then we asked the survey participants to assess the importance of each skill in terms of the work of staff involved in digital preservation and curation on a four-stage scale (essential, important, not important, non essential). The results are presented below.

3.2.4.a General tasks and skills

With regard to general skills and tasks, the survey respondents were asked to assess the importance of the following eight items:

- Collaborating with others
- Communicating with others
- Affinity for technology
- Managing projects
- Training others
- Managing budgets
- Leading a department or team
- Organising conferences, workshops or other events

The figures displayed below in figure 15 demonstrate that the three general skills considered most crucial for digital preservation and curation are communicating with others, collaborating with others and affinity for technology. Each of these is regarded as either essential or important by more than 95% of the respondents who answered these questions.

Collaborating with others is rated as essential by 59.5% (267), as important by 39.9% (179) (in total 99.3%). Communicating with others holds 56.8% (255) with respect to essential, 41.4% (186) with respect to important (in total 98.2%). Affinity for technology is viewed as essential by 40.4% (180) and as important by 55.4% (247) (in total 95.7%).

Managing projects and training others were considered to be of high importance as well. They have been indicated to be either important or essential by 83.7% (managing projects) and 77.0% (training others) of the respondents.

The opinions with regard to managing budgets are divided. After all, 52.2% of the participants considered it to be either important or essential.

Two areas of activity were thought to be not as relevant: leading a department or team and organising conferences, workshops or other events. They were rated to be either not important or non essential in 59.2% (leading a department or team) and 65.3% (organising conferences, workshops or other events) of the valid cases.

The tables with the detailed figures for each item can be found in the appendix ([tables 32-39](#)).

Fig. 15: Importance of general tasks/skills

With regard to the task-, organisation- and country-specific distributions, there were few major deviations from the overall trends, mainly concerning differences between countries. The respondents from the United States, for example, value the areas of communicating with others, collaborating with others, affinity for technology and managing projects higher than the average survey population. The respondents from the group of ‘other countries’ also expressed a higher degree of appreciation with respect to communicating and collaborating with others and managing projects. In contrast, the respondents from Germany rated managing projects below average. Training others was another item that was rated above

average for important and essential from the USA, the other countries and the UK. (see [tables 48-55](#)).

In terms of organisation-specific differences, it can be noticed that the proportion of respondents who regarded project management as being important or essential was below average for museums. With respect to training others, the proportion of university employees who regarded it as being important or essential was above average ([see tables 40-47](#)).

The only major difference in terms of task-specific groups can be observed with regard to training others. The percentage of respondents considering this activity important or essential was not surprisingly considerably above average among those who were responsible for the education of students or the training of practitioners. Training others was rated below average by respondents dealing with technical development or programming ([see tables 56-63](#)).

3.2.4.b Digital preservation-specific and technical tasks and skills

In this section, respondents have been asked to assess the importance of the following eight digital preservation-specific and technical tasks:

- Preservation Planning
- Ensuring access
- Managing data
- Evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation
- Storing data
- Ingesting data
- Research, development and implementation of digital preservation environments
- Administering the archive

The results are displayed in figure 16 (for the detailed figures for each item see [tables 64-71](#)). It is striking that, with respect to digital preservation and curation, a high relevance was ascribed to virtually all of the given tasks. Even the one with the lowest proportion of respondents considering it either important or essential (research, development and implementation of digital preservation/curation environments) holds 90.7%. The corresponding percentages for the other seven items lie between 93.5% and 97.7%. There were five tasks that are viewed to be essential by more than 50% of the respondents: preservation planning (261, 58.7%), ensuring access (259, 58.2%) managing data (258, 58.2%), evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation (258, 57.5%) and storing

data (248, 56.0%). The remaining three are regarded essential by 45.4 to 50.0% of the survey participants.

Fig. 16: Importance of digital preservation-specific and technical skills

When looking at the different countries, a tendency to regard a task more essential than the average can be observed with regard to a number of items for respondents from USA, the UK and the group of other countries. In particular, for the USA, this applies to evaluating and selecting data for long term preservation, storing data, managing data, administering the archive, preservation planning and ensuring access. The UK rate lies above average with regard to evaluating and selecting data for long term preservation, ingesting data, storing data, managing data, and preservation planning. The corresponding percentages for the group of other countries lie above the overall rating for every one of the given items. In contrast, among the group of respondents from Germany there seems to be a tendency to assess the tasks less essential than the average (with a corresponding higher percentage of votes for important) ([see also tables 80- 87](#)).

With respect to the organisation-specific distribution, respondents employed in museums also rated the tasks as being of lower importance. By contrast employees from national, federal or legal deposit libraries rated the tasks (applying to ingesting data, storing data, managing data, administering the archive and preservation planning) as essential more often

than the general survey population. Employees from archives rated the activities of ingesting data, storing data and administering the archive as essential more often ([see also tables 72-79](#)).

Among the group of respondents engaged in the education of students, the responses were below average for ingesting data, storing data, managing data and administering the archive. Besides this, there were no other significant differences ([see also tables 88-95](#)).

3.2.5 Training needs with regard to digital preservation and curation

After having collected the survey participants' opinions about the importance of a number of tasks and skills when dealing with the matter of digital preservation and curation, we also wanted to know how they assessed the need for training of staff involved in digital preservation and curation, on a scale from great need, moderate need, hardly any need to not needed. Again, the items in question have been divided into two groups: general skills and digital preservation-specific and technical areas.

3.2.5.a General skills

In terms of general skills, we asked the survey participants to assess the training needs of digital preservation staff with regard to the following six areas:

- Liaising between customers and information technology experts
- Communication
- Project Management
- Networking with people
- Training others
- Administration and finances

With respect to four of these six items, the percentage of respondents who stated that there is either a moderate or a great need is higher than 80%: liaising between customers and information technology experts (85.4%), communication (83.6%), project management (81.9%) and networking with people (81.4%). The proportions of participants indicating a great need are 44.2% (194, liaising between customers and information technology experts), 36.8% (162, communication), 33.9% (150, project management) and 33.4% (147, networking with people). Approximately three quarters of the respondents indicated that there is a need for training with respect to the ability to train others (great need: 23.1%, 101, moderate need: 50.2%, 220). The lowest proportion of persons indicating a moderate or great need for training can be found with regard to administration and finances. It is nevertheless 60.6% (see figure 17 below and [tables 96-101](#)).

The degree of organisation-, task- and country-specific variation with regard to the training needs in general skills is rather low.

Fig. 17: Training needs with regard to general tasks

Among the different organisation types, respondents from research centres gave a below average response when ranking the need for communication, administration and finances and project management training. Below average responses were also recorded by museum respondents with regard to great need for training in liaising between customers and information technology experts, and project management; and from respondents from archives and national, federal and legal deposit libraries with regard to the need for training others ([see also tables 102-107](#)).

When looking at the country-specific distributions, it can be noticed that respondents from the UK rated the need for training in communication and networking with people below average. Networking training was also rated below average by US respondents. On the contrary, communication and networking with people were rated above average by respondents from the group of other countries. Among the German group, training in project management and training others were rated below average, while project management training was rated above average for the United States ([see also tables 108-113](#)).

With regard to the tasks responsibilities, it is worth noting that those respondents with responsibilities for educating students or training practitioners rated all forms of training need above average ([see also tables 114-119](#)).

3.2.5.b Digital preservation-specific and technical tasks and skills

To identify the needs for training with regard to digital preservation and curation, we asked the respondents to assess the training needs in the following eight areas:

- General knowledge / basic knowledge of digital preservation issues
- Preservation and data management planning
- Preservation tools
- Information modelling and metadata
- Trusted repositories
- Strategic planning and policies
- Technical systems
- Legal aspects

When having a look at the proportions of respondents stating either a moderate or a great need, it becomes obvious that a high degree of need for training is assumed for each of the areas (see figure 18 below and [tables 120-127](#)).

The parts of the survey population asserting a great need range from 39.5% at the lowest to 64.5%. The items with the greatest identified need were general/basic knowledge of digital preservation issues (287, 64.5%), preservation and data management planning (285, 64.3%), preservation tools (263, 59.5%) and information modelling and metadata (230, 52.3%). The percentages of participants stating that there is either a great need or a moderate need range from 86.2% at the lowest to 96.2%. In terms of this cumulative amount, the greatest proportions can be observed with regard to preservation and data management planning (96.2%), preservation tools (94.6%), information modelling and metadata (93%) and general knowledge (92.6%).

Fig. 18: Training needs with regard to digital preservation-specific and technical tasks

When comparing the distributions with regard to the tasks the respondents are responsible for, there were a few groups that rated these tasks below average in comparison to the general survey population. Respondents in charge of the recruitment of staff rated the need for training in general knowledge, strategic planning and policies and technical systems below average. Respondents responsible for training practitioners rated the need for training in strategic planning and policies, and trusted repositories below average. While respondents responsible for the education of students or engaged in research rated the need for training in technical systems below average ([see also tables 144-151](#))

With regard to the country-specific distributions, the UK respondents rated the need for training in general knowledge, strategic planning and policies, trusted repositories and technical systems below average. The United States respondents expressed less need for training in strategic planning and policies as well as legal aspects. While the German respondents expressed above average need for training in general knowledge and strategic planning and policies. Finally, in the group of other countries, a general tendency to indicate a greater need for training in all topics was observed ([see also tables 136-143](#)).

Besides a higher percentage of respondents stating a great need above average with regard to technical systems in museums and research centres, no major variations can be found between the different types of organisations ([see also tables 128-135](#)).

3.2.5.c Most pressing needs

When designing the survey questions, we assumed that it might be the case that the degree of need for training would be very high for the majority of the given areas. Therefore, we included a question that invited the participants to set priorities by indicating up to three areas in which they believed the need for training to be most pressing. The list to choose from for this question included the general as well as the digital preservation-specific and technical areas that had already been subject to the assessment of the training needs in the last two questions.

The ranking of the items is displayed in figure 19 and table 15. It is noticeable that the digital preservation-specific and technical areas were the areas for which the need for training was stated to be most pressing. The two areas that were ranked the highest were general or basic knowledge of digital preservation issues (indicated to be most pressing by nearly half of the survey population (219, 48.9%) and preservation and data management planning (with almost the same number of votes: 218, 48.7%).

Other items associated with an urgent need for training by large proportions of the participants are preservation tools (171, 38.2%), information modelling and metadata (143, 31.9%) and strategic planning and policies (133, 29.7%). About a fifth of the survey population regards technical systems (92, 20.5%) and trusted repositories (82, 18.3%) to be areas with a pressing training need. The least pressing digital preservation-specific area was legal aspects (71, 15.8%).

Although a considerable need for training in general skills was expressed in the results from the previous survey questions, when asked to prioritise the respondents reveal that this area is considered less urgent than training for the digital preservation-specific skills. Only 13 to 39 (1.3%-8.7%) of all respondents rated the need for training in general skills to be most pressing.

The organisation-, task- and country-specific distributions correspond by and large with the average trend. There are of course some variations in the ranking. The most noticeable one is an interchange of the first two positions. Respondents from archives, research or university libraries and national, federal or legal deposit libraries recorded the most pressing need for

training in preservation and data management planning (position 2 in the overall results) instead of general/basic knowledge (position 1 in the overall findings). Respondents engaged in research and from the UK, USA and the other group of European countries also rated training in preservation and data management planning as being more pressing than general/basic knowledge ([see tables 152-154](#)).

The large number of respondents that regard general or basic knowledge and preservation and data management planning to belong to the areas with the most pressing need for training suggests that many of the organisations in our survey are in the early stages of implementing digital preservation. Again this suggests that there will be a considerable demand for training measures, especially with regard to the basics of digital preservation and curation.

Fig. 19: Most pressing needs for training

Table 15: Most pressing needs for training

	Responses		Percent of Cases
	N	Percent	
General knowledge / basic knowledge of digital preservation issues	219	17.1%	48.9%
Preservation and data management planning	218	17.1%	48.7%
Preservation tools	171	13.4%	38.2%
Information modelling and metadata	143	11.2%	31.9%
Strategic planning and policies	133	10.4%	29.7%
Technical Systems	92	7.2%	20.5%
Trusted repositories	82	6.4%	18.3%
Legal aspects	71	5.6%	15.8%
Coordinating between customers and information technology experts	39	3.1%	8.7%
Project management	35	2.7%	7.8%
Communication	19	1.5%	4.2%
Networking with people	18	1.4%	4.0%
Training others	18	1.4%	4.0%
Administration and finances	13	1.0%	2.9%
Other	6	.5%	1.3%
Total	1277	100.0%	285.0%

* 448 valid cases, 6 missing cases

3.2.6 Summary of the training needs survey results

In total, the survey received 454 responses. The majority of participants (81.3%) were from Europe. Among these, the largest proportion came from the countries of the DigCurV partners (Germany, the UK, Ireland, Italy and Lithuania) who together made up 53.9% of the total survey population. 14.0% of the responses received were from North America. Other countries were underrepresented, forming merely 4.7% of the total population.

The survey participants were affiliated to a broad spectrum of organisations from the cultural heritage as well as the scientific and education sectors. Cultural heritage institutions were represented by large proportions of respondents (archives by 24.4%, research and university libraries by 23.8%, national, federal or legal deposit libraries by 14.5% and museums by 10.8%). Organisation related to science and education were also well represented (universities 18.1%, research centres 11.5%, scientific associations 2.0% and research and university libraries 23.8%). Many (18.7%) respondents indicated that they were affiliated to institutions which we had not included in the list of options, such as broadcasters and national, state or local authorities.

The size of the organisations the survey respondents were affiliated to reflected the distribution that we had anticipated. The largest proportion of respondents (45.3%) came from small institutions with up to 100 FTEs (full time equivalents). About a third (30.3%) were employed at middle-sized organisations of 101-500 FTEs. Roughly a quarter (24.4%) came from large institutions with more than 500 FTEs.

The survey participants were involved in a variety of activities related to digital preservation and curation, ranging from management tasks to functional tasks as well as training, education and research.

About three quarters (75.7%) of the participant's organisations are already storing digital materials for long-term preservation. Another 18.1% plan to store materials for long term preservation in the future. Merely 6.2% of the institutions neither store nor intend to store digital assets.

Of the organisations that store digital materials, 62.8% reported employing core-funded staff partly assigned to digital preservation tasks, 30.8% reported core-funded staff exclusively assigned to digital preservation tasks. Respondents stated that in some institutions digital preservation duties are fulfilled by externally funded staff either exclusively (12.3%) or partly

(10.8%) assigned to digital preservation. 12.0% of the respondents from organisations holding digital materials stated that there was no staff that was assigned to the related tasks.

The vast majority (93.8%) of the institutions in our survey face the challenge of digital preservation. However, 57.3% do not intend to hire new staff for digital preservation duties. 31.0% of the respondents indicated plans to hire staff who is partly assigned to this field of activity, 16.7% indicate that their organisations intend to hire exclusively assigned staff for digital preservation. With regard to the large proportion of institutions that do not intend to hire new digital preservation staff, it seems likely that the tasks associated with the long-term storage of digital materials will be assigned to existing staff who will need training to acquire or develop the necessary skills and competences. This suggests that there will be a considerable need for appropriate training offers arising from these circumstances.

A considerable proportion of respondents stated that their organisation is planning training for digital preservation staff. 35.4% signify that there will be training for staff with no previous experience in the subject matter, 31.4% say that there are plans to train staff that has already got some experience in digital preservation and curation. However, there is also a percentage of 35.1% that indicate that there are no training plans for digital preservation staff.

With regard to the training methods that are regarded as most suitable for their organisation by the respondents, one method clearly stood out – small group work shops were favoured by 75.3%. Blended learning (a mixture of face-to-face instruction and online training) was favoured by 38.6% and ranked as the second most popular form of training. The other methods suggested (written manuals, one-to-one training by a senior staff member, online training and large group workshops) were by far less popular.

In terms of the time frame considered most suitable, the trend is similar. By far the most popular time frame (mentioned by 55.3% of the respondents) were one time training events of 1-2 work days. Next in line, with a percentage of 29.8% were one time events of 3-5 work days. Training forms that require more time, such as course of 1-4 hours a week for one or more semesters or recurring 1-2 week block courses for several semesters were regarded less suitable. The comments for this question suggest this pattern of preferences is related to time constraints caused by heavy workloads.

The survey participants were asked to assess the importance of certain tasks and skills for the work of digital preservation staff. They were presented with two sets, one referring to

general tasks and skills, such as management or communication skills, the other referring to digital preservation-specific and technical skills.

In terms of general tasks and skills, three items were clearly indicated as the most important – collaborating with others, communicating with others and affinity for technology. These areas are regarded either essential or important by more than 95% of the respondents.

As for digital preservation-specific and technical tasks and skills, all of the given options were ranked as being of a high importance, with 90% of participants considering all these tasks and skills to be either essential or important.

The need for training was stated to be substantial for the digital-preservation specific and technical skills as well as for the general skills.

With regard to the general skills, between 60.6% and 85.4% of the respondents indicated either a great or moderate need for training. The greatest need for training is stated in terms of liaising between customers and information technology experts.

When looking at the digital preservation-specific and technical skills, the high degree of need for training expressed by the participants is striking. For each of the given areas (general/basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning, preservation tools, information modelling and metadata, trusted repositories, strategic planning and policies, technical systems and legal aspects) between 86.2% and 96.2% of respondents signified a great or moderate need for training. General/basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning and preservation tools were the areas rated with the highest need.

Although the survey recorded a considerable training need in terms of general skills, the most pressing need prioritised by respondents is for digital preservation-specific and technical skills. The areas where the survey results suggest the most pressing need are general/basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning, and preservation tools with 48.9%, 48,7% and 38.2% of respondents identifying these as the priority areas for training.

4. Summary of the Focus Groups Analysis

To gather additional information on the training needs in the field, DigCurV conducted a series of nine focus groups with stakeholders. These were carried out in the DigCurV partner countries (Germany, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania and the UK) in autumn 2011.

Focus groups can be described as structured group discussions on a specific topic. The participants have in common certain characteristics that relate to this topic. The groups are held in a permissive environment to make the participants feel comfortable and free to share their thoughts and opinions about the matter in question²⁰.

The DigCurV focus groups aimed at identifying the skills and competences needed for digital preservation and curation as well as the corresponding training needs. The discussions started with a brief introduction and then moved on to the challenges that the participants perceived with respect to digital preservation and curation. Thereafter, the participants were asked to indicate the skills and competences that they regarded necessary for staff involved in the field and to develop a number of ideal job profiles including the relevant task and skills. Subsequently, the training needs with respect to the skills and competences elaborated before were assessed. The session closed with a discussion about suitable formats for training and the relevance of accreditation or certification.

In terms of challenges related to digital preservation and curation, the participants reported a lack of properly skilled staff in the field as well as a lack of training offers. With respect to the skill-sets of both existing and potential staff, especially the combination of technical expertise, information science and subject knowledge as well as communication skills is hard to find. In addition, a general lack of awareness was stated for the importance of digital preservation among many organisations.

According to the participants, the skills and competences required for digital preservation and curation cover a broad spectrum that ranges from technical expertise, IT knowledge and digital preservation-specific skills to social skills, management skills, and knowledge of the organisation, the subject domain as well as library, archival or information science. These manifold requirements are also reflected in the different job profiles that were elaborated by the participants.

²⁰ See: Krueger, Richard A.; Casey, Mary Ann: Focus Groups. A Practical Guide for Applied Research. 4th edition. Los Angeles: Sage 2009, pp. 2 et sqq.

In terms of training in digital preservation and curation, the participants stated an urgent need, particularly with regard to IT skills and technical digital preservation skills. However, generic skills, management skills and the ability to train others have also been indicated as areas with a considerable training need. Furthermore, for Ireland and Lithuania, participants also reported a great need for introductory training.

With regard to suitable training methods, blended learning, courses of one to two weeks length and short-term courses of a few days were the most frequently mentioned forms. Several participants also expressed a need for long-term courses, such as a 1-2 year master's degree. In addition, some participants stated the necessity to rearrange the curricula of basic professional education and training of cultural heritage professionals to integrate digital preservation and curation issues.

In the majority of the groups, the participants stressed the importance of accreditation or certification – for staff as a proof of their qualification, and for employers as a benchmark which could be referred to during the recruitment process. However, other participants, particularly from the management level, held the opinion that the need for skilled staff is so great, that certification is rather irrelevant when recruiting staff.

The results of the focus groups reflect the difficult situation that many cultural heritage organisations are struggling with at present. They have to rise to the challenges that result from the growing importance of digital materials – including long-term preservation and curation. To be able to do this, they need qualified staff. The focus group participants indicated a severe lack of staff in this area as well as great difficulties in finding professionals with the appropriate skills and competences on the labour market. On top of this, they also state a lack of training offers that could help existing staff to up-skill. They express an urgent need for training, particularly in terms of technical and IT skills, but also with regard to other areas such as communication and management.

The findings of the focus groups are in accordance with the results of the survey. Both indicate that there is a great demand for training in the field of digital preservation and curation. The results suggest that, in the longer term, there is an interest in the accreditation of courses. However, in view of the urgent demand for staff, certification is not the immediate concern.

5. Results of the Job Advertisement Analysis

5.1 Introduction

From February 2011 to January 2012, DigCurV collected forty-eight²¹ job advertisements of posts related to the area of digital preservation and curation²². The job descriptions²³ included in these advertisements have been analysed with regard to the tasks the prospective job holders will be responsible for, the required skills, competences, experiences and knowledge as well as the degrees and qualifications. The findings of the analysis provide supplementary information to the results of the survey and the focus groups and are described below.

5.2 Job advertisements collected

The advertisements collected included postings from the USA (26), the UK (12), Germany (8), New Zealand (4), Australia (2) and Canada (1). The vast majority of jobs were advertised by university or research libraries, few by national libraries, archives, universities, research centres and other organisations, e.g. the ANDS. Many of them looked for Digital Archivists, Digital Preservation/Curation Officers or Librarians, Research Data Managers, Officers or Librarians and Project Officers. The advertised positions also included Professors as well as a few Consultants or Advisors. (please see the appendix for a full list of the job titles and institutions).

5.3 Tasks

The majority of the tasks listed in the job descriptions collected fell into the following categories:

- Communications, outreach and liaison;
- Digital collection and data management;
- Digital curation and preservation;
- Project management;
- Trusted repository and archive;
- Resource, teaching and training;
- Technical;
- Trends, best practice and documentation;

²¹ Two job descriptions were for three open positions; one job description was for two open positions. The forty-eight job descriptions collected represent a total of fifty-three open posts.

²² Please note that the collection is neither exhaustive nor representative.

²³ In the analysis we focused on the job description part of the advertisements. Therefore, we use the terms “job advertisement” and “job description” almost synonymically.

- Supervisory; and
- Grants and funding.

Communications, outreach and liaison tasks mainly related to representing the institution at local, national and international meetings and events; preparing written reports, policies, articles and various internal and external communications; working with stakeholders, clients, project partners, and internal staff; as well as updating websites and engaging in social media activity.

The following tasks were noted frequently in the job descriptions:

- Develop and maintain a network of professional contacts to keep abreast of latest ideas and developments;
- Engage in activities including service, research, presentations and publication to expose research data and/or the project to an international audience;
- Participate in professional societies at a local, national and international level, including: committees, association membership, conference and workshop attendance, etc.;
- Represent and champion digital preservation interests across the institution.

Digital collections and data management tasks were described as leading the day-to-day management of digital collections and related project staff including carrying out or supervising acquisitions, accessioning and cataloguing; training staff and volunteers in systems; development and maintenance of a trusted digital repository; project implementation planning; planning, implementing and supervising use of metadata standards; make data available and enhance discovery; and ensure data is maintained and stored. The following tasks were frequently listed as a part of the job description:

- Lead and advise efforts in planning, implementation, use and assessment of metadata content used in innovative tools, technologies and services involving a variety of formats (e.g. books, rare books, dissertations, theses, photographs, art slides, digital images, data sets, printed texts, manuscripts, audio-visual material, and three-dimensional objects);
- Champion, communicate and promote research data management;
- Scan and scope the landscape of practical data management globally;
- Ensure research data is accessible to external researchers and the general public in a way that is in keeping with legislative requirements, international agreements and government policy;
- Develop guidelines and templates for research data management plans;

- Develop, coordinate, and implement operating procedures and a workflow for digital content creation, born-digital content acquisition, and preservation;
- Advise on all phases of the lifecycle of digital content with the aim of long-term retention and access;
- Assist in the ongoing development of requirements and specifications, including formats and metadata, for digital material the institution solicits, accepts or purchases into its collections.

Digital curation and preservation-related tasks focussed on the development and implementation of preservation strategies, services and techniques as well as the development of sustained services in support of curation. The following are some frequent tasks found in job descriptions:

- Provide leadership and direction for preservation and conservation efforts;
- Establish workflows for the preservation of digital materials;
- Identify digital records of continuing institutional value;
- Assess feasibility and develop plans for digital projects to design and implement technical infrastructure;
- Evaluate conservation needs of items and determine optimal treatment and workflow;
- Research, test and implement solutions for digital preservation in line with accepted best practice and international standards;
- Prepare specifications for vended services supporting the digital conservation programme, evaluate responses to proposals for such services, make recommendations for selecting vendors and act on behalf of the institution as a technical liaison on preservation issues to vendors providing digital materials.

The majority of job advertisements listed tasks within the realm of project or programme management, such as day-to-day budgetary monitoring, annual estimating and operational planning; monitoring the progress of projects and programmes of work to ensure that current standards, milestones and targets are met and objectives achieved; and driving delivery of work package or project objectives within agreed budget, timescales, and professional standards, meeting targets and negotiating external dependencies. Potential employees would be required to prepare workflows, offer technical advice, recommend long-range programme plans, goals, objectives, and milestones, carry out reviews and prepare reports. The main goal of these tasks is to increase project efficiency, identify problem areas, and address and resolve policy issues that involve major areas of uncertainty in approach or methodology. Specific tasks included:

- Complex analyses;

- Written reports;
- Organising special committees, workshops or other gatherings;
- Initiating programme reviews;
- Developing or fostering cross-agency activities.

Tasks related to trusted digital repositories and/or archives stated that the candidate would be responsible, in many cases, for the architecture development and management, supporting migration, refining metadata schema, providing user-support and engaging in promotional activities.

Specific tasks included:

- Generation of metadata and preparation for the archive
- Development of written documentation, policies and procedures governing the management of the data repository service;
- Development and maintenance of an accurate, complete and accessible catalogue and repository of all research data/collections created or held;
- Shaping the archives' online presence and strategic marketing to audiences;
- Develop data models and system architectures to guide the development ingest, registry, and repository workflows for the submission and preservation of science and engineering data;
- Provide direct assistance and user education services to clients and patrons of the institution's repository;
- Actively seek out new user communities and content for the digital repository and other digital storage and retrieval systems.

Many tasks in the job descriptions focussed on establishing resources institutionally and beyond, as well as providing teaching and training, including awareness raising of current and emerging digital strategies and theories and consulting on specific projects. Tasks included:

- Support the work of researchers and enable data discovery and retrieval of data sets across Europe;
- Participate in the activities related to acquiring, organising and providing access to the institution's digital resources;
- Design produce and pilot training materials and document outcomes for the wider community;
- Provide direct consulting, educational and reference services to faculty and students related to the collection, preservation and use of data (including meeting funding

agency data management requirements) in the form of one-on-one meetings, classroom instruction, workshops, and presentations;

- Contribute to the teaching mission of the university (both formal and informal for internal and external audiences) encompassing online learning tools, workshops featuring research support, one-on-one training and instruction, creating inquiry-based assignments, individual research consultations, and developing curricula;
- Participate in and lead institutional initiatives, committees and task forces relating to data management and storage;
- Provide leadership and vision in planning and implementing future digital library development.

Technical tasks included activities such as: capture and manage content from the web using bespoke software and perform quality assurance checks on harvested web content; maintain software development project schedules and perform acceptance testing; lead system development including specifications and requirements for systems; research and analyse suitable software; analyse the effectiveness of previous solution developments and recommend and lead enhancements; monitors and contribute to the development of local, national, and international metadata standards and trends; convert electronic and paper-based records to searchable online data sets; create born-digital documents in open source formats; and engage in ongoing qualitative and quantitative assessment of library digital services through data gathering and analysis. Additionally, successful candidates would be tasked with treating rare and special collections materials and implementing ontology frameworks.

Maintaining awareness of trends in digital libraries, digital preservation, curation of digital objects and data management was a very central task to many job descriptions. Practitioners would be required to contribute to the development of best practices, standards and policies for long-term protection and access to digital objects. Creating and maintaining documentation, anticipating future trends in an evolving digital environment and review of existing practices are all elements of these tasks.

Candidates would be tasked with the effective supervision of assigned employees (part-time, full-time, volunteers, and graduate assistants) including, in many cases, all required training, career development and performance reviews. This task frequently includes setting goals, development and assessment, future planning, and maintaining relationships.

Several job descriptions included tasks around seeking and/or managing grant funding; requiring the successful candidate to identify funding sources and contribute to the preparation of funding proposals.

The data collected from the job advertisements demonstrates the diversity and wide scope of the tasks and activities associated with positions in the field of digital preservation and curation. The areas of activity comprise technical and digital preservation-specific areas as well as fields of activity of a more general kind, like communications and outreach or project management.

5.4 Skills, competences and knowledge

As described above, staff working in the field of digital preservation and curation are involved in a broad range of tasks and activities. Similar to the sets of tasks and skills assessed in the survey, these can be divided into two groups: a group of general skills that are important for digital preservation and curation, but are also relevant in many other contexts, e.g. communication, management or leadership skills, and a group of digital preservation-specific or technical skills or knowledge.

5.4.1 General skills and competences

With regard to general skills and competences, commonly found keywords used to describe the ideal candidate for the job included: analytical, collaborative, creative, energetic, enthusiastic, flexible, highly motivated, independent, innovative, pro-active, professional, self-motivated, service-oriented, team player, versatile and web-savvy.

All but one of the job advertisements highlighted excellent interpersonal, oral, written and online communication skills as being desirable, if not required. Additional communication skills include confidence working with the public, consistent communication, strong presentation skills, and the ability to liaise confidently with academic and administrative staff. Several job descriptions looked for candidates who are able to interact effectively with audiences of diverse technological backgrounds and/or a wide variety of audiences.

The job advertisements stressed the importance of teamwork skills such as being an effective contributor, keeping others informed by sharing useful or relevant information to enhance team effectiveness, and a demonstrated ability to work effectively and collegially with staff at all levels, as well as with faculty, students, other institutions, vendors, corporate partners, and stakeholders. Some jobs looked for proven experience working on a project in large, decentralised and heterogeneous teams, others looked for the ability to work both

independently and as part of a dynamic team. The ability to foster collaborative relationships and work with sensitivity to an existing framework are valued team skills.

Project management stands out as a highly valued skill, with just over half of the job descriptions looking for demonstrated ability to plan, document and complete projects; strong project planning, management, and execution skills; analytical, organisational and problem-solving skills; as well as the ability to prioritise and work to deadlines. Several job descriptions looked for candidates to have a strong understanding of project management principles, concepts, methodologies and techniques.

A small percentage of job descriptions looked for a candidate with proven experience managing and forecasting budgets; good listening skills, a high degree of customer service and experience in a customer service role; as well as successful supervisory experience.

Many of the job advertisements stated that time management including the ability to multi-task, manage multiple projects simultaneously, and demonstrated ability to meet deadlines and goals was a must for candidates to be successful. Additionally, a quarter of the job descriptions highlighted a need for a flexible and adaptable attitude to a rapidly evolving working environment, stating that candidates should demonstrate their ability to work successfully with rapidly changing technology. Ideal candidates should have the ability to engage with stakeholders to lead change, as well as approach change with flexibility, innovation and creativity. The majority of job advertisements required candidates to have developed teamwork, project management and communication skills.

5.4.2 Digital preservation-specific and technical skills, knowledge and experiences

In terms of the digital preservation-specific and technical skills, employers prefer the ideal candidates to have not only theoretical knowledge but also practical experience. Job advertisements seek from one to seven years (varied by role and institution) previous professional experience in digital archives, content management, supervisory, information technology/informatics, lifecycle data management, programming, e-records and information management, electronic research data and digital preservation. Work with archival resources, repositories, institutional records (physical and digital preservation), digital library collections, as well as relevant project experience is frequently required. Many job descriptions prefer previous professional experience working in an academic, library, museum or archival setting.

Technical experience includes:

- Software development;
- Scientific metadata conventions and standards;
- Information analysis methods;
- Metadata structures and definition including Dublin Core, EAD, LCSH, MARC, MeSH, METS, MIX, MODS, NISO Image, PREMIS, TEI, TGM etc.;
- XML;
- Authority records including AACR2 and RDA;
- Classification schema including LCC and NLMC;
- CRI structures, research policies and trends;
- Relational databases;
- Metadata Manipulation and scripting languages including PHP, Perl, Java, Python and XSLT;
- Repository and content management platforms including bepress, CONTENTdm, Fedora, Eprints and DSpace;
- Software applications including SPSS and QDAMiner;
- Supporting long-term archiving;
- Working with tools that verify file authenticity, search for personal information and harvest websites;
- Employing metadata schema/mark-up standards;
- Using controlled vocabularies;
- Digital serials;
- Knowledge bases (i.e. Serial Solutions);
- Digital conversion for a variety of formats including audio/video;
- Interface development for the World Wide Web;
- Ontologies in the sciences;
- Linked open data and/or bibliometrics;
- Library standards, technologies and techniques including OAI, OAI/PMH, Z39.50 and TRAC;
- Taxonomies;
- File conversion tools;
- Visualisation techniques;
- Image capture and manipulation;
- Project management tools including Microsoft Project and Basecamp;
- Desktop productivity software including Microsoft Office and OpenOffice.

Many job advertisements are concerned with finding a candidate with experience in developing and implementing policies, procedures, and best practices as well as applying best practices and standards to digitisation and preservation processes. Grant writing experience, familiarity with funders and funding requirements, and experience in administering grants was frequently required.

The majority of job descriptions require experience managing digital projects and/or digital collections; familiarity with the research data life cycle: creation, processing, analysing, preserving, providing access to, and re-using; demonstrated experience curating digital content in an archival repository; records management training and experience; evidence of strong research orientation; evidence of strong record of public service; experience in a scholarly communication or research environment; publishing (including open access) and successful collaboration on major preservation projects.

Several job descriptions indicated required knowledge of applicable provisions of copyright law and permissions as they relate to digital collections. Job descriptions indicated that candidates should be familiar with and/or have knowledge (varying in degrees from working knowledge to proven and demonstrated knowledge) of the Open Archival Information Systems reference model; digital preservation and curation practices (open-source and vendor-based); auditing procedures as they relate to digital preservation and the Trustworthy Repositories Audit and Certification Checklist; as well as current and evolving approaches and trends. The ideal candidate must understand business strategies; functions and information needs and be able to translate them into business and system requirements, policies and standards.

Job advertisements included knowledge of the following:

- Digital information management;
- Digital preservation practice and theory;
- Current models and tools used by academic libraries for the access and discoverability of e-resources;
- Research process;
- Working in an academic or research library;
- Issues and technical challenges related to data management/curation;
- Digital Humanities;
- Concepts of distributed architectures, technologies and information infrastructures;
- Management, preservation and access of e-records;
- Grant funding agencies, grant writing and oversight;

- Outcome based planning and evaluation criteria.

Job descriptions looked for competences such as the ability to select the appropriate standards and tools for web authoring (i.e. XHTML, CSS, XSL, PHP), content management systems (i.e. Drupal, Wordpress), and metadata schema (EAD, MODS, METS, PREMIS); and initiate implementation of current trends in web authoring and archival access tools; competence when interfacing with information technology and information science. It was noted in several job descriptions that candidates should demonstrate capacity to analyse complex situations to transform practices and/or resolved issues, as well as reason insightfully when presented with a technical problem and present coherent arguments for a chosen way forward.

5.5 Degrees, qualifications and background

Job advertisements expressed a strong preference for an advanced degree. Most of them stated that a master's degree or equivalent would be required. Many job descriptions specified that the MA should be in Library Information Sciences, stating that Archival Science, Archival Studies, or a degree in a relevant academic field would also be acceptable. In addition, job descriptions from the United States specified that the MA should be ALA-accredited. In one case, a description stated that a BA degree with 3-6 years experience would be acceptable. Fields of study in the job descriptions include: Library and Information Science, Archival Studies, Information Science, Archival Science, Public History, History, Science, Engineering, Computer Science, Humanities, Information Management and Digital Humanities.

Several job descriptions highlighted a requirement of formal training in conversion techniques on a wide range of library materials as well as implementation of digital preservation solutions and strategies. Job advertisements for professor positions described their ideal candidate as someone with evidence of excellence in teaching and proven record of outstanding scholarship.

5.6 Summary

The analysis of job advertisements shows that the task responsibilities of professionals working in the field of digital preservation and curation are manifold and cover a broad spectrum. Tasks include generic activities as well as activities that are of technical nature and/or specific to the field. General fields of activity include communications, outreach and liaison, project management, teaching and training, supervisory and grants and funding. Frequently mentioned digital preservation-specific or technical task areas are digital

collection and data management, digital curation and preservation, trusted repository and archive, technical tasks as well as best practice and documentation.

Corresponding to the extensive scope of task responsibilities, the skills, competences and knowledge sought of ideal candidates cover a broad spectrum. Communication, collaboration and team work skills as well as project management skills stand out with regard to general skills, being required or indicated as desirable in the majority of job descriptions. In terms of the digital preservation and technical skills, the requirements also specify a variety of areas including: digital archives, digital library collections, trusted repositories, lifecycle data management, information technology, programming, metadata, current long term preservation tools as well as policies, standards and best practices. In many cases, not only theoretical knowledge was required, but practical experience as well.

Job advertisements expressed a strong preference for an advanced degree; most of them stated that a master's degree or equivalent would be required. The preferred fields of study were Library and Information Science and Archival Studies or Science, with many job descriptions stating that a relevant academic field, such as Information Science, Computer Science or Humanities, would also be acceptable.

The information obtained from the job advertisements with regard to the tasks, skills and competences relevant in the field of digital preservation and curation underpins the findings of the survey. The task responsibilities and the corresponding skills, competences and knowledge are wide-ranging and cover many digital preservation-specific and technical as well as general areas. This diversity should be taken into account when designing training.

6. Summary and Conclusion

The findings of our research illustrate the difficult situation many organisations of the cultural heritage sector as well as scientific institutions find themselves in at the moment. More than 90% of the survey respondents stated that their organisation already stores or plans to store digital materials for long-term preservation. However, around 12% of them also indicated that there are no staff assigned to the corresponding tasks. This particularly applies to smaller institutions, which constitute the majority of cultural heritage organisations. In addition, more than half of the respondents reported that their organisation does not plan to hire staff for digital preservation tasks in the future. In their comments, many respondents pointed out that budget constraints are the main reason for this. Some also noted that there are not enough skilled candidates on the labour market.

The lack of properly skilled staff is also brought up as a major issue by the focus group participants. Again, the reasons given for this are a lack of funding that prevents the hiring of new staff and a lack of qualified applicants. In terms of the latter, it is particularly difficult to find professionals with both subject or domain knowledge and technical expertise. Another challenge is the ongoing and constant rate of change in the field. This requires staff to permanently keep up to date with new developments. Across the groups participants stated a lack of appropriate training offers.

In summary, the findings described above suggest a great demand for training in digital preservation and curation to help the staff of cultural heritage institutions to acquire the skills and competences needed to take care of digital holdings.

The information gathered in the survey, the focus groups and the job advertisement analysis consistently indicates that the necessary skills and competences are wide-ranging and cover various areas. Among them, digital preservation-specific skills and technical expertise are regarded crucial. But a number of generic skills are considered equally important, particularly social skills, such as communication and collaborating with others.

In the survey, all of the given options for digital preservation-specific and technical skills were considered to be either important or essential by more than 90% of the respondents. They included: preservation and data management planning, ensuring access, managing data, evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation, storing data, ingesting data, research, development and implementation of digital preservation environments and

administering the archive. As for the general skills, collaborating with others, communicating with others and affinity for technology stood out with more than 95% of the respondents considering them to be either essential or important. Managing projects and training others were considered to be of high importance as well.

Other areas mentioned in this respect in the focus groups and the job advertisements include: knowledge of the organisation and the subject domain as well as archival, library or information science. In addition, people working in the field should ideally have an open minded attitude, the willingness to learn, the ability to think in structures and processes as well as a solution-focused way of thinking.

Both the respondents of the survey and the focus group participants indicate a substantial need for training with respect to digital preservation-specific and technical skills as well as general skills.

In terms of the digital preservation-specific and technical skills, the percentage of survey respondents signifying a great or moderate training need was between 86% and 96% for each of the given areas (including general/ basic knowledge, preservation and data management planning, preservation tools, information modelling and metadata, trusted repositories, strategic planning and policies, technical systems and legal aspects).

With regard to the general skills, between 60% and 85% of the respondents indicated either a great or moderate need for training. The greatest need for training is stated in terms of liaising between customers and information technology experts, followed by communication, project management and networking with people.

The areas where the survey results suggest the most pressing need are general and basic knowledge of digital preservation issues, preservation and data management planning, and preservation tools.

With respect to the training methods that were regarded as most suitable for their organisation by the survey respondents, one method clearly stood out – small group work shops were favoured by 75.3%. Blended learning (a mixture of face-to-face instruction and online training) was favoured by 38.6% and ranked as the second most popular form of training.

In terms of the time frame considered most suitable, the trend in the survey is similar. By far the most popular time frame was one time training events of 1-2 work days. Next in line were one time events of 3-5 work days. Training forms that require more time, such as courses of 1-4 hours a week for one or more semesters or recurring 1-2 week block courses for several semesters were regarded less suitable. The comments for this question suggest this pattern of preferences is related to time constraints caused by heavy workloads.

The best method and time frame indicated by the focus group participants are similar, but not exactly the same. Three forms of training were frequently mentioned across the groups: blended learning, courses of one to two weeks' length and short-term courses of a few days. Blended learning emerged as the most popular method, because it allows working staff to reconcile job and training more easily. Several participants also advocated long-term courses, such as a 1-2 year master's degree, as well as the restructuring of the basic professional education and training for library, archive and museum professionals to integrate at least basic knowledge of digital preservation and curation issues. In addition, participants stressed the importance of building a bridge between theory and practical application.

In conclusion, the results of the research suggest a great demand for training in digital preservation and curation that arises from a severe lack of qualified staff in the field. The findings revealed a broad spectrum of skills and competences relevant for staff involved in digital preservation. When designing training, this diversity as well as the integration of practical application and the suitability of the format for working staff should be taken into account.

Appendix

A. Survey Questionnaire

DigCurV: Survey on training needs

As part of the EU funded project “Digital Curator Vocational Education Europe” (DigCurV), we are conducting this survey on the training needs of staff in cultural institutions across Europe and internationally in the field of digital preservation and digital curation, which deals with maintaining and preserving digital data to ensure its long-term availability.

The survey has 18 questions and will take you about 15 minutes to complete. It is structured into the four parts below:

- basic information about your organisation;
- design of training measures;
- skills and competences required for digital preservation/curation;
- training needs in digital preservation/curation.

The information you provide will contribute to the design of a curriculum framework for training in digital preservation/curation by DigCurV. For more information about the project and the results of the survey, please see the project website: www.digcur-education.org or contact: info@digcur-education.org.

Note on data protection

The information you give in this survey will be anonymised and only used for the purpose of this survey or future research on the same topic, it will be treated as confidential according to the German Federal Data Protection Act (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz/BDSG). You can find more information on our data protection policy here: [\(link\)](#)

If you have any questions about the survey, please contact:

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DigCurV Survey on Training Needs - Part 1: General Information

1. Which of the following best describes the type of your organisation?
(multiple answers allowed)
 - National, Federal or Legal Deposit Library
 - Research or University Library
 - Museum
 - Archive
 - University
 - Research Centre
 - Scientific Association
 - Company
 - Other (please specify)

2. In which country is your organisation located?

3. Approximately how many Full Time Equivalents (FTE) does your organisation employ?
 - 1 – 25 FTEs
 - 26 – 100 FTEs
 - 101 – 300 FTEs
 - 301 – 500 FTEs
 - > 500 FTEs
 - I don't know

4. Which of the following tasks are you responsible for in your organisation?
(multiple answers allowed)
 - General management
 - Management for digital preservation/curation issues
 - Recruitment of staff
 - Education of students (i.e. future professionals) in digital preservation/curation
 - Training of practitioners in digital preservation/curation
 - Workflow planning for digital preservation/curation
 - Functional tasks in digital preservation/curation
 - Technical development/programming
 - Research
 - Other (please specify)

5. Does your institution store digital materials for long-term preservation?

- Yes, in-house
- Yes, but we out-source this task
- Yes, partly in-house, partly out-sourced
- No, but we plan to do so
- No
- I don't know

Comments: _____

5a. Which of the following statements about staff apply best to your organisation?
(multiple answers allowed)

- We have core-funded staff assigned exclusively to digital preservation/curation tasks
- We have externally funded staff on contract assigned exclusively to digital preservation/ curation tasks
- We have core-funded staff who work on digital preservation/curation and also for other sections/departments
- We have externally funded staff on contract who work on digital preservation/curation and also for other sections/departments
- We have staff assigned to managing out-sourced preservation of digital materials
- We have no staff who are currently assigned to digital preservation/curation tasks
- I don't know
- Other (please specify)

5.b How many members of your staff are involved in digital preservation/curation (both either full- or part-time)?

- _____ (please type the number)
- I don't know

6. Is your organisation planning to hire staff for digital preservation/curation tasks in future?
(multiple answers allowed)

- Yes, we are planning to hire staff exclusively assigned to digital preservation/curation tasks
- Yes, we are planning to hire staff partly assigned to digital preservation/curation amongst other duties
- No
- I don't know

Comments: _____

7. Is your organisation planning any training for existing staff?
(multiple answers allowed)

- We already provide training for our staff
- Yes, we are planning training for staff with previous experience in digital preservation/curation
- Yes, we are planning training for staff without previous experience in digital preservation/curation
- No
- I don't know

Comments: _____

DigCurV Survey on Training Needs - Part 2: Training

8. Does your organisation have a budget for training?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Comments: _____

9. Does your organisation have in-house training facilities? (Trainers, training suite, library of training materials etc.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Comments: _____

10. Is it important to your organisation that training for staff is certified?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Comments: _____

11. Which training methods for digital preservation/curation do you consider the most suitable for your organisation? (please choose up to 2 answers)

- Small group workshop (hands-on training)
- Large group workshop (lectures and practical exercises)
- Online training (webinar, self-paced courses or asynchronous learning)
- Blended learning (i.e. a mixture of face to face instruction and online components)
- Written manuals
- Supervised one-to-one training by a senior staff member
- Other (please specify)

Comments: _____

12. Which time frame for training in digital preservation/curation do you consider the most suitable for your organisation? (please choose up to 2 answers)

- One-time event of 1-2 work days
- One-time event of 3-5 work days
- Course of 1-4 hours a week for one semester
- Course of 1-4 hours a week for two or more semesters
- Recurring block course of one to two weeks for several semesters
- Other (please specify)

Comments: _____

DigCurV Survey on Training Needs - Part 3: Tasks, skills and competences

13: In terms of the work of staff involved in digital preservation/curation, how important do you consider the following general tasks/skills?

	Essential	Important	Not important	Non essential	I don't know
Communicating with others	<input type="radio"/>				
Collaborating with others	<input type="radio"/>				
Affinity for technology	<input type="radio"/>				
Leading a department or team	<input type="radio"/>				
Managing budgets	<input type="radio"/>				
Managing projects	<input type="radio"/>				
Training Others	<input type="radio"/>				
Organising conferences, workshops or other events	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

14. In terms of the work of staff involved in digital preservation/curation, how important do you consider the following digital preservation/curation-related tasks?

	Essential	Important	Not important	Non essential	I don't know
Research, development and implementation of digital preservation environment	<input type="radio"/>				
Evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation	<input type="radio"/>				
Ingesting data	<input type="radio"/>				
Storing data	<input type="radio"/>				
Managing data	<input type="radio"/>				
Administering the archive	<input type="radio"/>				
Preservation planning	<input type="radio"/>				
Ensuring access	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

DigCurV Survey on Training Needs - Part 4: Training needs

15. How would you assess the training needs of digital preservation staff in the following general skills?

	Great need	Moderate need	Hardly any need	Not needed	I don't know
Communication	<input type="radio"/>				
Networking with people	<input type="radio"/>				
Liaising between customers & information technology experts	<input type="radio"/>				
Administration & finances	<input type="radio"/>				
Project management	<input type="radio"/>				
Training others	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

16. How would you assess the training needs of digital preservation staff in the following digital preservation-specific and technical areas?

	Great need	Moderate need	Hardly any need	Not needed	I don't know
General knowledge / basic knowledge of digital preservation issues	<input type="radio"/>				
Strategic planning and policies	<input type="radio"/>				
Trusted repositories	<input type="radio"/>				
Preservation and data management planning	<input type="radio"/>				
Information modelling and metadata	<input type="radio"/>				
Preservation tools	<input type="radio"/>				
Technical systems	<input type="radio"/>				
Legal aspects	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

17. In which of the following digital preservation-related field/s is the need for training most pressing?

- General knowledge / basic knowledge of digital preservation issues
- Strategic planning and policies
- Trusted repositories
- Preservation and data management planning
- Information modelling and metadata
- Preservation tools
- Technical Systems
- Legal aspects
- Communication
- Networking with people
- Coordinating between customers and information technology experts
- Administration and finances
- Project management
- Training others
- Other (please specify)

18. You have come to the end of the survey now. Thank you very much for your cooperation. If you would like to add any additional comments or recommendations, please feel free to use the box below.

B. Detailed Tables

Table 16: Countries

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Germany	122	26.9	27.2	27.2
	United States of America	56	12.3	12.5	39.6
	United Kingdom	42	9.3	9.4	49.0
	Ireland	37	8.1	8.2	57.2
	Switzerland	23	5.1	5.1	62.4
	Italy	22	4.8	4.9	67.3
	Lithuania	19	4.2	4.2	71.5
	Belgium	18	4.0	4.0	75.5
	Netherlands	16	3.5	3.6	79.1
	Spain	8	1.8	1.8	80.8
	Canada	7	1.5	1.6	82.4
	Denmark	6	1.3	1.3	83.7
	Portugal	6	1.3	1.3	85.1
	Austria	5	1.1	1.1	86.2
	Sweden	5	1.1	1.1	87.3
	Australia	5	1.1	1.1	88.4
	France	4	.9	.9	89.3
	Hungary	4	.9	.9	90.2
	Romania	4	.9	.9	91.1
	Serbia	4	.9	.9	92.0
	Czech Republic	3	.7	.7	92.7
	Greece	3	.7	.7	93.3
	New Zealand	3	.7	.7	94.0
	Croatia	2	.4	.4	94.4
	Latvia	2	.4	.4	94.9
	Luxembourg	2	.4	.4	95.3
	Poland	2	.4	.4	95.8
	India	2	.4	.4	96.2
	South Africa	2	.4	.4	96.7
	Bulgaria	1	.2	.2	96.9
	Cyprus	1	.2	.2	97.1
	Finland	1	.2	.2	97.3
	Liechtenstein	1	.2	.2	97.6
Norway	1	.2	.2	97.8	
Slovenia	1	.2	.2	98.0	
Singapore	1	.2	.2	98.2	
Belize	1	.2	.2	98.4	
Cameroon	1	.2	.2	98.7	
Georgia	1	.2	.2	98.9	
Ghana	1	.2	.2	99.1	
Kenya	1	.2	.2	99.3	
Philippines	1	.2	.2	99.6	
Sri Lanka	1	.2	.2	99.8	
Trinidad	1	.2	.2	100.0	
	Total	449	98.9	100.0	
Missing	no answer	5	1.1		
	Total	454	100.0		

Table 17: Cross tabulation of “statements applying to staff” and the number of full time equivalents

	Full Time Equivalents (FTE)			Total
	1 - 25 FTEs	26 -100 FTEs	101 - 300 FTEs	
We have core-funded staff assigned exclusively to digital preservation/curation tasks	18 25.4%	17 23.9%	26 36.6%	61
We have externally funded staff on contract assigned exclusively to digital preservation/curation tasks	9 12.7%	11 15.5%	8 11.3%	28
We have core-funded staff who work on digital preservation/curation and also for other sections/departments	38 53.5%	46 64.8%	53 74.6%	137
We have externally funded staff on contract who work on digital preservation/curation and also for other sections/departments	5 7.0%	8 11.3%	8 11.3%	21
We have staff assigned to managing out-sourced preservation of digital materials	8 11.3%	7 9.9%	5 7.0%	20
We have no staff who are currently assigned to digital preservation/curation tasks	14 19.7%	10 14.1%	7 9.9%	31
Total	71	71	71	213

Table 18: Cross tabulation of “training plans” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Not planning any training	18 29.5%	35 40.7%	15 39.5%	29 30.2%	26 40.0%	17 37.8%	33 36.3%	130
Planning training for staff with previous experience in digital preservation/curation	23 37.7%	21 24.4%	10 26.3%	36 37.5%	19 29.2%	18 40.0%	24 26.4%	116
Planning training for staff without previous experience in digital preservation/curation	23 37.7%	33 38.4%	12 31.6%	35 36.5%	24 36.9%	13 28.9%	32 35.2%	131
Already providing training for our staff	25 41.0%	19 22.1%	8 21.1%	32 33.3%	11 16.9%	14 31.1%	24 26.4%	96
Total	61	86	38	96	65	45	91	370

Table 19: Cross tabulation of “training plans” and “countries”

	Countries Groups					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Not planning any training	33 33.7%	7 20.6%	62 37.6%	18 39.1%	7 30.4%	127
Planning training for staff with previous experience in digital preservation/curation	22 22.4%	12 35.3%	59 35.8%	13 28.3%	10 43.5%	116
Planning training for staff without previous experience in digital preservation/curation	32 32.7%	16 47.1%	51 30.9%	21 45.7%	10 43.5%	130
Already providing training for our staff	31 31.6%	11 32.4%	33 20.0%	13 28.3%	8 34.8%	96
Total	98	34	165	46	23	366

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 20: Cross tabulation of “budget for training” and “type of organisation”

		Type of organisation							Total
		National, Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Does the organisation have a budget for training?	Yes	41 70.7%	65 69.9%	23 51.1%	77 73.3%	51 69.9%	29 60.4%	65 71.4%	277
	No	17 29.3%	28 30.1%	22 48.9%	28 26.7%	22 30.1%	19 39.6%	26 28.6%	124
Total		58	93	45	105	73	48	91	401

Table 21: Cross tabulation of “budget for training” and “countries”

		Countries Groups					Total
		Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	World	
Does the organisation have a budget for training?	Yes	77 72.0%	36 90.0%	110 60.1%	34 77.3%	18 78.3%	275 69.3%
	No	30 28.0%	4 10.0%	73 39.9%	10 22.7%	5 21.7%	122 30.7%
Total		107 100.0%	40 100.0%	183 100.0%	44 100.0%	23 100.0%	397 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 22: Cross tabulation of “in-house training facilities” and “type of organisation”

		Type of Organisation						Total	
		Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre		Other
Does the organisation have in-house training facilities?	Yes	36 57.1%	54 55.7%	15 31.9%	53 50.5%	47 59.5%	24 50.0%	48 51.1%	215
	No	27 42.9%	43 44.3%	32 68.1%	52 49.5%	32 40.5%	24 50.0%	46 48.9%	209
Total		63	97	47	105	79	48	94	424

Table 23: Cross tabulation of “in-house training facilities” and “countries”

		Countries					Total
		Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Does the organisation have in-house training facilities?	Yes	59 51.3%	29 76.3%	91 47.6%	23 46.9%	11 42.3%	213 50.8%
	No	56 48.7%	9 23.7%	100 52.4%	26 53.1%	15 57.7%	206 49.2%
Total		115 100.0%	38 100.0%	191 100.0%	49 100.0%	26 100.0%	419 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 24: Cross tabulation of “importance of certification” and “type of organisation”

		Type of organisation						Total	
		Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre		Other
Is it important to the organisation that training is certified?	Yes	27 51.9%	30 40.0%	24 60.0%	36 44.4%	29 45.3%	21 51.2%	38 43.2%	165
	No	25 48.1%	45 60.0%	16 40.0%	45 55.6%	35 54.7%	20 48.8%	50 56.8%	182
Total		52	75	40	81	64	41	88	347

Table 25: Cross tabulation of” importance of certification” and “countries”

		Countries					Total
		Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Is it important to the organisation that training is certified?	Yes	34 37.8%	12 50.0%	95 58.6%	11 24.4%	13 56.5%	165 48.0%
	No	56 62.2%	12 50.0%	67 41.4%	34 75.6%	10 43.5%	179 52.0%
Total		90 100.0%	24 100.0%	162 100.0%	45 100.0%	23 100.0%	344 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 26: Cross tabulation of “most suitable method for training” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	National, Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Small group workshop (hands-on training)	49 75.4%	83 76.9%	29 59.2%	90 81.8%	62 75.6%	37 72.5%	75 72.1%	336
Large group workshop (lectures and practical exercises)	9 13.8%	6 5.6%	7 14.3%	9 8.2%	13 15.9%	7 13.7%	16 15.4%	57
Online training (webinar, self-paced courses or asynchronous learning)	10 15.4%	24 22.2%	6 12.2%	13 11.8%	13 15.9%	6 11.8%	20 19.2%	78
Blended learning (i.e. a mixture of face to face instruction and online components)	33 50.8%	36 33.3%	27 55.1%	35 31.8%	38 46.3%	19 37.3%	35 33.7%	172
Written manuals	7 10.8%	30 27.8%	11 22.4%	33 30.0%	18 22.0%	12 23.5%	25 24.0%	96
Supervised one-to-one training by a senior staff member	14 21.5%	22 20.4%	10 20.4%	29 26.4%	11 13.4%	16 31.4%	23 22.1%	90
Other	0 .0%	2 1.9%	0 .0%	3 2.7%	0 .0%	1 2.0%	1 1.0%	6
Total	65	108	49	110	82	51	104	446

Table 27: Cross tabulation of “most suitable method for training” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Small group workshop (hands-on training)	92 75.4%	36 87.8%	143 73.3%	40 71.4%	20 74.1%	331
Large group workshop (lectures and practical exercises)	16 13.1%	4 9.8%	30 15.4%	5 8.9%	1 3.7%	56
Online training (webinar, self-paced courses or asynchronous learning)	19 15.6%	8 19.5%	31 15.9%	18 32.1%	1 3.7%	77
Blended learning (i.e. a mixture of face to face instruction and online components)	32 26.2%	21 51.2%	82 42.1%	19 33.9%	15 55.6%	169
Written manuals	43 35.2%	6 14.6%	35 17.9%	11 19.6%	1 3.7%	96
Supervised one-to-one training by a senior staff member	22 18.0%	6 14.6%	42 21.5%	11 19.6%	9 33.3%	90
Other	3 2.5%	0 .0%	1 .5%	2 3.6%	0 .0%	6
Total	122	41	195	56	27	441

* excluding Germany and the UK

Table 28: Cross tabulation of “most suitable method for training” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for ^a										Total
	General management	Managem. for digital preservation/curation issues	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in digital preservation/curation	Training of practitioners in digital preservation/curation	Workflow planning for digital preservation/curation	Functional tasks in digital preservation/curation	Technical development /programming	Research	Other	
Small group workshop (hands-on training)	93 75.0%	181 75.7%	53 74.6%	56 73.7%	81 77.1%	165 76.7%	141 74.6%	62 69.7%	106 75.7%	51 70.8%	335
Large group workshop (lectures and practical exercises)	14 11.3%	27 11.3%	8 11.3%	11 14.5%	15 14.3%	25 11.6%	21 11.1%	10 11.2%	13 9.3%	12 16.7%	56
Online training (webinar, self-paced courses or asynchronous learning)	19 15.3%	47 19.7%	14 19.7%	13 17.1%	18 17.1%	38 17.7%	39 20.6%	27 30.3%	20 14.3%	16 22.2%	78
Blended learning (i.e. a mixture of face to face instruction and online components)	51 41.1%	84 35.1%	27 38.0%	34 44.7%	40 38.1%	74 34.4%	61 32.3%	29 32.6%	55 39.3%	26 36.1%	172
Written manuals	25 20.2%	56 23.4%	12 16.9%	12 15.8%	19 18.1%	51 23.7%	47 24.9%	26 29.2%	28 20.0%	15 20.8%	96
Supervised one-to-one training by a senior staff member	30 24.2%	57 23.8%	23 32.4%	16 21.1%	30 28.6%	56 26.0%	50 26.5%	17 19.1%	39 27.9%	16 22.2%	90
Other	1 .8%	1 .4%	0 .0%	1 1.3%	0 .0%	2 .9%	2 1.1%	0 .0%	1 .7%	3 4.2%	6
Total	124	239	71	76	105	215	189	89	140	72	445

List of alternative time frames indicated by the respondents

- full time program
- course of 4 hours for one semester (update)
- Periodic training on new procedures and technologies
- recurring 1-2 working days
- Recurring blocks of 1-2 days, continuously
- It is ongoing as needed for staff
- recurring 1-2 working days
- 1-2 days course
- weekly: case discussions
- continuous
- focused occasional
- occasional
- Periodic 1-2 hour sessions on specific topics
- a few days every year
- short courses or bite-sized online articles about particular aspects
- 2 events of 1-4 hours
- hands on for 1-2 hours
- 1-2 hour sessions
- repetition after 2-4 weeks
- personal advisory as long as the pilot project takes time
- Learning by practise
- cross-training for several months
- upon demand of individuals with similar literacy
- as needed
- Training/refresher as needed
- as needed
- if necessary
- Depends...
- Depends on the subject

Table 29: Cross tabulation of “most suitable time frame for training” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	National, Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
One-time event of 1-2 work days	36 56.3%	61 57.0%	24 49.0%	64 58.7%	37 45.1%	30 60.0%	66 63.5%	245
One-time event of 3-5 work days	25 39.1%	33 30.8%	12 24.5%	31 28.4%	23 28.0%	13 26.0%	26 25.0%	132
Course of 1-4 hours a week for one semester	10 15.6%	26 24.3%	12 24.5%	22 20.2%	15 18.3%	7 14.0%	17 16.3%	86
Course of 1-4 hours a week for two or more semesters	7 10.9%	4 3.7%	6 12.2%	7 6.4%	9 11.0%	6 12.0%	9 8.7%	40
Recurring block course of one to two weeks for several semesters	15 23.4%	13 12.1%	8 16.3%	21 19.3%	17 20.7%	6 12.0%	10 9.6%	64
Other	1 1.6%	9 8.4%	4 8.2%	10 9.2%	8 9.8%	6 12.0%	8 7.7%	33
Total	64	107	49	109	82	50	104	443

Table 30: Cross tabulation of “most suitable time frame for training” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
One-time event of 1-2 work days	74 61.2%	29 70.7%	97 50.0%	35 63.6%	9 33.3%	244
One-time event of 3-5 work days	34 28.1%	11 26.8%	56 28.9%	16 29.1%	13 48.1%	130
Course of 1-4 hours a week for one semester	16 13.2%	5 12.2%	48 24.7%	11 20.0%	4 14.8%	84
Course of 1-4 hours a week for two or more semesters	8 6.6%	2 4.9%	24 12.4%	1 1.8%	5 18.5%	40
Recurring block course of one to two weeks for several semesters	17 14.0%	5 12.2%	33 17.0%	2 3.6%	4 14.8%	61
Other	6 5.0%	4 9.8%	12 6.2%	10 18.2%	1 3.7%	33
Total	121	41	194	55	27	438

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 31: Cross tabulation of “most suitable time frame for training” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for digital preservation/curation issues	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in digital preservation/curation	Training of practitioners in digital preservation/curation	Workflow planning for digital preservation/curation	Functional tasks in digital preservation/curation	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
One-time event of 1-2 work days	66 54.1%	138 58.0%	39 56.5%	35 46.7%	64 61.5%	125 58.4%	108 57.4%	43 48.9%	84 60.9%	33 45.8%	244
One-time event of 3-5 work days	45 36.9%	74 31.1%	24 34.8%	21 28.0%	23 22.1%	61 28.5%	61 32.4%	32 36.4%	36 26.1%	15 20.8%	132
Course of 1-4 hours a week for one semester	23 18.9%	45 18.9%	15 21.7%	13 17.3%	21 20.2%	45 21.0%	38 20.2%	11 12.5%	25 18.1%	16 22.2%	86
Course of 1-4 hours a week for two or more semesters	12 9.8%	16 6.7%	9 13.0%	10 13.3%	5 4.8%	17 7.9%	18 9.6%	9 10.2%	12 8.7%	9 12.5%	40
Recurring block course of one to two weeks for several semesters	14 11.5%	35 14.7%	6 8.7%	13 17.3%	19 18.3%	32 15.0%	27 14.4%	16 18.2%	17 12.3%	10 13.9%	64
Other	6 4.9%	21 8.8%	7 10.1%	11 14.7%	14 13.5%	21 9.8%	19 10.1%	12 13.6%	12 8.7%	11 15.3%	33
Total	122	238	69	75	104	214	188	88	138	72	442

Skills and competences needed for digital preservation and curation

Importance of general tasks and skills – Frequency tables

Table 32: Collaborating with others

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	267	58.8	59.5	59.5
	Important	179	39.4	39.9	99.3
	Not important	2	.4	.4	99.8
	Non essential	1	.2	.2	100.0
	Total	449	98.9	100.0	
Missing	Total*	5	1.1		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 2, no answer: 3

Table 33: Communicating with others

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	255	56.2	56.8	56.8
	Important	186	41.0	41.4	98.2
	Not important	6	1.3	1.3	99.6
	Non essential	2	.4	.4	100.0
	Total	449	98.9	100.0	
Missing	Total*	5	1.1		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 2, no answer: 3

Table 34: Affinity for technology

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	180	39.6	40.4	40.4
	Important	247	54.4	55.4	95.7
	Not important	16	3.5	3.6	99.3
	Non essential	3	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	446	98.2	100.0	
Missing	Total*	8	1.8		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 2, no answer: 6

Table 35: Managing projects

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	113	24.9	25.5	25.5
	Important	258	56.8	58.2	83.7
	Not important	49	10.8	11.1	94.8
	Non essential	23	5.1	5.2	100.0
	Total	443	97.6	100.0	
Missing	Total*	11	2.4		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 6, no answer: 5

Table 36: Training others

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	84	18.5	18.9	18.9
	Important	258	56.8	58.1	77.0
	Not important	72	15.9	16.2	93.2
	Non essential	30	6.6	6.8	100.0
	Total	444	97.8	100.0	
Missing	Total*	10	2.2		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 5, no answer: 5

Table 37: Managing budgets

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	35	7.7	8.0	8.0
	Important	195	43.0	44.5	52.5
	Not important	147	32.4	33.6	86.1
	Non essential	61	13.4	13.9	100.0
	Total	438	96.5	100.0	
Missing	Total*	16	3.5		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 10, no answer: 6

Table 38: Leading a department or team

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	33	7.3	7.6	7.6
	Important	145	31.9	33.3	40.8
	Not important	194	42.7	44.5	85.3
	Non essential	64	14.1	14.7	100.0
	Total	436	96.0	100.0	
Missing*	Total	18	4.0		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 11, no answer: 7

Table 39: Organising conferences, workshops or other events

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	23	5.1	5.3	5.3
	Important	129	28.4	29.5	34.7
	Not important	162	35.7	37.0	71.7
	Non essential	124	27.3	28.3	100.0
	Total	438	96.5	100.0	
Missing	Total*	16	3.5		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 14, no answer: 2

Importance of general tasks and skills

Table 40: Cross tabulation of “collaborating with others” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	38 57.6%	66 62.3%	23 46.9%	70 63.6%	43 53.8%	26 52.0%	77 70.6%	267
Important	28 42.4%	38 35.8%	25 51.0%	40 36.4%	36 45.0%	23 46.0%	32 29.4%	179
Not important	0 .0%	1 .9%	1 2.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Non essential	0 .0%	1 .9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 1.3%	1 2.0%	0 .0%	1
Total	66	106	49	110	80	50	109	449

Table 41: Cross tabulation of “communicating with others” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	35 53.0%	64 60.4%	23 46.9%	63 57.3%	49 60.5%	27 52.9%	65 60.2%	255
Important	30 45.5%	40 37.7%	24 49.0%	45 40.9%	32 39.5%	24 47.1%	42 38.9%	186
Not important	1 1.5%	1 .9%	2 4.1%	1 .9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .9%	6
Non essential	0 .0%	1 .9%	0 .0%	1 .9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Total	66	106	49	110	81	51	108	449

Table 42: Cross tabulation of “affinity for technology” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	29 44.6%	50 48.1%	18 38.3%	40 36.7%	33 40.7%	18 35.3%	40 37.0%	180
Important	33 50.8%	50 48.1%	28 59.6%	65 59.6%	46 56.8%	32 62.7%	61 56.5%	247
Not important	3 4.6%	4 3.8%	1 2.1%	4 3.7%	1 1.2%	0 .0%	6 5.6%	16
Non essential	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 1.2%	1 2.0%	1 .9%	3
Total	65	104	47	109	81	51	108	446

Table 43: Cross tabulation of “managing projects” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	17 26.6%	32 30.8%	12 25.0%	26 23.9%	27 32.9%	13 26.0%	26 24.3%	113
Important	38 59.4%	58 55.8%	21 43.8%	69 63.3%	44 53.7%	23 46.0%	62 57.9%	258
Not important	6 9.4%	9 8.7%	10 20.8%	11 10.1%	7 8.5%	9 18.0%	13 12.1%	49
Non essential	3 4.7%	5 4.8%	5 10.4%	3 2.8%	4 4.9%	5 10.0%	6 5.6%	23
Total	64	104	48	109	82	50	107	443

Table 44: Cross tabulation of “training others” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	14 21.5%	28 26.7%	11 22.9%	13 12.0%	15 18.3%	6 12.0%	21 19.6%	84
Important	38 58.5%	50 47.6%	23 47.9%	72 66.7%	57 69.5%	30 60.0%	59 55.1%	258
Not important	12 18.5%	16 15.2%	9 18.8%	21 19.4%	7 8.5%	9 18.0%	18 16.8%	72
Non essential	1 1.5%	11 10.5%	5 10.4%	2 1.9%	3 3.7%	5 10.0%	9 8.4%	30
Total	65	105	48	108	82	50	107	444

Table 45: Cross tabulation of “managing budgets” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	3 4.6%	9 8.9%	1 2.1%	8 7.5%	9 11.0%	3 6.1%	11 10.4%	35
Important	36 55.4%	43 42.6%	25 52.1%	49 45.8%	34 41.5%	17 34.7%	47 44.3%	195
Not important	17 26.2%	36 35.6%	14 29.2%	34 31.8%	25 30.5%	23 46.9%	33 31.1%	147
Non essential	9 13.8%	13 12.9%	8 16.7%	16 15.0%	14 17.1%	6 12.2%	15 14.2%	61
Total	65	101	48	107	82	49	106	438

Table 46: Cross tabulation of “leading a department or team” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	7 10.8%	7 6.8%	4 8.5%	6 5.6%	9 11.4%	1 2.1%	6 5.6%	33
Important	27 41.5%	41 39.8%	15 31.9%	36 33.6%	26 32.9%	10 20.8%	33 30.8%	145
Not important	22 33.8%	40 38.8%	19 40.4%	44 41.1%	34 43.0%	31 64.6%	49 45.8%	194
Non essential	9 13.8%	15 14.6%	9 19.1%	21 19.6%	10 12.7%	6 12.5%	19 17.8%	64
Total	65	103	47	107	79	48	107	436

Table 47: Cross tabulation of “organising conferences, workshops or other events” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	5 7.8%	7 7.0%	3 6.3%	2 1.9%	4 5.0%	3 6.3%	3 2.8%	23
Important	25 39.1%	28 28.0%	12 25.0%	29 26.9%	26 32.5%	12 25.0%	32 29.9%	129
Not important	21 32.8%	32 32.0%	20 41.7%	46 42.6%	33 41.3%	21 43.8%	34 31.8%	162
Non essential	13 20.3%	33 33.0%	13 27.1%	31 28.7%	17 21.3%	12 25.0%	38 35.5%	124
Total	64	100	48	108	80	48	107	438

Table 48: Cross tabulation of “collaborating with others” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	63 52.5%	26 61.9%	119 59.5%	38 70.4%	19 67.9%	265 59.7%
Important	55 45.8%	16 38.1%	81 40.5%	16 29.6%	8 28.6%	176 39.6%
Not important	2 1.7%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 .5%
Non essential	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 3.6%	1 .2%
Total	120 100.0%	42 100.0%	200 100.0%	54 100.0%	28 100.0%	444 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 49: Cross tabulation of “communicating with others” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	58 48.7%	23 56.1%	113 56.2%	38 69.1%	20 71.4%	252 56.8%
Important	58 48.7%	17 41.5%	84 41.8%	17 30.9%	8 28.6%	184 41.4%
Not important	2 1.7%	1 2.4%	3 1.5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	6 1.4%
Non essential	1 .8%	0 .0%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 .5%
Total	119 100.0%	41 100.0%	201 100.0%	55 100.0%	28 100.0%	444 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 50: Cross tabulation of “affinity for technology” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	43 36.1%	19 45.2%	78 39.4%	29 53.7%	10 35.7%	179 40.6%
Important	68 57.1%	23 54.8%	109 55.1%	25 46.3%	18 64.3%	243 55.1%
Not important	7 5.9%	0 .0%	9 4.5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	16 3.6%
Non essential	1 .8%	0 .0%	2 1.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	3 .7%
Total	119 100.0%	42 100.0%	198 100.0%	54 100.0%	28 100.0%	441 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 51: Cross tabulation of “managing projects” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	14 12.0%	14 33.3%	47 23.9%	27 50.0%	9 32.1%	111 25.3%
Important	70 59.8%	24 57.1%	119 60.4%	25 46.3%	17 60.7%	255 58.2%
Not important	25 21.4%	3 7.1%	18 9.1%	1 1.9%	2 7.1%	49 11.2%
Non essential	8 6.8%	1 2.4%	13 6.6%	1 1.9%	0 .0%	23 5.3%
Total	117 100.0%	42 100.0%	197 100.0%	54 100.0%	28 100.0%	438 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 52: Cross tabulation of “training others” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	16 13.7%	12 28.6%	32 16.2%	16 29.6%	7 25.0%	83 18.9%
Important	66 56.4%	25 59.5%	114 57.6%	30 55.6%	21 75.0%	256 58.3%
Not important	27 23.1%	5 11.9%	34 17.2%	4 7.4%	0 .0%	70 15.9%
Non essential	8 6.8%	0 .0%	18 9.1%	4 7.4%	0 .0%	30 6.8%
Total	117 100.0%	42 100.0%	198 100.0%	54 100.0%	28 100.0%	439 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 53: Cross tabulation of “managing budgets” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	5 4.2%	2 4.8%	16 8.2%	6 11.8%	6 21.4%	35 8.1%
Important	50 42.4%	22 52.4%	93 47.9%	21 41.2%	7 25.0%	193 44.6%
Not important	48 40.7%	10 23.8%	64 33.0%	13 25.5%	10 35.7%	145 33.5%
Non essential	15 12.7%	8 19.0%	21 10.8%	11 21.6%	5 17.9%	60 13.9%
Total	118 100.0%	42 100.0%	194 100.0%	51 100.0%	28 100.0%	433 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 54: Cross tabulation of “leading a department or team” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	3 2.5%	3 7.1%	19 9.9%	3 5.8%	4 14.3%	32 7.4%
Important	27 22.9%	16 38.1%	62 32.5%	28 53.8%	10 35.7%	143 33.2%
Not important	65 55.1%	19 45.2%	84 44.0%	14 26.9%	11 39.3%	193 44.8%
Non essential	23 19.5%	4 9.5%	26 13.6%	7 13.5%	3 10.7%	63 14.6%
Total	118 100.0%	42 100.0%	191 100.0%	52 100.0%	28 100.0%	431 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 55: Cross tabulation of “organising conferences, workshops or other events” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	5 4.2%	2 5.0%	13 6.7%	1 1.9%	2 7.1%	23 5.3%
Important	30 25.4%	10 25.0%	66 34.0%	8 15.1%	13 46.4%	127 29.3%
Not important	54 45.8%	19 47.5%	63 32.5%	19 35.8%	6 21.4%	161 37.2%
Non essential	29 24.6%	9 22.5%	52 26.8%	25 47.2%	7 25.0%	122 28.2%
Total	118 100.0%	40 100.0%	194 100.0%	53 100.0%	28 100.0%	433 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 56: Cross tabulation of “collaborating with others” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	76 58.9%	145 60.7%	46 63.0%	44 58.7%	69 65.1%	132 61.7%	115 61.5%	50 56.2%	83 58.0%	47 62.7%	267
Important	52 40.3%	92 38.5%	27 37.0%	31 41.3%	37 34.9%	80 37.4%	72 38.5%	39 43.8%	59 41.3%	28 37.3%	178
Not important	1 .8%	2 .8%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 .9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Non essential	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .7%	0 .0%	1
Total	129	239	73	75	106	214	187	89	143	75	448

Table 57: Cross tabulation of “communicating with others” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for digital preservation/ curation	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	68 53.1%	134 56.1%	42 57.5%	44 57.9%	62 58.5%	120 56.1%	108 57.4%	43 47.8%	79 55.6%	41 55.4%	255
Important	57 44.5%	99 41.4%	30 41.1%	30 39.5%	42 39.6%	89 41.6%	77 41.0%	45 50.0%	61 43.0%	31 41.9%	185
Not important	2 1.6%	5 2.1%	1 1.4%	2 2.6%	2 1.9%	4 1.9%	2 1.1%	1 1.1%	1 .7%	2 2.7%	6
Non essential	1 .8%	1 .4%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .5%	1 .5%	1 1.1%	1 .7%	0 .0%	2
Total	128	239	73	76	106	214	188	90	142	74	448

Table 58: Cross tabulation of “affinity for technology” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	51 40.2%	103 43.3%	29 40.3%	31 40.8%	47 44.8%	89 41.8%	71 38.4%	42 47.2%	51 36.2%	23 30.7%	180
Important	68 53.5%	126 52.9%	39 54.2%	42 55.3%	56 53.3%	115 54.0%	110 59.5%	45 50.6%	86 61.0%	48 64.0%	246
Not important	8 6.3%	8 3.4%	4 5.6%	2 2.6%	2 1.9%	8 3.8%	3 1.6%	2 2.2%	4 2.8%	3 4.0%	16
Non essential	0 .0%	1 .4%	0 .0%	1 1.3%	0 .0%	1 .5%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 1.3%	3
Total	127	238	72	76	105	213	185	89	141	75	445

Table 59: Cross tabulation of “managing projects” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	28 22.2%	59 24.8%	15 20.8%	17 23.0%	28 26.7%	61 28.6%	59 31.7%	19 21.3%	29 20.7%	17 23.0%	113
Important	78 61.9%	143 60.1%	45 62.5%	49 66.2%	63 60.0%	128 60.1%	107 57.5%	52 58.4%	87 62.1%	43 58.1%	258
Not important	15 11.9%	27 11.3%	10 13.9%	8 10.8%	11 10.5%	19 8.9%	13 7.0%	13 14.6%	19 13.6%	8 10.8%	49
Non essential	5 4.0%	9 3.8%	2 2.8%	0 .0%	3 2.9%	5 2.3%	7 3.8%	5 5.6%	5 3.6%	6 8.1%	22
Total	126	238	72	74	105	213	186	89	140	74	442

Table 60: Cross tabulation of “training others” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	16 12.7%	39 16.5%	11 15.5%	14 18.7%	25 24.0%	33 15.5%	34 18.3%	11 12.2%	19 13.7%	15 20.3%	84
Important	82 65.1%	147 62.0%	44 62.0%	53 70.7%	68 65.4%	136 63.8%	116 62.4%	50 55.6%	97 69.8%	45 60.8%	258
Not important	22 17.5%	38 16.0%	11 15.5%	6 8.0%	8 7.7%	32 15.0%	25 13.4%	18 20.0%	15 10.8%	8 10.8%	72
Non essential	6 4.8%	13 5.5%	5 7.0%	2 2.7%	3 2.9%	12 5.6%	11 5.9%	11 12.2%	8 5.8%	6 8.1%	29
Total	126	237	71	75	104	213	186	90	139	74	443

Table 61: Cross tabulation of “managing budgets” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	9 7.3%	19 8.1%	3 4.3%	6 8.2%	7 6.9%	20 9.6%	21 11.7%	6 6.7%	7 5.1%	5 6.7%	35
Important	45 36.3%	109 46.6%	25 35.7%	34 46.6%	53 52.0%	94 45.0%	84 46.7%	38 42.2%	58 42.3%	30 40.0%	195
Not important	52 41.9%	70 29.9%	29 41.4%	21 28.8%	24 23.5%	66 31.6%	48 26.7%	31 34.4%	45 32.8%	28 37.3%	146
Non essential	18 14.5%	36 15.4%	13 18.6%	12 16.4%	18 17.6%	29 13.9%	27 15.0%	15 16.7%	27 19.7%	12 16.0%	61
Total	124	234	70	73	102	209	180	90	137	75	437

Table 62: Cross tabulation of “leading a department or team” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	6 5.0%	14 6.1%	6 8.7%	6 8.3%	7 6.9%	14 6.8%	17 9.5%	6 7.0%	8 5.8%	7 9.3%	33
Important	37 30.6%	74 32.0%	16 23.2%	23 31.9%	42 41.2%	71 34.5%	63 35.2%	27 31.4%	45 32.8%	24 32.0%	145
Not important	63 52.1%	109 47.2%	36 52.2%	29 40.3%	36 35.3%	92 44.7%	69 38.5%	38 44.2%	61 44.5%	31 41.3%	193
Non essential	15 12.4%	34 14.7%	11 15.9%	14 19.4%	17 16.7%	29 14.1%	30 16.8%	15 17.4%	23 16.8%	13 17.3%	64
Total	121	231	69	72	102	206	179	86	137	75	435

Table 63: Cross tabulation of “organising conferences, workshops and other events” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for ^a										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	5 4.1%	10 4.3%	2 2.9%	4 5.4%	6 5.8%	11 5.3%	9 4.9%	2 2.3%	7 5.0%	3 4.1%	23
Important	34 28.1%	65 27.9%	13 19.1%	23 31.1%	27 26.2%	56 26.9%	50 27.5%	23 26.4%	44 31.2%	25 33.8%	129
Not important	52 43.0%	92 39.5%	30 44.1%	27 36.5%	39 37.9%	77 37.0%	66 36.3%	34 39.1%	54 38.3%	24 32.4%	162
Non essential	30 24.8%	66 28.3%	23 33.8%	20 27.0%	31 30.1%	64 30.8%	57 31.3%	28 32.2%	36 25.5%	22 29.7%	123
Total	121	233	68	74	103	208	182	87	141	74	437

Importance of digital preservation-specific and technical tasks and skills – Frequency tables

Table 64: Preservation Planning

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	261	57.5	58.7	58.7
	Important	165	36.3	37.1	95.7
	Not important	17	3.7	3.8	99.6
	Non essential	2	.4	.4	100.0
	Total	445	98.0	100.0	
Missing	Total*	9	2.0		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 4, no answer: 5

Table 65: Ensuring access

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	259	57.0	58.2	58.2
	Important	157	34.6	35.3	93.5
	Not important	25	5.5	5.6	99.1
	Non essential	4	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	445	98.0	100.0	
Missing	Total*	9	2.0		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 5, no answer: 4

Table 66: Managing data

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	258	56.8	58.2	58.2
	Important	175	38.5	39.5	97.7
	Not important	9	2.0	2.0	99.8
	Non essential	1	.2	.2	100.0
	Total	443	97.6	100.0	
Missing	Total*	11	2.4		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 7, no answer: 4

Table 67: Evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	258	56.8	57.5	57.5
	Important	170	37.4	37.9	95.3
	Not important	15	3.3	3.3	98.7
	Non essential	6	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	449	98.9	100.0	
Missing	Total*	5	1.1		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 1, no answer: 4

Table 68: Storing data

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	248	54.6	56.0	56.0
	Important	173	38.1	39.1	95.0
	Not important	20	4.4	4.5	99.5
	Non essential	2	.4	.5	100.0
	Total	443	97.6	100.0	
Missing	Total*	11	2.4		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 7, no answer: 4

Table 69: Ingesting data

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	217	47.8	50.0	50.0
	Important	201	44.3	46.3	96.3
	Not important	16	3.5	3.7	100.0
	Total	434	95.6	100.0	
Missing	Total*	20	4.4		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 15, no answer: 5

Table 70: Research, development and implementation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	218	48.0	49.4	49.4
	Important	182	40.1	41.3	90.7
	Not important	31	6.8	7.0	97.7
	Non essential	10	2.2	2.3	100.0
	Total	441	97.1	100.0	
Missing	Total*	13	2.9		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 6, no answer: 7

Table 71: Administering the archive

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Essential	200	44.1	45.4	45.4
	Important	212	46.7	48.1	93.4
	Not important	27	5.9	6.1	99.5
	Non essential	2	.4	.5	100.0
	Total	441	97.1	100.0	
Missing	Total*	13	2.9		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 8, no answer: 5

Importance of digital preservation-specific and technical tasks and skills – Cross tabulations

Table 72: Cross tabulation of “preservation planning” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	46 69.7%	69 65.1%	23 47.9%	67 61.5%	47 58.8%	29 58.0%	57 53.3%	261
Important	19 28.8%	31 29.2%	23 47.9%	38 34.9%	29 36.3%	20 40.0%	45 42.1%	165
Not important	1 1.5%	4 3.8%	2 4.2%	4 3.7%	4 5.0%	1 2.0%	5 4.7%	17
Non essential	0 .0%	2 1.9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Total	66	106	48	109	80	50	107	445

Table 73: Cross tabulation of “ensuring access” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	41 62.1%	64 60.4%	22 44.9%	67 62.6%	48 60.8%	33 66.0%	59 54.6%	259
Important	21 31.8%	36 34.0%	23 46.9%	33 30.8%	27 34.2%	15 30.0%	38 35.2%	157
Not important	3 4.5%	5 4.7%	4 8.2%	6 5.6%	4 5.1%	1 2.0%	10 9.3%	25
Non essential	1 1.5%	1 .9%	0 .0%	1 .9%	0 .0%	1 2.0%	1 .9%	4
Total	66	106	49	107	79	50	108	445

Table 74: Cross tabulation of “managing data” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	44 67.7%	65 62.5%	19 39.6%	66 61.1%	39 48.8%	25 51.0%	71 65.1%	258
Important	20 30.8%	35 33.7%	28 58.3%	41 38.0%	38 47.5%	24 49.0%	38 34.9%	175
Not important	1 1.5%	3 2.9%	1 2.1%	1 .9%	3 3.8%	0 .0%	0 .0%	9
Non essential	0 .0%	1 1.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1
Total	65	104	48	108	80	49	109	443

Table 75: Cross tabulation of “evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	39 59.1%	62 58.5%	19 38.8%	71 65.1%	49 60.5%	24 48.0%	62 56.9%	258
Important	25 37.9%	37 34.9%	29 59.2%	36 33.0%	28 34.6%	24 48.0%	39 35.8%	170
Not important	1 1.5%	6 5.7%	0 .0%	2 1.8%	4 4.9%	2 4.0%	5 4.6%	15
Non essential	1 1.5%	1 .9%	1 2.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	3 2.8%	6
Total	66	106	49	109	81	50	109	449

Table 76: Cross tabulation of “storing data” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	42 64.6%	56 53.8%	22 44.9%	68 62.4%	44 55.0%	27 55.1%	61 56.5%	248
Important	20 30.8%	40 38.5%	26 53.1%	38 34.9%	30 37.5%	18 36.7%	43 39.8%	173
Not important	3 4.6%	8 7.7%	1 2.0%	2 1.8%	5 6.3%	3 6.1%	3 2.8%	20
Non essential	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .9%	1 1.3%	1 2.0%	1 .9%	2
Total	65	104	49	109	80	49	108	443

Table 77: Cross tabulation of “ingesting data” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	43 66.2%	47 45.6%	11 23.9%	73 67.6%	36 46.2%	23 46.9%	53 51.0%	217
Important	20 30.8%	52 50.5%	32 69.6%	34 31.5%	38 48.7%	26 53.1%	47 45.2%	201
Not important	2 3.1%	4 3.9%	3 6.5%	1 .9%	4 5.1%	0 .0%	4 3.8%	16
Total	65	103	46	108	78	49	104	434

Table 78: Cross tabulation of “research, development and implementation of a digital preservation/curation environment” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	38 58.5%	49 47.1%	12 25.5%	49 45.8%	43 53.1%	25 51.0%	53 49.1%	218
Important	23 35.4%	43 41.3%	24 51.1%	49 45.8%	35 43.2%	18 36.7%	44 40.7%	182
Not important	2 3.1%	10 9.6%	8 17.0%	6 5.6%	2 2.5%	4 8.2%	6 5.6%	31
Non essential	2 3.1%	2 1.9%	3 6.4%	3 2.8%	1 1.2%	2 4.1%	5 4.6%	10
Total	65	104	47	107	81	49	108	441

Table 79: Cross tabulation of “administering the archive” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Essential	36 54.5%	47 45.2%	19 38.8%	57 52.3%	28 35.4%	18 37.5%	51 47.7%	200
Important	29 43.9%	49 47.1%	27 55.1%	48 44.0%	44 55.7%	26 54.2%	47 43.9%	212
Not important	1 1.5%	7 6.7%	3 6.1%	4 3.7%	6 7.6%	4 8.3%	9 8.4%	27
Non essential	0 .0%	1 1.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 1.3%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Total	66	104	49	109	79	48	107	441

Table 80: Cross tabulation of “preservation planning” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	61 52.1%	31 73.8%	105 53.0%	41 74.5%	19 67.9%	257 58.4%
Important	49 41.9%	11 26.2%	83 41.9%	13 23.6%	8 28.6%	164 37.3%
Not important	6 5.1%	0 .0%	9 4.5%	1 1.8%	1 3.6%	17 3.9%
Non essential	1 .9%	0 .0%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 .5%
Total	117 100.0%	42 100.0%	198 100.0%	55 100.0%	28 100.0%	440 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 81: Cross tabulation of “ensuring access” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	51 44.7%	26 61.9%	113 56.2%	42 76.4%	24 85.7%	256 58.2%
Important	49 43.0%	15 35.7%	74 36.8%	13 23.6%	4 14.3%	155 35.2%
Not important	13 11.4%	0 .0%	12 6.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	25 5.7%
Non essential	1 .9%	1 2.4%	2 1.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	4 .9%
Total	114 100.0%	42 100.0%	201 100.0%	55 100.0%	28 100.0%	440 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 82: Cross tabulation of “managing data” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	57 49.6%	31 73.8%	115 57.8%	35 63.6%	18 66.7%	256 58.4%
Important	50 43.5%	11 26.2%	82 41.2%	20 36.4%	9 33.3%	172 39.3%
Not important	8 7.0%	0 .0%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	9 2.1%
Non essential	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .2%
Total	115 100.0%	42 100.0%	199 100.0%	55 100.0%	27 100.0%	438 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 83: Cross tabulation of “evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	62 52.5%	30 71.4%	105 52.5%	38 67.9%	21 75.0%	256 57.7%
Important	49 41.5%	12 28.6%	85 42.5%	16 28.6%	6 21.4%	168 37.8%
Not important	6 5.1%	0 .0%	6 3.0%	1 1.8%	1 3.6%	14 3.2%
Non essential	1 .8%	0 .0%	4 2.0%	1 1.8%	0 .0%	6 1.4%
Total	118 100.0%	42 100.0%	200 100.0%	56 100.0%	28 100.0%	444 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 84: Cross tabulation of “storing data” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	52 45.6%	28 66.7%	110 55.3%	37 67.3%	20 71.4%	247 56.4%
Important	51 44.7%	13 31.0%	82 41.2%	16 29.1%	8 28.6%	170 38.8%
Not important	9 7.9%	1 2.4%	7 3.5%	2 3.6%	0 .0%	19 4.3%
Non essential	2 1.8%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 .5%
Total	114 100.0%	42 100.0%	199 100.0%	55 100.0%	28 100.0%	438 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 85: Cross tabulation of “ingesting data” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	49 43.0%	25 62.5%	88 46.1%	31 55.4%	21 75.0%	214 49.9%
Important	61 53.5%	14 35.0%	96 50.3%	22 39.3%	7 25.0%	200 46.6%
Not important	4 3.5%	1 2.5%	7 3.7%	3 5.4%	0 .0%	15 3.5%
Total	114 100.0%	40 100.0%	191 100.0%	56 100.0%	28 100.0%	429 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 86: Cross tabulation of “research, development and implementation of digital preservation environment” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	45 39.1%	21 51.2%	100 51.0%	28 50.0%	23 82.1%	217 49.8%
Important	52 45.2%	18 43.9%	79 40.3%	25 44.6%	4 14.3%	178 40.8%
Not important	13 11.3%	2 4.9%	14 7.1%	1 1.8%	1 3.6%	31 7.1%
Non essential	5 4.3%	0 .0%	3 1.5%	2 3.6%	0 .0%	10 2.3%
Total	115 100.0%	41 100.0%	196 100.0%	56 100.0%	28 100.0%	436 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 87: Cross tabulation of “administering the archive” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Essential	45 39.1%	20 47.6%	85 43.4%	30 54.5%	17 60.7%	197 45.2%
Important	57 49.6%	20 47.6%	99 50.5%	24 43.6%	11 39.3%	211 48.4%
Not important	13 11.3%	1 2.4%	11 5.6%	1 1.8%	0 .0%	26 6.0%
Non essential	0 .0%	1 2.4%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 .5%
Total	115 100.0%	42 100.0%	196 100.0%	55 100.0%	28 100.0%	436 100.0%

* without Germany and the UK

Table 88: Cross tabulation of “preservation planning” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Essential	76 60.8%	151 63.2%	50 69.4%	48 64.0%	67 63.8%	131 60.9%	119 64.0%	55 61.8%	81 57.0%	43 58.9%	261
Important	45 36.0%	77 32.2%	16 22.2%	25 33.3%	34 32.4%	73 34.0%	58 31.2%	32 36.0%	55 38.7%	27 37.0%	164
Not important	4 3.2%	9 3.8%	5 6.9%	1 1.3%	4 3.8%	10 4.7%	8 4.3%	2 2.2%	5 3.5%	3 4.1%	17
Non essential	0 .0%	2 .8%	1 1.4%	1 1.3%	0 .0%	1 .5%	1 .5%	0 .0%	1 .7%	0 .0%	2
Total	125	239	72	75	105	215	186	89	142	73	444

Table 89: Cross tabulation of “ensuring access” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Essential	74 58.7%	147 61.5%	47 65.3%	46 61.3%	62 59.0%	127 59.3%	114 61.3%	51 57.3%	80 56.7%	40 53.3%	259
Important	43 34.1%	75 31.4%	19 26.4%	23 30.7%	36 34.3%	71 33.2%	59 31.7%	30 33.7%	53 37.6%	31 41.3%	156
Not important	9 7.1%	14 5.9%	5 6.9%	4 5.3%	6 5.7%	12 5.6%	12 6.5%	7 7.9%	5 3.5%	4 5.3%	25
Non essential	0 .0%	3 1.3%	1 1.4%	2 2.7%	1 1.0%	4 1.9%	1 .5%	1 1.1%	3 2.1%	0 .0%	4
Total	126	239	72	75	105	214	186	89	141	75	444

Table 90: Cross tabulation of “managing data” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	76 60.3%	147 61.8%	44 62.0%	31 41.9%	59 56.2%	126 58.9%	116 62.0%	49 55.1%	72 51.4%	42 57.5%	258
Important	48 38.1%	87 36.6%	25 35.2%	40 54.1%	45 42.9%	84 39.3%	68 36.4%	37 41.6%	65 46.4%	30 41.1%	174
Not important	2 1.6%	3 1.3%	1 1.4%	2 2.7%	1 1.0%	3 1.4%	3 1.6%	3 3.4%	2 1.4%	1 1.4%	9
Non essential	0 .0%	1 .4%	1 1.4%	1 1.4%	0 .0%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .7%	0 .0%	1
Total	126	238	71	74	105	214	187	89	140	73	442

Table 91: Cross tabulation of “evaluating and selecting data for long-term preservation” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	74 57.8%	139 57.9%	46 63.9%	44 58.7%	68 64.8%	129 60.0%	112 59.9%	48 53.3%	78 54.9%	45 60.0%	258
Important	47 36.7%	90 37.5%	23 31.9%	28 37.3%	34 32.4%	78 36.3%	69 36.9%	35 38.9%	61 43.0%	26 34.7%	169
Not important	5 3.9%	8 3.3%	2 2.8%	2 2.7%	2 1.9%	5 2.3%	4 2.1%	5 5.6%	2 1.4%	3 4.0%	15
Non essential	2 1.6%	3 1.3%	1 1.4%	1 1.3%	1 1.0%	3 1.4%	2 1.1%	2 2.2%	1 .7%	1 1.3%	6
Total	128	240	72	75	105	215	187	90	142	75	448

Table 92: Cross tabulation of “storing data” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	71 56.3%	137 57.3%	41 57.7%	36 48.6%	59 56.2%	119 55.6%	109 58.6%	50 56.8%	70 50.0%	38 52.1%	248
Important	50 39.7%	90 37.7%	28 39.4%	34 45.9%	38 36.2%	82 38.3%	73 39.2%	35 39.8%	63 45.0%	33 45.2%	172
Not important	5 4.0%	11 4.6%	2 2.8%	3 4.1%	6 5.7%	12 5.6%	3 1.6%	3 3.4%	7 5.0%	2 2.7%	20
Non essential	0 .0%	1 .4%	0 .0%	1 1.4%	2 1.9%	1 .5%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Total	126	239	71	74	105	214	186	88	140	73	442

Table 93: Cross tabulation of “ingesting data” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	57 47.1%	129 54.9%	42 60.9%	31 42.5%	58 55.8%	118 55.9%	101 55.2%	38 44.7%	62 45.3%	30 41.7%	217
Important	60 49.6%	100 42.6%	27 39.1%	39 53.4%	43 41.3%	88 41.7%	77 42.1%	45 52.9%	71 51.8%	40 55.6%	200
Not important	4 3.3%	6 2.6%	0 .0%	3 4.1%	3 2.9%	5 2.4%	5 2.7%	2 2.4%	4 2.9%	2 2.8%	16
Total	121	235	69	73	104	211	183	85	137	72	433

Table 94: Cross tabulation of “research, development and implementation of digital preservation environment” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	59 47.6%	115 48.9%	34 47.2%	34 45.3%	51 48.6%	104 48.8%	93 50.0%	47 53.4%	80 56.7%	40 55.6%	218
Important	54 43.5%	97 41.3%	31 43.1%	40 53.3%	45 42.9%	89 41.8%	81 43.5%	35 39.8%	56 39.7%	26 36.1%	181
Not important	7 5.6%	17 7.2%	6 8.3%	1 1.3%	6 5.7%	14 6.6%	8 4.3%	5 5.7%	4 2.8%	6 8.3%	31
Non essential	4 3.2%	6 2.6%	1 1.4%	0 .0%	3 2.9%	6 2.8%	4 2.2%	1 1.1%	1 .7%	0 .0%	10
Total	124	235	72	75	105	213	186	88	141	72	440

Table 95: Cross tabulation of “administering the archive” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Essential	55 44.0%	116 48.9%	35 48.6%	26 35.1%	48 46.2%	106 49.8%	94 50.5%	40 46.0%	56 40.0%	34 46.6%	200
Important	67 53.6%	102 43.0%	34 47.2%	44 59.5%	49 47.1%	92 43.2%	84 45.2%	42 48.3%	73 52.1%	37 50.7%	211
Not important	3 2.4%	17 7.2%	2 2.8%	3 4.1%	7 6.7%	14 6.6%	8 4.3%	4 4.6%	10 7.1%	2 2.7%	27
Non essential	0 .0%	2 .8%	1 1.4%	1 1.4%	0 .0%	1 .5%	0 .0%	1 1.1%	1 .7%	0 .0%	2
Total	125	237	72	74	104	213	186	87	140	73	440

A.VI Training needs with regard to digital preservation and curation

Training needs with regard to general skills – Frequency tables

Table 96: Liaising between customers and information technology experts

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	194	42.7	44.2	44.2
	Moderate need	181	39.9	41.2	85.4
	Hardly any need	57	12.6	13.0	98.4
	Not needed	7	1.5	1.6	100.0
	Total	439	96.7	100.0	
Missing	Total*	15	3.3		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 10, no answer: 5

Table 97: Communication

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	162	35.7	36.8	36.8
	Moderate need	206	45.4	46.8	83.6
	Hardly any need	60	13.2	13.6	97.3
	Not needed	12	2.6	2.7	100.0
	Total	440	96.9	100.0	
Missing	Total*	14	3.1		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 8, no answer: 6

Table 98: Project Management

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	150	33.0	33.9	33.9
	Moderate need	212	46.7	48.0	81.9
	Hardly any need	66	14.5	14.9	96.8
	Not needed	14	3.1	3.2	100.0
	Total	442	97.4	100.0	
Missing	Total*	12	2.6		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 7, no answer: 5

Table 99: Networking with people

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	147	32.4	33.4	33.4
	Moderate need	211	46.5	48.0	81.4
	Hardly any need	73	16.1	16.6	98.0
	Not needed	9	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	440	96.9	100.0	
Missing	Total*	14	3.1		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 9, no answer: 5

Table 100: Training others

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	101	22.2	23.1	23.1
	Moderate need	220	48.5	50.3	73.5
	Hardly any need	91	20.0	20.8	94.3
	Not needed	25	5.5	5.7	100.0
	Total	437	96.3	100.0	
Missing	Total*	17	3.7		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 9, no answer: 7

Table 101: Administration and finances

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	47	10.4	10.9	10.9
	Moderate need	214	47.1	49.7	60.6
	Hardly any need	140	30.8	32.5	93.0
	Not needed	30	6.6	7.0	100.0
	Total	431	94.9	100.0	
Missing	Total*	23	5.1		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 18, no answer: 5

Training needs with regard to general skills – Cross tabulations
Table 102: Cross tabulation of “liaising between customers and information technology experts” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	26 39.4%	50 49.0%	15 32.6%	45 41.7%	38 46.3%	21 41.2%	40 38.8%	194
Moderate need	34 51.5%	35 34.3%	22 47.8%	46 42.6%	33 40.2%	21 41.2%	49 47.6%	181
Hardly any need	5 7.6%	13 12.7%	9 19.6%	17 15.7%	11 13.4%	9 17.6%	11 10.7%	57
Not needed	1 1.5%	4 3.9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	3 2.9%	7
Total	66	102	46	108	82	51	103	439

Table 103: Cross tabulation of “communication” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	23 34.8%	44 43.6%	16 35.6%	36 33.6%	29 35.4%	11 21.6%	42 39.6%	162
Moderate need	31 47.0%	40 39.6%	23 51.1%	48 44.9%	41 50.0%	29 56.9%	49 46.2%	206
Hardly any need	10 15.2%	13 12.9%	4 8.9%	20 18.7%	12 14.6%	11 21.6%	10 9.4%	60
Not needed	2 3.0%	4 4.0%	2 4.4%	3 2.8%	0 .0%	0 .0%	5 4.7%	12
Total	66	101	45	107	82	51	106	440

Table 104: Cross tabulation of “project management” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	20 30.3%	42 40.8%	12 25.5%	37 33.9%	34 42.5%	13 25.5%	32 30.2%	150
Moderate need	36 54.5%	46 44.7%	20 42.6%	49 45.0%	33 41.3%	24 47.1%	53 50.0%	212
Hardly any need	6 9.1%	11 10.7%	11 23.4%	20 18.3%	12 15.0%	13 25.5%	14 13.2%	66
Not needed	4 6.1%	4 3.9%	4 8.5%	3 2.8%	1 1.3%	1 2.0%	7 6.6%	14
Total	66	103	47	109	80	51	106	442

Table 105: Cross tabulation of “networking with people” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	20 30.3%	32 32.0%	15 33.3%	29 27.1%	27 32.9%	16 31.4%	44 41.5%	147
Moderate need	33 50.0%	49 49.0%	20 44.4%	53 49.5%	41 50.0%	24 47.1%	44 41.5%	211
Hardly any need	11 16.7%	18 18.0%	8 17.8%	22 20.6%	13 15.9%	10 19.6%	15 14.2%	73
Not needed	2 3.0%	1 1.0%	2 4.4%	3 2.8%	1 1.2%	1 2.0%	3 2.8%	9
Total	66	100	45	107	82	51	106	440

Table 106: Cross tabulation of “training others” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	11 16.7%	29 28.2%	12 25.5%	13 12.3%	19 24.1%	11 22.4%	25 24.3%	101
Moderate need	39 59.1%	42 40.8%	24 51.1%	64 60.4%	42 53.2%	22 44.9%	52 50.5%	220
Hardly any need	15 22.7%	22 21.4%	7 14.9%	26 24.5%	17 21.5%	12 24.5%	20 19.4%	91
Not needed	1 1.5%	10 9.7%	4 8.5%	3 2.8%	1 1.3%	4 8.2%	6 5.8%	25
Total	66	103	47	106	79	49	103	437

Table 107: Cross tabulation of “administration and finances” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	4 6.1%	11 11.6%	5 10.6%	12 11.1%	8 10.0%	8 16.0%	9 8.6%	47
Moderate need	35 53.0%	47 49.5%	22 46.8%	51 47.2%	43 53.8%	17 34.0%	48 45.7%	214
Hardly any need	23 34.8%	31 32.6%	15 31.9%	37 34.3%	28 35.0%	20 40.0%	36 34.3%	140
Not needed	4 6.1%	6 6.3%	5 10.6%	8 7.4%	1 1.3%	5 10.0%	12 11.4%	30
Total	66	95	47	108	80	50	105	431

Table 108: Cross tabulation of “liaising between customers and information technology experts” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	44 37.3%	18 47.4%	96 48.5%	22 42.3%	12 42.9%	192 44.2%
Moderate need	51 43.2%	16 42.1%	78 39.4%	22 42.3%	13 46.4%	180 41.5%
Hardly any need	21 17.8%	4 10.5%	22 11.1%	6 11.5%	2 7.1%	55 12.7%
Not needed	2 1.7%	0 .0%	2 1.0%	2 3.8%	1 3.6%	7 1.6%
Total	118 100.0%	38 100.0%	198 100.0%	52 100.0%	28 100.0%	434 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 109: Cross tabulation of “communication” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	40 33.9%	8 20.5%	78 39.2%	19 35.8%	15 55.6%	160 36.7%
Moderate need	60 50.8%	21 53.8%	94 47.2%	21 39.6%	10 37.0%	206 47.2%
Hardly any need	14 11.9%	10 25.6%	23 11.6%	10 18.9%	1 3.7%	58 13.3%
Not needed	4 3.4%	0 .0%	4 2.0%	3 5.7%	1 3.7%	12 2.8%
Total	118 100.0%	39 100.0%	199 100.0%	53 100.0%	27 100.0%	436 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 110: Cross tabulation of “project management” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	22 18.6%	11 28.9%	75 37.7%	29 53.7%	10 35.7%	147 33.6%
Moderate need	70 59.3%	20 52.6%	86 43.2%	17 31.5%	17 60.7%	210 48.1%
Hardly any need	24 20.3%	7 18.4%	30 15.1%	5 9.3%	0 .0%	66 15.1%
Not needed	2 1.7%	0 .0%	8 4.0%	3 5.6%	1 3.6%	14 3.2%
Total	118 100.0%	38 100.0%	199 100.0%	54 100.0%	28 100.0%	437 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 111: Cross tabulation of “networking with people” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	38 32.2%	6 15.4%	79 39.5%	10 19.2%	12 44.4%	145 33.3%
Moderate need	58 49.2%	25 64.1%	88 44.0%	27 51.9%	12 44.4%	210 48.2%
Hardly any need	20 16.9%	8 20.5%	30 15.0%	13 25.0%	1 3.7%	72 16.5%
Not needed	2 1.7%	0 .0%	3 1.5%	2 3.8%	2 7.4%	9 2.1%
Total	118 100.0%	39 100.0%	200 100.0%	52 100.0%	27 100.0%	436 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 112: Cross tabulation of “training others” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	17 14.5%	8 21.6%	54 27.3%	12 22.6%	8 29.6%	99 22.9%
Moderate need	62 53.0%	22 59.5%	93 47.0%	25 47.2%	17 63.0%	219 50.7%
Hardly any need	28 23.9%	7 18.9%	40 20.2%	13 24.5%	1 3.7%	89 20.6%
Not needed	10 8.5%	0 .0%	11 5.6%	3 5.7%	1 3.7%	25 5.8%
Total	117 100.0%	37 100.0%	198 100.0%	53 100.0%	27 100.0%	432 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 113: Cross tabulation of “administration and finances” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe	USA	Other	
Great need	12 10.3%	1 2.6%	24 12.3%	4 7.8%	6 22.2%	47 11.0%
Moderate need	59 50.9%	23 60.5%	94 48.2%	23 45.1%	12 44.4%	211 49.4%
Hardly any need	38 32.8%	13 34.2%	61 31.3%	20 39.2%	7 25.9%	139 32.6%
Not needed	7 6.0%	1 2.6%	16 8.2%	4 7.8%	2 7.4%	30 7.0%
Total	116 100.0%	38 100.0%	195 100.0%	51 100.0%	27 100.0%	427 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 114: Cross tabulation of “liaising between customers and information technology experts” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Great need	54 43.5%	106 44.9%	28 40.6%	22 30.1%	42 41.6%	92 43.6%	81 44.3%	31 36.5%	60 42.9%	32 43.2%	194
Moderate need	53 42.7%	93 39.4%	30 43.5%	37 50.7%	43 42.6%	81 38.4%	68 37.2%	38 44.7%	61 43.6%	33 44.6%	180
Hardly any need	14 11.3%	32 13.6%	8 11.6%	12 16.4%	11 10.9%	33 15.6%	30 16.4%	13 15.3%	16 11.4%	8 10.8%	57
Not needed	3 2.4%	5 2.1%	3 4.3%	2 2.7%	5 5.0%	5 2.4%	4 2.2%	3 3.5%	3 2.1%	1 1.4%	7
Total	124	236	69	73	101	211	183	85	140	74	438

Table 115: Cross tabulation of “communication” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Great need	41 32.8%	75 31.6%	22 31.0%	27 35.5%	33 31.4%	69 32.7%	58 31.7%	25 29.1%	53 37.3%	35 47.3%	162
Moderate need	58 46.4%	111 46.8%	30 42.3%	34 44.7%	49 46.7%	98 46.4%	91 49.7%	47 54.7%	66 46.5%	29 39.2%	205
Hardly any need	21 16.8%	40 16.9%	13 18.3%	13 17.1%	19 18.1%	35 16.6%	28 15.3%	12 14.0%	20 14.1%	9 12.2%	60
Not needed	5 4.0%	11 4.6%	6 8.5%	2 2.6%	4 3.8%	9 4.3%	6 3.3%	2 2.3%	3 2.1%	1 1.4%	12
Total	125	237	71	76	105	211	183	86	142	74	439

Table 116: Cross tabulation of “project management” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Great need	53 42.7%	82 34.3%	21 29.6%	24 31.6%	37 35.6%	80 37.6%	76 40.9%	26 29.9%	43 30.3%	18 24.0%	150
Moderate need	52 41.9%	111 46.4%	33 46.5%	38 50.0%	46 44.2%	96 45.1%	76 40.9%	39 44.8%	72 50.7%	44 58.7%	211
Hardly any need	15 12.1%	37 15.5%	12 16.9%	11 14.5%	17 16.3%	31 14.6%	29 15.6%	17 19.5%	23 16.2%	11 14.7%	66
Not needed	4 3.2%	9 3.8%	5 7.0%	3 3.9%	4 3.8%	6 2.8%	5 2.7%	5 5.7%	4 2.8%	2 2.7%	14
Total	124	239	71	76	104	213	186	87	142	75	441

Table 117: Cross tabulation of “networking with people” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Great need	35 28.0%	80 33.8%	19 27.1%	27 36.0%	35 33.7%	64 30.5%	53 29.0%	26 30.2%	47 33.1%	27 36.5%	147
Moderate need	67 53.6%	107 45.1%	34 48.6%	35 46.7%	46 44.2%	103 49.0%	94 51.4%	42 48.8%	75 52.8%	39 52.7%	211
Hardly any need	18 14.4%	43 18.1%	11 15.7%	13 17.3%	20 19.2%	37 17.6%	32 17.5%	15 17.4%	18 12.7%	7 9.5%	72
Not needed	5 4.0%	7 3.0%	6 8.6%	0 .0%	3 2.9%	6 2.9%	4 2.2%	3 3.5%	2 1.4%	1 1.4%	9
Total	125	237	70	75	104	210	183	86	142	74	439

Table 118: Cross tabulation of “training others” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Great need	28 22.6%	43 18.5%	15 21.4%	14 18.4%	26 25.2%	40 19.1%	38 20.8%	14 16.5%	32 23.0%	21 28.4%	101
Moderate need	69 55.6%	118 50.6%	38 54.3%	48 63.2%	61 59.2%	112 53.6%	100 54.6%	43 50.6%	80 57.6%	37 50.0%	220
Hardly any need	24 19.4%	59 25.3%	12 17.1%	11 14.5%	13 12.6%	46 22.0%	36 19.7%	22 25.9%	24 17.3%	11 14.9%	91
Not needed	3 2.4%	13 5.6%	5 7.1%	3 3.9%	3 2.9%	11 5.3%	9 4.9%	6 7.1%	3 2.2%	5 6.8%	24
Total	124	233	70	76	103	209	183	85	139	74	436

Table 119: Cross tabulation of “administration and finances” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Great need	14 11.3%	23 9.8%	4 5.7%	5 6.6%	11 10.6%	19 9.1%	21 11.7%	7 8.2%	15 10.8%	6 8.2%	47
Moderate need	61 49.2%	110 46.8%	31 44.3%	45 59.2%	50 48.1%	104 50.0%	87 48.3%	39 45.9%	72 51.8%	36 49.3%	213
Hardly any need	39 31.5%	81 34.5%	27 38.6%	23 30.3%	35 33.7%	69 33.2%	60 33.3%	33 38.8%	42 30.2%	24 32.9%	140
Not needed	10 8.1%	21 8.9%	8 11.4%	3 3.9%	8 7.7%	16 7.7%	12 6.7%	6 7.1%	10 7.2%	7 9.6%	30
Total	124	235	70	76	104	208	180	85	139	73	430

Training needs with regard to digital preservation-specific and technical skills – Frequency tables

Table 120: General knowledge / basic knowledge of digital preservation issues

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	287	63.2	64.5	64.5
	Moderate need	125	27.5	28.1	92.6
	Hardly any need	26	5.7	5.8	98.4
	Not needed	7	1.5	1.6	100.0
	Total	445	98.0	100.0	
Missing	Total*	9	2.0		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 7 no answer: 2

Table 121: Preservation and data management planning

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	285	62.8	64.3	64.3
	Moderate need	141	31.1	31.8	96.2
	Hardly any need	15	3.3	3.4	99.5
	Not needed	2	.4	.5	100.0
	Total	443	97.6	100.0	
Missing	Total*	11	2.4		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 8, no answer: 3

Table 122: Preservation tools

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	263	57.9	59.5	59.5
	Moderate need	155	34.1	35.1	94.6
	Hardly any need	22	4.8	5.0	99.5
	Not needed	2	.4	.5	100.0
	Total	442	97.4	100.0	
Missing	Total*	12	2.6		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 7, no answer: 5

Table 123: Information modelling and metadata

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	230	50.7	52.3	52.3
	Moderate need	179	39.4	40.7	93.0
	Hardly any need	27	5.9	6.1	99.1
	Not needed	4	.9	.9	100.0
	Total	440	96.9	100.0	
Missing	Total*	14	3.1		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 13, no answer: 1

Table 124: Trusted repositories

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	204	44.9	46.8	46.8
	Moderate need	198	43.6	45.4	92.2
	Hardly any need	29	6.4	6.7	98.9
	Not needed	5	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	436	96.0	100.0	
Missing	Total*	18	4.0		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 15, no answer: 3

Table 125: Strategic planning and policies

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	195	43.0	43.8	43.8
	Moderate need	194	42.7	43.6	87.4
	Hardly any need	51	11.2	11.5	98.9
	Not needed	5	1.1	1.1	100.0
	Total	445	98.0	100.0	
Missing	Total*	9	2.0		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 1, no answer: 9

Table 126: Technical systems

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	185	40.7	41.9	41.9
	Moderate need	217	47.8	49.1	91.0
	Hardly any need	37	8.1	8.4	99.3
	Not needed	3	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	442	97.4	100.0	
Missing	Total*	12	2.6		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 10, no answer: 2

Table 127: Legal aspects

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Great need	175	38.5	39.5	39.5
	Moderate need	207	45.6	46.7	86.2
	Hardly any need	52	11.5	11.7	98.0
	Not needed	9	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	443	97.6	100.0	
Missing	Total*	11	2.4		
Total		454	100.0		

* I don't know: 8, no answer: 3

Training needs with regard to digital preservation-specific and technical skills – Cross tabulations

Table 128: Cross tabulation of “general/ basic knowledge of digital preservation issues” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	39 59.1%	61 57.5%	33 70.2%	68 63.0%	54 66.7%	35 70.0%	73 68.9%	287
Moderate need	21 31.8%	34 32.1%	12 25.5%	29 26.9%	24 29.6%	10 20.0%	25 23.6%	125
Hardly any need	4 6.1%	8 7.5%	2 4.3%	8 7.4%	3 3.7%	4 8.0%	6 5.7%	26
Not needed	2 3.0%	3 2.8%	0 .0%	3 2.8%	0 .0%	1 2.0%	2 1.9%	7
Total	66	106	47	108	81	50	106	445

Table 129: Cross tabulation of “preservation and data management planning” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	43 65.2%	66 64.1%	28 59.6%	75 68.8%	55 67.9%	30 58.8%	65 61.3%	285
Moderate need	21 31.8%	32 31.1%	17 36.2%	31 28.4%	24 29.6%	19 37.3%	35 33.0%	141
Hardly any need	1 1.5%	4 3.9%	2 4.3%	2 1.8%	2 2.5%	2 3.9%	5 4.7%	15
Not needed	1 1.5%	1 1.0%	0 .0%	1 .9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .9%	2
Total	66	103	47	109	81	51	106	443

Table 130: Cross tabulation of “digital preservation tools” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	34 52.3%	62 60.2%	29 61.7%	71 65.7%	53 65.4%	30 58.8%	59 55.7%	263
Moderate need	27 41.5%	36 35.0%	13 27.7%	32 29.6%	23 28.4%	20 39.2%	40 37.7%	155
Hardly any need	3 4.6%	3 2.9%	5 10.6%	5 4.6%	5 6.2%	1 2.0%	7 6.6%	22
Not needed	1 1.5%	2 1.9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Total	65	103	47	108	81	51	106	442

Table 131: Cross tabulation of “information modelling and metadata” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	33 50.0%	51 49.0%	23 50.0%	60 55.6%	43 53.8%	27 52.9%	52 50.0%	230
Moderate need	29 43.9%	44 42.3%	19 41.3%	40 37.0%	32 40.0%	19 37.3%	45 43.3%	179
Hardly any need	2 3.0%	6 5.8%	3 6.5%	7 6.5%	4 5.0%	4 7.8%	7 6.7%	27
Not needed	2 3.0%	3 2.9%	1 2.2%	1 .9%	1 1.3%	1 2.0%	0 .0%	4
Total	66	104	46	108	80	51	104	440

Table 132: Cross tabulation of “trusted repositories” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	29 44.6%	42 41.2%	20 43.5%	58 54.7%	39 48.1%	24 47.1%	42 40.0%	204
Moderate need	29 44.6%	52 51.0%	20 43.5%	39 36.8%	37 45.7%	25 49.0%	51 48.6%	198
Hardly any need	6 9.2%	7 6.9%	5 10.9%	7 6.6%	5 6.2%	2 3.9%	9 8.6%	29
Not needed	1 1.5%	1 1.0%	1 2.2%	2 1.9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	3 2.9%	5
Total	65	102	46	106	81	51	105	436

Table 133: Cross tabulation of “strategic planning and policies” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	29 43.9%	42 40.0%	18 38.3%	48 44.0%	39 48.1%	21 41.2%	48 45.3%	195
Moderate need	30 45.5%	46 43.8%	21 44.7%	46 42.2%	30 37.0%	22 43.1%	45 42.5%	194
Hardly any need	5 7.6%	16 15.2%	7 14.9%	13 11.9%	12 14.8%	8 15.7%	11 10.4%	51
Not needed	2 3.0%	1 1.0%	1 2.1%	2 1.8%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 1.9%	5
Total	66	105	47	109	81	51	106	445

Table 134: Cross tabulation of “technical systems” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	25 38.5%	51 49.5%	24 51.1%	46 42.6%	28 35.0%	27 52.9%	36 33.6%	185
Moderate need	35 53.8%	43 41.7%	17 36.2%	53 49.1%	47 58.8%	18 35.3%	59 55.1%	217
Hardly any need	4 6.2%	7 6.8%	6 12.8%	8 7.4%	5 6.3%	6 11.8%	11 10.3%	37
Not needed	1 1.5%	2 1.9%	0 .0%	1 .9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 .9%	3
Total	65	103	47	108	80	51	107	442

Table 135: Cross tabulation of “legal aspects” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
Great need	23 35.4%	47 45.6%	21 44.7%	45 41.3%	34 42.5%	23 46.0%	40 37.0%	175
Moderate need	33 50.8%	42 40.8%	20 42.6%	50 45.9%	36 45.0%	21 42.0%	49 45.4%	207
Hardly any need	7 10.8%	12 11.7%	4 8.5%	12 11.0%	10 12.5%	6 12.0%	15 13.9%	52
Not needed	2 3.1%	2 1.9%	2 4.3%	2 1.8%	0 .0%	0 .0%	4 3.7%	9
Total	65	103	47	109	80	50	108	443

Table 136: Cross tabulation of “general/ basic knowledge of digital preservation issues” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	87 74.4%	16 41.0%	126 63.0%	32 57.1%	23 82.1%	284 64.5%
Moderate need	26 22.2%	16 41.0%	60 30.0%	19 33.9%	3 10.7%	124 28.2%
Hardly any need	4 3.4%	5 12.8%	11 5.5%	5 8.9%	0 .0%	25 5.7%
Not needed	0 .0%	2 5.1%	3 1.5%	0 .0%	2 7.1%	7 1.6%
Total	117 100.0%	39 100.0%	200 100.0%	56 100.0%	28 100.0%	440 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 137: Cross tabulation of “preservation and data management planning” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	76 64.4%	27 69.2%	122 61.6%	35 63.6%	22 78.6%	282 64.4%
Moderate need	35 29.7%	9 23.1%	70 35.4%	19 34.5%	6 21.4%	139 31.7%
Hardly any need	6 5.1%	3 7.7%	5 2.5%	1 1.8%	0 .0%	15 3.4%
Not needed	1 .8%	0 .0%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 .5%
Total	118 100.0%	39 100.0%	198 100.0%	55 100.0%	28 100.0%	438 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 138: Cross tabulation of “preservation tools” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	65 55.6%	24 61.5%	116 58.6%	33 60.0%	23 82.1%	261 59.7%
Moderate need	41 35.0%	14 35.9%	73 36.9%	20 36.4%	5 17.9%	153 35.0%
Hardly any need	10 8.5%	1 2.6%	8 4.0%	2 3.6%	0 .0%	21 4.8%
Not needed	1 .9%	0 .0%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2 .5%
Total	117 100.0%	39 100.0%	198 100.0%	55 100.0%	28 100.0%	437 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 139: Cross tabulation of “information modelling and metadata” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	61 51.7%	16 41.0%	107 54.3%	25 46.3%	19 67.9%	228 52.3%
Moderate need	44 37.3%	20 51.3%	78 39.6%	26 48.1%	9 32.1%	177 40.6%
Hardly any need	12 10.2%	2 5.1%	10 5.1%	3 5.6%	0 .0%	27 6.2%
Not needed	1 .8%	1 2.6%	2 1.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	4 .9%
Total	118 100.0%	39 100.0%	197 100.0%	54 100.0%	28 100.0%	436 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 140: Cross tabulation of “trusted repositories” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	57 49.1%	8 20.5%	97 50.0%	21 38.9%	19 67.9%	202 46.9%
Moderate need	48 41.4%	27 69.2%	84 43.3%	28 51.9%	9 32.1%	196 45.5%
Hardly any need	10 8.6%	3 7.7%	10 5.2%	5 9.3%	0 .0%	28 6.5%
Not needed	1 .9%	1 2.6%	3 1.5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	5 1.2%
Total	116 100.0%	39 100.0%	194 100.0%	54 100.0%	28 100.0%	431 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 141: Cross tabulation of “strategic planning and policies” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	61 51.7%	13 33.3%	91 45.5%	16 29.1%	11 39.3%	192 43.6%
Moderate need	43 36.4%	21 53.8%	84 42.0%	28 50.9%	17 60.7%	193 43.9%
Hardly any need	12 10.2%	5 12.8%	23 11.5%	10 18.2%	0 .0%	50 11.4%
Not needed	2 1.7%	0 .0%	2 1.0%	1 1.8%	0 .0%	5 1.1%
Total	118 100.0%	39 100.0%	200 100.0%	55 100.0%	28 100.0%	440 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 142: Cross tabulation of “technical systems” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	47 39.8%	13 33.3%	86 43.0%	25 48.1%	12 42.9%	183 41.9%
Moderate need	58 49.2%	24 61.5%	95 47.5%	23 44.2%	15 53.6%	215 49.2%
Hardly any need	12 10.2%	2 5.1%	17 8.5%	4 7.7%	1 3.6%	36 8.2%
Not needed	1 .8%	0 .0%	2 1.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	3 .7%
Total	118 100.0%	39 100.0%	200 100.0%	52 100.0%	28 100.0%	437 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 143: Cross tabulation of “legal aspects” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
Great need	56 47.1%	13 32.5%	81 40.9%	15 27.8%	9 33.3%	174 39.7%
Moderate need	48 40.3%	21 52.5%	89 44.9%	31 57.4%	15 55.6%	204 46.6%
Hardly any need	14 11.8%	6 15.0%	21 10.6%	7 13.0%	3 11.1%	51 11.6%
Not needed	1 .8%	0 .0%	7 3.5%	1 1.9%	0 .0%	9 2.1%
Total	119 100.0%	40 100.0%	198 100.0%	54 100.0%	27 100.0%	438 100.0%

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 144: Cross tabulation of “general/ basic knowledge of digital preservation issues” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Great need	70 55.6%	151 63.2%	34 47.2%	49 63.6%	65 61.9%	125 58.4%	110 58.8%	53 60.2%	88 62.0%	56 75.7%	286
Moderate need	42 33.3%	65 27.2%	29 40.3%	23 29.9%	30 28.6%	65 30.4%	56 29.9%	27 30.7%	45 31.7%	17 23.0%	125
Hardly any need	12 9.5%	20 8.4%	7 9.7%	5 6.5%	8 7.6%	19 8.9%	17 9.1%	6 6.8%	9 6.3%	1 1.4%	26
Not needed	2 1.6%	3 1.3%	2 2.8%	0 .0%	2 1.9%	5 2.3%	4 2.1%	2 2.3%	0 .0%	0 .0%	7
Total	126	239	72	77	105	214	187	88	142	74	444

Table 145: Cross tabulation of “preservation and data management planning” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Great need	84 67.2%	162 67.8%	41 56.9%	48 63.2%	63 60.0%	137 64.3%	112 59.9%	55 62.5%	85 59.9%	51 68.0%	285
Moderate need	36 28.8%	66 27.6%	25 34.7%	24 31.6%	37 35.2%	67 31.5%	67 35.8%	32 36.4%	53 37.3%	22 29.3%	140
Hardly any need	3 2.4%	9 3.8%	5 6.9%	4 5.3%	4 3.8%	7 3.3%	8 4.3%	1 1.1%	4 2.8%	2 2.7%	15
Not needed	2 1.6%	2 .8%	1 1.4%	0 .0%	1 1.0%	2 .9%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Total	125	239	72	76	105	213	187	88	142	75	442

Table 146: Cross tabulation of “preservation tools” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Great need	77 62.1%	145 60.7%	43 60.6%	44 57.9%	59 56.2%	120 56.3%	107 57.2%	49 55.1%	74 52.5%	46 63.0%	263
Moderate need	39 31.5%	85 35.6%	25 35.2%	27 35.5%	40 38.1%	82 38.5%	68 36.4%	35 39.3%	61 43.3%	23 31.5%	154
Hardly any need	7 5.6%	7 2.9%	2 2.8%	5 6.6%	5 4.8%	10 4.7%	11 5.9%	5 5.6%	6 4.3%	4 5.5%	22
Not needed	1 .8%	2 .8%	1 1.4%	0 .0%	1 1.0%	1 .5%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	2
Total	124	239	71	76	105	213	187	89	141	73	441

Table 147: Cross tabulation of “information modelling and metadata” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Great need	73 58.4%	128 53.3%	38 52.8%	44 57.9%	47 44.8%	107 50.0%	89 47.8%	42 48.3%	71 50.7%	39 54.2%	230
Moderate need	45 36.0%	95 39.6%	28 38.9%	27 35.5%	50 47.6%	88 41.1%	80 43.0%	38 43.7%	62 44.3%	30 41.7%	178
Hardly any need	6 4.8%	15 6.3%	5 6.9%	5 6.6%	6 5.7%	16 7.5%	15 8.1%	5 5.7%	6 4.3%	2 2.8%	27
Not needed	1 .8%	2 .8%	1 1.4%	0 .0%	2 1.9%	3 1.4%	2 1.1%	2 2.3%	1 .7%	1 1.4%	4
Total	125	240	72	76	105	214	186	87	140	72	439

Table 148: Cross tabulation of “trusted repositories” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Great need	59 48.0%	113 47.3%	29 40.3%	37 48.7%	38 36.2%	91 42.9%	69 37.7%	34 39.5%	62 45.3%	35 47.3%	203
Moderate need	52 42.3%	105 43.9%	35 48.6%	34 44.7%	55 52.4%	100 47.2%	95 51.9%	48 55.8%	65 47.4%	36 48.6%	198
Hardly any need	7 5.7%	17 7.1%	6 8.3%	5 6.6%	11 10.5%	18 8.5%	17 9.3%	4 4.7%	10 7.3%	3 4.1%	29
Not needed	5 4.1%	4 1.7%	2 2.8%	0 .0%	1 1.0%	3 1.4%	2 1.1%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	5
Total	123	239	72	76	105	212	183	86	137	74	435

Table 149: Cross tabulation of “strategic planning and policies” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/programming	Research	Other	
Great need	59 46.8%	101 42.1%	22 30.6%	31 40.8%	37 35.2%	85 39.7%	71 38.0%	34 38.6%	59 41.5%	31 41.3%	194
Moderate need	54 42.9%	107 44.6%	37 51.4%	36 47.4%	52 49.5%	97 45.3%	87 46.5%	40 45.5%	61 43.0%	36 48.0%	194
Hardly any need	11 8.7%	28 11.7%	12 16.7%	9 11.8%	15 14.3%	30 14.0%	28 15.0%	13 14.8%	20 14.1%	7 9.3%	51
Not needed	2 1.6%	4 1.7%	1 1.4%	0 .0%	1 1.0%	2 .9%	1 .5%	1 1.1%	2 1.4%	1 1.3%	5
Total	126	240	72	76	105	214	187	88	142	75	444

Table 150: Cross tabulation of “technical systems” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Great need	50 40.0%	101 42.3%	24 33.8%	20 26.3%	38 36.2%	77 36.3%	74 40.4%	37 42.5%	49 35.3%	29 39.2%	185
Moderate need	66 52.8%	117 49.0%	40 56.3%	49 64.5%	57 54.3%	113 53.3%	90 49.2%	44 50.6%	81 58.3%	41 55.4%	216
Hardly any need	7 5.6%	19 7.9%	6 8.5%	7 9.2%	9 8.6%	21 9.9%	18 9.8%	6 6.9%	9 6.5%	4 5.4%	37
Not needed	2 1.6%	2 .8%	1 1.4%	0 .0%	1 1.0%	1 .5%	1 .5%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	3
Total	125	239	71	76	105	212	183	87	139	74	441

Table 151: Cross tabulation of “legal aspects” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
Great need	51 40.2%	86 36.0%	26 36.1%	32 42.7%	35 33.3%	74 34.7%	63 34.1%	35 39.3%	55 39.0%	29 39.2%	175
Moderate need	60 47.2%	114 47.7%	35 48.6%	28 37.3%	53 50.5%	100 46.9%	93 50.3%	42 47.2%	64 45.4%	36 48.6%	206
Hardly any need	14 11.0%	34 14.2%	11 15.3%	14 18.7%	16 15.2%	34 16.0%	26 14.1%	11 12.4%	21 14.9%	8 10.8%	52
Not needed	2 1.6%	5 2.1%	0 .0%	1 1.3%	1 1.0%	5 2.3%	3 1.6%	1 1.1%	1 .7%	1 1.4%	9
Total	127	239	72	75	105	213	185	89	141	74	442

Most pressing needs - Cross tabulations
Table 152: Cross tabulation of “most pressing needs” and “type of organisation”

	Type of Organisation							Total
	Ntl., Federal or Legal Deposit Library	Research or University Library	Museum	Archive	University	Research Centre	Other	
General knowledge / basic knowledge of digital preservation issues	26 40.0%	46 43.4%	23 47.9%	55 49.5%	43 53.1%	18 36.7%	57 53.8%	219
Preservation and data management planning	35 53.8%	48 45.3%	21 43.8%	56 50.5%	40 49.4%	17 34.7%	47 44.3%	218
Preservation tools	17 26.2%	48 45.3%	14 29.2%	45 40.5%	36 44.4%	21 42.9%	39 36.8%	171
Information modelling and metadata	21 32.3%	36 34.0%	18 37.5%	35 31.5%	24 29.6%	20 40.8%	33 31.1%	143
Strategic planning and policies	24 36.9%	22 20.8%	11 22.9%	38 34.2%	25 30.9%	10 20.4%	37 34.9%	133
Technical Systems	12 18.5%	23 21.7%	7 14.6%	21 18.9%	16 19.8%	13 26.5%	23 21.7%	92
Trusted repositories	14 21.5%	15 14.2%	14 29.2%	26 23.4%	14 17.3%	15 30.6%	15 14.2%	82
Legal aspects	12 18.5%	25 23.6%	11 22.9%	13 11.7%	13 16.0%	9 18.4%	16 15.1%	71
Coordinating between customers and information technology experts	5 7.7%	11 10.4%	2 4.2%	14 12.6%	5 6.2%	4 8.2%	4 3.8%	39
Project management	8 12.3%	10 9.4%	1 2.1%	7 6.3%	6 7.4%	6 12.2%	11 10.4%	35
Communication	5 7.7%	7 6.6%	2 4.2%	1 .9%	2 2.5%	1 2.0%	5 4.7%	19
Networking with people	2 3.1%	1 .9%	4 8.3%	4 3.6%	1 1.2%	2 4.1%	7 6.6%	18
Training others	3 4.6%	8 7.5%	5 10.4%	3 2.7%	6 7.4%	2 4.1%	3 2.8%	18
Administration and finances	3 4.6%	3 2.8%	1 2.1%	2 1.8%	4 4.9%	1 2.0%	1 .9%	13
Total	65	106	48	111	81	49	106	446

Table 153: Cross tabulation of “most pressing needs” and “countries”

	Countries					Total
	Germany	United Kingdom	Europe*	USA	Other	
General knowledge / basic knowledge of digital preservation issues	70 58.8%	17 40.5%	92 46.2%	22 40.0%	17 65.4%	218
Preservation and data management planning	49 41.2%	24 57.1%	102 51.3%	28 50.9%	11 42.3%	214
Preservation tools	44 37.0%	18 42.9%	67 33.7%	26 47.3%	13 50.0%	168
Information modelling and metadata	32 26.9%	11 26.2%	68 34.2%	21 38.2%	9 34.6%	141
Strategic planning and policies	37 31.1%	16 38.1%	58 29.1%	15 27.3%	6 23.1%	132
Technical Systems	29 24.4%	5 11.9%	41 20.6%	14 25.5%	2 7.7%	91
Trusted repositories	20 16.8%	8 19.0%	37 18.6%	8 14.5%	7 26.9%	80
Legal aspects	20 16.8%	5 11.9%	38 19.1%	6 10.9%	2 7.7%	71
Coordinating between customers and information technology experts	13 10.9%	6 14.3%	14 7.0%	3 5.5%	2 7.7%	38
Project management	6 5.0%	3 7.1%	17 8.5%	8 14.5%	1 3.8%	35
Communication	3 2.5%	1 2.4%	10 5.0%	3 5.5%	2 7.7%	19
Networking with people	2 1.7%	0 .0%	15 7.5%	1 1.8%	0 .0%	18
Training others	4 3.4%	1 2.4%	9 4.5%	3 5.5%	1 3.8%	18
Administration and finances	3 2.5%	1 2.4%	7 3.5%	1 1.8%	1 3.8%	13
Total	119	42	199	55	26	441

*excluding Germany and the UK

Table 154: Cross tabulation of “most pressing needs” and “tasks responsible for”

	Tasks responsible for										Total
	General management	Management for dp/dc	Recruitment of staff	Education of students in dp/dc	Training of practitioners in dp/dc	Workflow planning for dp/dc	Functional tasks in dp/dc	Technical development/ programming	Research	Other	
General knowledge / basic knowledge of digital preservation issues	66 52.0%	112 46.9%	30 41.7%	37 48.7%	51 48.6%	93 43.5%	85 45.5%	42 46.2%	70 50.0%	42 56.0%	219
Preservation and data management planning	72 56.7%	125 52.3%	41 56.9%	38 50.0%	54 51.4%	114 53.3%	89 47.6%	47 51.6%	63 45.0%	33 44.0%	218
Preservation tools	46 36.2%	89 37.2%	28 38.9%	26 34.2%	40 38.1%	82 38.3%	75 40.1%	37 40.7%	52 37.1%	32 42.7%	171
Information modelling and metadata	40 31.5%	84 35.1%	29 40.3%	26 34.2%	35 33.3%	73 34.1%	67 35.8%	37 40.7%	48 34.3%	18 24.0%	143
Strategic planning and policies	44 34.6%	69 28.9%	17 23.6%	20 26.3%	31 29.5%	62 29.0%	53 28.3%	20 22.0%	42 30.0%	25 33.3%	133
Technical Systems	24 18.9%	51 21.3%	10 13.9%	14 18.4%	16 15.2%	45 21.0%	46 24.6%	24 26.4%	30 21.4%	12 16.0%	92
Trusted repositories	19 15.0%	47 19.7%	11 15.3%	17 22.4%	12 11.4%	38 17.8%	28 15.0%	12 13.2%	24 17.1%	20 26.7%	82
Legal aspects	17 13.4%	36 15.1%	14 19.4%	14 18.4%	15 14.3%	38 17.8%	25 13.4%	19 20.9%	27 19.3%	10 13.3%	71
Coordinating between customers and information technology experts	5 3.9%	20 8.4%	8 11.1%	10 13.2%	13 12.4%	23 10.7%	23 12.3%	8 8.8%	17 12.1%	5 6.7%	39
Project management	8 6.3%	18 7.5%	3 4.2%	5 6.6%	12 11.4%	19 8.9%	18 9.6%	7 7.7%	11 7.9%	7 9.3%	35
Communication	3 2.4%	8 3.3%	3 4.2%	2 2.6%	3 2.9%	8 3.7%	9 4.8%	1 1.1%	8 5.7%	5 6.7%	19
Networking with people	3 2.4%	11 4.6%	2 2.8%	3 3.9%	5 4.8%	11 5.1%	10 5.3%	2 2.2%	6 4.3%	1 1.3%	18
Training others	4 3.1%	10 4.2%	7 9.7%	5 6.6%	8 7.6%	9 4.2%	8 4.3%	2 2.2%	7 5.0%	2 2.7%	18
Administration and finances	3 2.4%	4 1.7%	1 1.4%	3 3.9%	5 4.8%	5 2.3%	5 2.7%	2 2.2%	1 .7%	1 1.3%	13
Total	127	239	72	76	105	214	187	91	140	75	446

C. Job advertisement analysis

List of the job advertisements collected (titles and institutions)

United States of America (26)

- Visiting Digital Preservation Coordinator, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
- Digital Archivist, Rutgers University Library
- Scientific Data Curation Specialist/Metadata Librarian, Cornell University Libraries
- Head – Metadata Services, Drexel University Libraries
- Data Management Planning Consultant, John Hopkins University
- Associate Archivist – Institute for Social Research Survey Research Centre (SRC), University of Michigan
- Digital Archivist and Electronic Content Manager, The Archives of the Episcopal Church
- Manager – Data Management Services, John Hopkins University
- Digital Preservation Librarian, University of Iowa Libraries
- Head of Preservation, Ohio University Libraries
- Manton Digital Production Manager, Dartmouth College;
- Project Manager for Program Outreach and Education, The Library of Congress
- Assistant Professor/Digital Initiatives Librarian – Kingston Library, University of Rhode Island
- Director of Digital Scholarship, University of Kentucky Libraries
- Digital Records Archivist – The Eberly Family Special Collections Library, Pennsylvania State University Libraries
- Digital Collections Librarian – Joyner Library, East Carolina University
- Preservation Librarian & Assistant/Associate/Full Professor of Library Administration, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
- Assistant Head – Digital Collections Department, Northwestern University Library
- Data Curation Librarian, University of New Mexico Libraries
- Assistant Professor/Data Management Librarian, Oregon State University
- Science Data Librarian – Branner Library, Stanford University Libraries and Academic Information Resources
- Digital Assets Librarian, Oakland University's Kresge Library
- Digital Repository Coordinator, Iowa State University Library
- National Leadership Grant Project Director – 'Exploring Digital Preservation Solutions for Small and Medium-sized College, University and Research Libraries,' Northern Illinois University Libraries
- Digital Archivist – Presbyterian Historical Society, Presbyterian Church (Philadelphia PA)

United Kingdom (12)

- Timescapes Digital Resources Officer, University of Leeds
- DSpace@Cambridge Research Data and Digital Curation Officer, University of Cambridge
- Clinical Data Manager, Anonymous Leading Biotech Company
- Digital Archivist, The Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Scotland (RCAHMS)
- APARSEN Project Officer, British Library
- Institutional Support Officer (two positions available), University of Edinburgh
- futureArch Graduate Trainee – Bodleian Libraries, University of Oxford
- Digital Preservation Project Officer, National Library of Wales
- Volunteer Opportunity in Web Archiving, British Library
- Project Officer – Digital Communications Enhancement, Library at London School of Economics
- Digital Library Metadata Specialist, Cambridge University Library

Germany (8)

- Research/Scientific Officer – Centre for Information, Media and Communication Technology, University of Trier
- Academic Officer for the conceptual design of a digital archive for complex digital objects – Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Centre of Cultural and General Studies for a soon to be established Competence Centre for Cultural Tradition/Transmission – digital Karlsruhe
- Part-time Professor –Records Management and Audit-Proof Archiving in Commercial Enterprises, Faculty of Information Sciences, University of Applied Sciences Potsdam
- Scientific Officers (two positions available) – Electronic Archive Project, Office of the Federal Commissioner for the Records of the State Security Service of the former German Democratic Republic (BStU)
- Scientific Officers (three positions available) – Development of Infrastructures for Digital Humanities and Research Data Management , Research and Development Department, Goettingen State and University Library

New Zealand (4)

- Senior Advisors – Digital Continuity (three positions; one permanent, one fixed-term parental leave cover and one fixed-term until 26 October 2012)
- Archives New Zealand and Research Data Manager, Landcare Research Manaaki Whenua

Australia (2)

- ANDS Research Data Analyst, Australian National Data Service
- Data Librarian, The University of New South Wales

Canada (1)

- Assistant/Associate/Full Professor – Digital Preservation/Records Management, University of Toronto
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